

Towards sustainable wellbeing: Integrated policies and transformative indicators.

Deliverable 4.2

COMPASS:
A social-ecological macroeconomic model for guiding pathways to equitable human wellbeing within planetary boundaries

WP4 – Modelling wellbeing and sustainability outcomes

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Executive Summary

Escalating socio-ecological crises highlight an urgent need for models that can inform national pathways towards the “Doughnut” – the “safe and just space” where everyone’s needs are met and no planetary boundaries are transgressed. Existing macroeconomic models and integrated assessment models remain limited in their representation of key social and environmental indicators that measure national performance with regards to human needs and planetary boundaries.

This report presents a new, open-source ecological macroeconomic model that seeks to address this gap: COMPASS (Comprehensive Open-source Macroeconomic model of Planetary And Social Sustainability). COMPASS integrates a stock–flow consistent, dynamic input–output macroeconomic model and a multi-cohort demographics model with two novel modules that assess sustainability and wellbeing. The sustainability module calculates seven types of national resource use and pollution and assesses them against planetary boundary indicators. The wellbeing module models 13 indicators of human wellbeing and assesses them against sufficiency thresholds.

Our model is, to our knowledge, the first stock–flow consistent ecological macroeconomic model that endogenously calculates most social and environmental indicators included in national-level representations of the Doughnut of social and planetary boundaries. We propose to classify our model as a first example of a new category of models: a social–ecological macroeconomic model. The model enables holistic assessments of the wellbeing and sustainability impacts of a wide range of social and environmental policies and development pathways, reflecting different sustainability visions such as green growth and post-growth.

About ToBe

ToBe is a 3-year project funded by the European Union through the Horizon Europe framework programme. Tampere University (Finland) acts as a coordinator for the project.

The ToBe project aims at studying the way in which mindsets, indicators, innovations, and policies could better work together towards a sustainability paradigm. The need for moving toward a sustainability paradigm has been widely called for, yet the path to achieving that is not clear. ToBe aims to contribute to filling this gap and create an understanding of a sustainable wellbeing economy through integrated policies and transformative indicators.

The ToBe consortium brings together acknowledged scholars with previous high-quality research on the topic and with diverse backgrounds from social sciences, ecological and political economy, environmental and innovation studies, science and technology, data science, AI and machine learning. All partners represent well-known and established universities, other research institutions and non-governmental organisations (NGOs). Table 1 lists the members of the consortium, which consists of 13 beneficiaries and one associated partner.

Table 1. ToBe Consortium Members

No	Role	Short Name	Legal Name	Country
1	COO	TAU	TAMPEREEN KORKEAKOULUSAATIO SR	FI
2	BEN	SU	STOCKHOLMS UNIVERSITET	SE
3	BEN	VTT	TEKNOLOGIAN TUTKIMUSKESKUS VTT OY	FI
4	BEN	EURADA	ASSOCIATION EUROPEENNE DES AGENCES DE DEVELOPPEMENT	BE
5	BEN	Sciences Po	FONDATION NATIONALE DES SCIENCES POLITIQUES	FR
6	BEN	ICHEC	HAUTE ECOLE ICHEC - ECAM - ISFSC	BE
7	BEN	IPE	INSTITUT ZA POLITICKU EKOLOGIJU	HR
8	BEN	UB	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA	ES
9	BEN	Ugent	UNIVERSITEIT GENT	BE
10	BEN	EPC	EUROPEAN POLICY CENTRE	BE
11	BEN	UAB	UNIVERSIDAD AUTONOMA DE BARCELONA	ES
12	BEN	EPN Ecuador	ESCUELA POLITECNICA NACIONAL	EC
13	BEN	CHAL	CHALMERS TEKNISKA HOGSKOLA AB	SE
14	Associated partner	UnivLeeds	UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS	UK

The main objective of ToBe is to contribute to a clearer understanding of how to move to a sustainability paradigm. More specifically, ToBe aims at achieving the following objectives:

- Construct a theoretical framework for a sustainable wellbeing economy by providing a systemic and dynamic understanding of how changing policy goals, mindsets, indicators, innovations and policies work together towards a sustainability paradigm.
- Identify different processes of economic growth by analysing their social and environmental implications.
- Evaluate and compare alternative growth initiatives as systemic innovations with a focus on drivers and barriers to implementation and impacts.
- Develop an ecological macroeconomic model combining conventional macroeconomic variables with indicators of wellbeing and sustainability to assess policies from a multidimensional perspective, and to reveal the synergies and trade-offs inherent in the transition to sustainability.
- Co-create policy solutions together with stakeholders to help institutionalise the new policies and indicators in Europe and beyond (potentially including South American and African countries).

1 Introduction

Humanity faces multiple interlinked social-ecological crises. Globally, we are already overshooting six planetary boundaries and continue to increase our ecological overshoot year by year, implying severe and escalating risk of climate and ecological breakdown (Richardson et al., 2023; Rockström et al., 2024). At the same time, billions of people remain deprived of basic human needs (Kikstra et al., 2021).

The ecological overshoot is overwhelmingly driven by those with the highest material consumption: the high-income countries of the Global North and wealthy individuals internationally (Hickel, 2020; Hickel et al., 2022; Chancel, 2023; Tian et al., 2024). Conversely, those with low levels of material consumption and thus more sustainable levels of resource use – the low-income countries of the Global South and low-income communities – are often heavily deprived of basic needs (O’Neill et al., 2018; Fanning et al., 2022; Kikstra et al., 2021; Baltruszewicz et al., 2021). Indeed, no country currently meets the basic needs of its population while limiting its resource use and environmental impact to sustainable levels (O’Neill et al., 2018; Fanning et al., 2022). In other words, no country is currently in line with the “safe and just space for humanity”, where all human needs are met and no ecological thresholds exceeded – which Kate Raworth (2017) famously depicts as a doughnut (Figure 1). Current provisioning systems and dominant development trajectories seem to be fundamentally misaligned with the Doughnut and the Sustainable Development Goals (Vogel et al., 2021; Fanning et al., 2022).

Social and environmental goals are, however, not inherently incompatible. Their compatibility depends on the socio-technical and political-economic characteristics of provisioning systems, including factors such as consumption levels and inequality, public service quality, income inequality, democracy, technology, and access to basic utilities and infrastructures (Vogel et al., 2021; Baltruszewicz, 2022; Garnier, 2025; Millward-Hopkins and Oswald, 2023). A wide range of environmental, social, and economic policies has been proposed for getting countries on a pathway towards the Doughnut (Stratford and O’Neill, 2020; Hickel et al., 2022; Fitzpatrick et al., 2022; Jackson, 2017; Vogel et al., 2024).

However, the impact of such policies on key social and environmental outcomes has hardly been studied, largely due to a lack of suitable tools for doing so in the absence of real-world examples or full-scale trials. In particular, while there is much evidence of the environmental unsustainability of mainstream policy paradigms (Vogel and Hickel, 2023; Haberl et al., 2020; Hickel and Kallis, 2020), the social sustainability or wellbeing impact of alternative policy paradigms such as post-growth has been studied qualitatively (Stratford and O’Neill, 2020; Vogel et al., 2024; Wiman, 2024; Hartley et al., 2020) but rarely quantitatively. Existing quantitative studies typically focus on a limited set of social indicators such as employment and income inequality (e.g. D’Alessandro et al., 2020; Jackson and Victor, 2020).

Numerical macroeconomic models are a key tool for exploring alternative future pathways and evaluating policies or provisioning system changes that have no empirical precedent and little scope for full-scale real-world experiments. Models enable us to conduct computational what-if experiments and assess the effects of isolated changes as well as interactions of different changes within a defined scenario context. There is an urgent need for models that can simulate alternative future scenarios involving a wide range of policy changes or policy packages, and assess their impacts on key social, environmental and economic outcomes, while adequately representing the dynamics of social–ecological–economic systems (Van Eynde et al., 2024; Hickel et al., 2022; Jackson et al., 2014, 2016; Victor and Jackson, 2020).

Three model capabilities seem particularly important for informing the socio-ecological challenges of our times. The first capability is to “model what matters” (Van Eynde et al., 2024), i.e. to model performance indicators for the irreducible sets of human needs (Doyal and Gough, 1991), planetary boundaries

Figure 1: The Doughnut of social and planetary boundaries. The Doughnut depicts the "safe and just space for humanity", where basic needs of the entire population are met (the social foundation) while environmental pressures remain within planetary boundaries (the ecological ceiling). Graphic reproduced from Doughnut Economics Action Lab, based on Raworth (2017).

(Rockstrom et al., 2024), and other non-substitutable elements of wellbeing and sustainability (Raworth, 2017; O’Neill et al., 2018). A comprehensive representation of these indicators is important for holistically assessing policy impacts and understanding potential blind spots, trade-offs, synergies, or interdependencies between policies. The second capability is to simulate a broad range of alternative policies, trends, or shocks across both growth-based and post-growth paradigms (Hickel et al., 2021, 2022; Keysser and Lenzen, 2021; Victor and Jackson, 2020; Kikstra et al., 2024). The third capability is to adequately represent social–ecological–economic systems, with regards to ecological principles, environmental accounting, sound economic theory, stock–flow consistent macroeconomic accounting, and macroeconomic as well as system-wide feedback mechanisms (Jackson et al., 2014; 2016; Victor and Jackson, 2020). It is important to combine these capabilities in the same model (rather than assessing different aspects with different models), to ensure consistency across policies, scenarios, and domains (social, environmental, economic), and account for feedbacks between these domains.

An increasing number of models address different parts of this challenge, with different strengths and weaknesses, but no existing model possesses all three capabilities satisfactorily (Van Eynde et al., 2024; Edwards et al., 2025; Lauer et al., 2025; Wiebe et al., 2023, Hardt and O’Neill, 2017). For example, the EUROGREEN model (D’Alessandro et al., 2020) features a detailed representation of the economy including a multi-sector input-output structure and remarkable granularity in its representation of the labour market and household types but is limited in its representation of social indicators and environmental indicators beyond greenhouse gas emissions. Similarly, the LowGrow-SFC model (Jackson and Victor, 2020) offers a strong representation of the economy with a sophisticated financial sector and investment structure but is also limited in its representation of environmental indicators and non-economic social indicators. Dafermos et al.’s (2017) stock-flow-fund ecological macroeconomic model offers a detailed representation of financial and environmental processes but does not consider wellbeing indicators beyond standard economic ones such as employment and income inequality. The MEDEAS and pymedeas models (Capellan-Perez et al., 2020; Solé et al., 2020) feature comprehensive representations of the energy system, greenhouse gas emissions, land use, and material use alongside impressive sectoral detail but are also limited in their representation of social indicators.

By contrast, neoclassical Integrated Assessment Models (IAMC, 2020), while often providing a detailed representation of multiple environmental indicators, not only lack non-economic wellbeing indicators but also have been criticized for their unrealistic representation of key macroeconomic dynamics and realities (e.g. Keen, 2011). An interesting exception is the iSDG model (Millenium Institute, 2021), as it simulates an impressive range of both environmental and social indicators. However, as it centres on a neoclassical macroeconomic model, it also inherits some of the issues that these models have been criticised for.

In summary, to our knowledge, there is to date no single, integrated model of the environment–society–economy system that (1) represents the full set of human wellbeing and planetary boundaries indicators (Van Eynde et al., 2024), (2) is able to simulate post-growth pathways (Edwards et al., 2025), and (3) reflects sound ecological macroeconomics principles and theory (Jackson et al., 2016; Victor and Jackson, 2020).

This report presents a new system dynamics model that seeks to address this gap and advance our capabilities to simulate integrated social–ecological–economic dynamics: COMPASS (Comprehensive Open-source Macroeconomic model of Planetary and Social Sustainability). COMPASS integrates a stock–flow consistent, demand-driven, dynamic input–output macroeconomic model and a multi-cohort demographics model with two novel modules: a sustainability module and a wellbeing module. The sustainability module calculates seven types of territorial resource use or pollution, assesses five of them against national fair shares

of the corresponding planetary boundary indicators or other sustainability benchmarks, and simulates three types of impacts of environmental change on society. The wellbeing module incorporates 13 indicators of human wellbeing and human need satisfaction and assesses them against sufficiency thresholds for minimum acceptable performance. Our model is thus to our knowledge the first stock-flow-consistent ecological macroeconomic model that endogenously calculates almost all social indicators and most environmental indicators included in national-level representations of the Doughnut of social and planetary boundaries (O’Neill et al., 2018; Fanning et al., 2022). Given that it goes beyond most existing ecological macroeconomic models in particular in terms of its comprehensive representation of social indicators, our model could be seen as a first example of a new category of models: a social-ecological macroeconomic model.

The model enables holistic assessments of the wellbeing and sustainability impacts of a wide range of national social, economic, and environmental policies (e.g. working time reduction, carbon tax and dividend) and development pathways reflecting different sustainability visions (e.g. green growth and post-growth). Doing so could reveal important trade-offs, synergies or blind spots, for example by identifying indirect impacts of environmental or social policies via environmental or macroeconomic feedbacks. Furthermore, the model also facilitates calculating composite measures of progress and comparing their behaviour under different policy scenarios against the behaviour of the Doughnut indicators. Finally, to support uptake, engagement, and collaborations without financial or institutional barriers, the model is open source, i.e. it is implemented in open source software and language, and the model code will be made publicly available.

The remainder of this report is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a high-level, non-technical overview of the model. Sections 3-6 provide detailed and more technical descriptions of the wellbeing module, the sustainability module, the economy module, and the demographics module, respectively. Section 7 provides an overview of the policy levers currently implemented in the model. Section 8 discusses limitations of the model and outlines avenues for future research and improvements. Section 9 concludes.

2 Model Overview

The COMPASS Model is an ecological macroeconomic model that dynamically simulates national-level social, environmental, and economic outcomes for a range of policies and future pathways. We propose to categorise it as a social-ecological macroeconomic model.

The purpose of the model is to holistically assess the impact of national policy choices on human wellbeing and ecological sustainability, and to inform national pathways towards the “safe and just space” where the needs of all people are met while keeping resource use and pollution to sustainable levels. To do so, the model simulates national-level environmental and social indicators of the Doughnut of social and planetary boundaries (O’Neill et al., 2018; Raworth, 2017) and a wide range of environmental, social, and economic policies (e.g. worktime reduction, carbon tax) across different sustainability visions (including green growth and post-growth).

The model combines a stock-flow consistent Post-Keynesian (demand-driven) macroeconomic core with a multi-sector, environmentally extended input-output structure in a system dynamics framework. It dynamically integrates four modules representing the monetised economy, demographics, sustainability, and wellbeing, with both economic and biophysical flows between the modules, and trade flows with an aggregate “rest of the world” foreign economy (Figure 2).

Figure 2: High-level overview of the COMPASS Model. The model dynamically integrates an economy module (yellow boxes), a demographics module (brown box), a sustainability module (green boxes), and a wellbeing module (blue boxes). Economic and biophysical flows (blue arrows) link the modules and connect the national economy to an aggregate “rest of the world” foreign economy.

The COMPASS Model covers a broad range of social and environmental outcomes, going beyond the scope of most existing models (Van Eynde et al., 2024). It incorporates five biophysical boundaries (related to four planetary boundary indicators), three environmental feedback mechanisms, and 13 indicators of human wellbeing and other social goals (Figure 3). It thus represents almost the complete set of national-level social and environmental indicators of the Doughnut of social and planetary boundaries (Fanning et al., 2021; O’Neill et al., 2018; Raworth, 2017).

Figure 3: The COMPASS Model simulates a broad range of national-level environmental and social outcomes included in O’Neill et al.’s (2018) operationalisation of Raworth’s (2017) Doughnut of social and planetary boundaries. The model incorporates five environmental indicators related to the ecological ceiling (planetary boundaries and other sustainability thresholds) and 13 social indicators related to the social foundation (human need and wellbeing thresholds) of the Doughnut’s “safe and just space”. The graphic shows a 2030 snapshot for a BusinessAsUsual scenario for Spain.

2.1 Main elements and high-level dynamics

The main elements of the COMPASS Model and the flows between them are summarized in Figure 4.

The main dynamics of the model are driven by the economy module, in interaction with population dynamics coming from the demographics module.

The economy module calculates key economic variables such as GDP, output, demand, employment, disposable income (and its distribution), trade, and inflation, which in turn drive environmental outcomes (sustainability module) and social outcomes (wellbeing module). Domestic (national) production and investment is driven by demand for domestic final goods or services, i.e. domestic producers (firms) produce the amount of goods and services required to satisfy the demand from domestic and foreign households and governments, plus the intermediate goods or services that other producers require to produce the goods or services demanded from them. Producers in turn invest as much and employ as many people as is required to produce the demanded amount of goods and services. Employment, income distribution, demand, GDP, and output are also affected by the labour supply, working-age population, and the number of pensioners, which are calculated in the demographics module, based on population dynamics that, in turn, are affected by economic outcomes and environmental feedbacks.

On the environmental side, economic output and resource and pollution intensities drive national resource use (material, energy, freshwater) and pollution (CO₂ emissions, nitrogen fixation, phosphorus fixation, air pollution). These environmental outcomes are assessed against national fair shares of planetary boundaries and other sustainability benchmarks (Fanning et al., 2021; O'Neill et al., 2018). Environmental feedbacks implemented in the model include climate change impacts on mortality and economic activity as well as air pollution impacts on mortality.

On the social side, the wellbeing module calculates life satisfaction, life expectancy, nutrition, sanitation, access to energy, education, income fairness, income adequacy, job availability, gender equality, social support, and democratic quality. These wellbeing outcomes are driven by a combination of economic outcomes (GDP per capita, (un)employment, household and government demand, and income distribution), demographic outcomes (population distribution, mortality rates), interactions between wellbeing indicators, and several exogenous variables. Wellbeing outcomes are assessed against social thresholds of minimum acceptable performance (Fanning et al., 2021; O'Neill et al., 2018).

The model encompasses a range of scenario parameters that can be varied to explore different scenarios, including policy changes, trends, and shocks. Currently implemented policy levers include worktime reduction, stronger progressive taxation, a living income, and a carbon tax. Economic shocks can be simulated by changing the propensity to consume (e.g. recession) or government final demand (e.g. public investment or austerity), for example. Furthermore, technological change or changes in provisioning systems can be emulated in a simplified way by exogenously varying the growth rates of labour productivity, resource intensities and pollution intensities. Other key parameters that can be varied exogenously include net migration rates, fertility rates, as well as the global climate change scenario.

Figure 4: Detailed overview of the COMPASS Model. The model dynamically simulates social, environmental, and economic outcomes for a range of future pathways by integrating an economy module (yellow boxes), a demographics module (brown boxes), a sustainability module (green boxes), and a wellbeing module (blue boxes) in a stock-flow-consistent input-output system dynamics framework. Information flows between the modules or sub-modules are shown by blue arrows annotated with the relevant variable names.

2.2 Overview and qualitative behaviour of the four modules

2.2.1 The economy module: qualitative behaviour

The economy module represents a national economy through five stylised economic agents (firms, individuals, the government, a commercial bank, and the central bank), while accounting for trade flows with an aggregated “rest of the world” foreign economy. Production and consumption are disaggregated into six sectors: energy supply, agriculture, healthcare, mobility, education, and “other sectors” (which also serves as a capital sector). Disposable income and household demand are disaggregated by employment status (role in production) and social groups (gender and skill level).

In the economy module, domestic production is driven by expected final demand (demand for domestic final goods or services), which is the sum of (i) domestic household demand for domestic final goods and services, (ii) domestic government demand for domestic final goods or services, (iii) investments (domestic demand for domestic capital goods), and (iv) exports (foreign demand for domestic final and intermediate goods or services and capital goods).

Using an input-output structure (the “production recipes”) and final demand for each sector, the economy module calculates the intermediate demand for each sector (the inputs required to produce the demanded final goods and services). Total demand for a given sector is then simply the sum of final and intermediate demand for that sector.

Total demand for a given sector determines the sector’s desired output, i.e. sectors produce as much as is needed to meet expected demand, taking into account inventories. Each sector determines its investments based on how much additional capital it needs (after accounting for capital depreciation) to be able to produce the desired output at a target capital utilization level. Investments are partly financed through retained profits and partly through loans, which currently do not bear interest and are granted without constraints on total or sectoral lending. A sector’s desired output also determines how many people it seeks to employ, depending on average sectoral working hours, labour supply, capital stock and the availability of the other intermediate inputs of production.

Household final demand is determined by disposable income (gross income minus taxes) and the propensity to consume (which in the current implementation does not vary with income or wealth levels). An individual’s gross income (pre-tax income) depends primarily on their employment status, i.e. whether they receive wages, unemployment benefits, pensions, and/or capital income, in addition to other social benefits. Wages also vary by sector (depending on sectoral working hours) and social group (depending on the initial wage distribution), and change over time as a function of employment rates, as a proxy for bargaining power. An individual’s tax payments depend on their gross income, with different marginal tax rates to different portions of their gross income (progressive tax system), such that effective tax rates differ with an individual’s gross income. Unemployment benefits and pensions are each calculated as a fraction of average wages (and are thus uniform across social groups), with pensions moreover changing with the ratio of the number of pensioners to the working-age population. Other social benefits can be modified for each employment status via scenario parameters reflecting a lever for (re)distributive fiscal policy.

Government final demand and exports change endogenously as a function of total population, while especially the former can also be varied exogenously, reflecting policy change.

Prices for each sector are determined based on sector-specific wage rates, labour intensities (working hours required per unit of output), technical coefficients (inputs required per unit of output), the prices of these inputs, and mark-ups. For simplicity, mark-ups and technical coefficients are currently kept constant,

and mark-ups are applied uniformly to all production (which also implies that all production is performed by profit-making firms). Profits are partly retained for reinvestment and partly distributed as dividends to the capitalist class (within this class, currently on an equal per capita basis).

The monetary stock-flow consistency of the model is ensured by a set of accounting equations for monetary stocks and flows, summarized in a balance sheet matrix and a transaction matrix, respectively. The basic principle is that all monetary assets have a liability counterpart, and all monetary transactions balance to zero across economic agents, i.e. deducting from one variable adds to another. The creation, circulation and destruction of money is thus explicitly represented through macroeconomic accounting. Flow variables in the economy module are reported, as appropriate, in nominal terms (market prices in each year), in deflated terms (market prices in each year, corrected for inflation), and/or in real terms (market prices in each year divided by the price level of a reference year, reflecting quantities of a sector’s output understood as a single type of good).

2.2.2 The demographics module

The demographics module calculates changes in the population size and the population distribution across gender and four age groups. For each gender and age group, changes in the size of this subpopulation are calculated as the balance of deaths, net migration, births (for the youngest age group only), and transfers between age groups (people “ageing out” of one age group and “ageing into” another). While future birth rates and net migration rates are projected exogenously, mortality rates are calculated endogenously for each age group and gender, as a function of endogenously calculated air pollution, the share of private healthcare, and the size of the healthcare sector (total healthcare output per capita, healthcare workers per capita), as well as exogenous projections of mortality contributions from specific causes of death. These “gross” mortality rates are finally adjusted by a “heat death multiplier” that accounts for excess heat-related mortality due to climate change, which is determined by the exogenously chosen global climate change scenario. Changes in total population are calculated bottom-up by aggregating the changes in the subgroup populations. Several aspects of the population distribution (e.g. the working age population and thus the potential labour force, as well as the number of pensioners) affect economic outcomes.

2.2.3 The sustainability module

The sustainability module endogenously calculates domestic (national-territorial) resource use and pollution in relation to planetary boundaries and other sustainability benchmarks, as well as impacts of environmental change on society. The module maps EXIOBASE3 data (Stadler et al., 2021) for historical sectoral resource use and pollution onto the six economic sectors in our model, and combines these with EXIOBASE3 historical sectoral output data (in real terms) to calculate historical sectoral resource or pollution intensity of output (e.g. CO₂ emissions per quantity of energy output produced). Projecting these intensities into the future based on exogenously defined intensity growth rates, the module then calculates future sectoral resource use and pollution by multiplying these intensities with sectoral real output (thus converting economic flow variables into biophysical flow variables). Aggregating across sectors and dividing by population (calculated in the demographics module) yields total per-capita domestic resource use or pollution, which is then assessed against national fair shares (here, equal per capita shares) of the corresponding planetary boundaries or other sustainability thresholds (Fanning et al., 2021; O’Neill et al., 2018). Finally, the module calculates environmental feedbacks (the impacts of environmental change on society) in terms of climate change impacts

on mortality rates (Kendrovski et al., 2017) and economic activity (Kotz et al., 2024; Neal et al., 2025) as well as air pollution impacts on mortality rates.

2.2.4 The wellbeing module

The wellbeing module calculates 13 key social indicators related to wellbeing, human needs, and social goals. Job availability, income fairness, income adequacy, and gender equality are calculated directly from the unemployment rate and income distribution (both of which calculated endogenously in the economy module). Life expectancy is calculated directly from mortality rates calculated endogenously in the demographics module. Nutrition is parameterized as a function of endogenously calculated household final demand for the agricultural sector. Sanitation, education, connectivity, life satisfaction, social support, and democratic quality are each calculated based on econometric estimations. They are driven by endogenous social, economic, and demographic variables in the model, and a range of exogenous variables. Finally, access to energy is calculated exogenously by linear extrapolation of its historical trend. Each social indicator is assessed against an adequacy threshold that reflects minimum acceptable performance on this indicator (based broadly on O’Neill et al., 2018).

2.3 Technical notes

2.3.1 Implementation and open-source software

The COMPASS Model is implemented in a continuous-time formulation, allowing high and flexible temporal resolution. It is currently parameterized, initialized, and being calibrated for Spain. Because many aspects of the parameterization and initialization are generic or data-driven, the model could be applied to other countries relatively easily, given appropriate data. The present implementation and calibration of the model is however a preliminary version that involves a number of simplifications. Key limitations as well as potential additions and improvements are discussed in Section 8.

The model is implemented in the open-source language Julia, primarily using the software package ModelingToolkit (Ma et al., 2022). The model code will be made publicly available on GitHub upon publication of the academic article that we seek to produce based on this report.

2.3.2 Notation conventions for variables and parameters

The notation of variables and parameters in the model follow a specific naming convention. For the sake of understandability, we chose to use descriptive names for the variables and parameters, instead of mathematical symbols. In general we don't use acronyms, with a few exceptions that are summarised in the table below.

Acronym	Description
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
LCU	Local Currency Unit
PPP	Purchasing Power Parity
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
PM2.5/PM25	Particulate Matter with a diameter of 2.5 micrometers or less
PC	Per Capita
AROPHR	At-risk-of-poverty headcount ratio

Variables that have one or multiple dimensions are subscripted by an index for each of the respective dimensions. When a variable has multiple dimensions, the subscripts are ordered alphabetically. Each index has a shorthand notation of two or three letters, which is used in the variable subscripts. The table below lists the indices used in the model.

Index name	Shorthand notation	Description
ageGroups	ag	The different age groups
genders	ge	The genders (or more accurately, sexes)
sectors	se	The different sectors of the economy
expandedSectors	ese	The expanded sectors of the economy, which consists of the original sectors plus a sector for final capital goods
socialGroups	sg	The different social groups, which are defined by the combination of genders and three skill levels
employmentStatus	es	The employment status for people in the adult population
sharedSocioeconomicPathways	sp	The shared socioeconomic pathways, which are used to define the scenarios
skillLevels	sk	The three skill levels for people in the adult population
lifeYears	ly	The different life years, required for the life expectancy calculations
lagsTemperature	lt	The lags used for the temperature variables when computing climate damages
lagsPrecipitation	lp	The lags used for the precipitation variables when computing climate damages
airPollutants	ap	The different types of air pollutants
taxBrackets	tb	The tax brackets used in the model
greenhouseGases	gg	The different types of greenhouse gases

So for instance, $domesticCO2_{se}$ is the domestic CO₂ emissions per sector, while $domesticCO2$ is the total domestic CO₂ emissions. The variable $disposableIncomePC_{es,sg}$ tracks the disposable income per capita for each combination of employment status and social group, while $disposableIncomePC'_{sg}$ tracks the disposable income per capita for each social group, regardless of employment status.

When referring to a specific value for an index, we subscript the variable with that specific value. So for instance, $domesticCO2_{agriculture}$ represents the domestic CO₂ emissions for the agriculture sector, or $disposableIncomePC_{employed,maleLowSkill}$ represents the disposable income per capita for the male low skilled population that is employed.

In general, parameters are considered to be constant, while variables are time-dependent. By default we do not mention the time-dependency of the variables in the equations. When time is not mentioned, it is implied that an equation holds for all time periods of the simulation.

In cases where the time-dependency of a variable is important, we use the notation $variable(t)$ to refer to the value of $variable$ at time t . For instance, $domesticCO2(0)$ refers to the historical value of the domestic CO₂ emissions at the start time of the simulation, while $domesticCO2(t - 2)$ refers to the value of the domestic CO₂ emissions at time $t - 2$.

3 Documentation of the Wellbeing Module

3.1 Module behaviour

The Wellbeing module estimates social outcomes in 13 key dimensions of wellbeing and human needs.

The selection of social indicators is primarily based on the 'safe and just space for humanity', also known as the 'Doughnut' framework of social and planetary boundaries (Raworth, 2017), and its operationalisation by O'Neill, Fanning and colleagues (O'Neill et al., 2018; Fanning et al., 2022).

Twelve of these 13 social indicators are calculated endogenously based on bespoke functions: *healthyLifeExpectancy*, *lifeSatisfaction*, *nutrition*, *sanitation*, *connectivity*, *incomeFairness*, *genderEquality*, *incomeAdequacy*, *jobAvailability*, *democraticQuality*, *socialSupport*, and *secondaryEducationNet*. These indicators are calculated based on a combination of exogenous and endogenous driver variables (the latter coming from the Economy and Demographics modules). Some of the social indicators are directly based on economic indicators (e.g. *incomeFairness*, *incomeAdequacy*, *jobAvailability*, *genderEquality*), while most other social indicators are based on econometric estimations. Only *accessToEnergy* is extrapolated exogenously, as it has historically remained constant at the maximum value.

3.1.1 Life Satisfaction

The equation for life satisfaction comes from a panel data analysis from the *World Happiness Report 2024* (Helliwell et al., 2024). The report identifies six independent variables that together explain about 75% of the variation in life satisfaction across 155 countries over the period from 2005 to 2023. The independent variables in the regression are GDP per capita (in 2017 PPP dollars), social support, healthy life expectancy, freedom to make life choices, generosity, and perceptions of corruption.

The equation use to calculate life satisfaction, which is based on Table 9 of the Statistical Appendix of the report, is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{lifeSatisfaction} = & 0.357 \ln(\text{GDP}PCPPP) + 2.627 \text{socialSupport} \\ & + 0.026 \text{healthyLifeExpectancy} + 1.230 \text{freedomToMakeChoices} \\ & + 0.517 \text{generosity} - 0.742 \text{perceptionsOfCorruption} + \text{offset} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The life satisfaction calculator treats the first three of the independent variables in the equation (i.e. GDP per capita in 2017 PPP dollars, social support, and healthy life expectancy) as dynamic variables, while the remaining three are treated as fixed parameters that do not change from their initial values in the start year of the simulation.

The final term in the equation is an offset that is added to ensure that the calculated value matches the actual life satisfaction value for the start year of the simulation. The offset is calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{offset} = & \text{lifeSatisfaction}(0) \\ & - [0.357 \ln(\text{GDP}PCPPP(0)) + 2.627 \text{socialSupport}(0) + 0.026 \text{healthyLifeExpectancy}(0) \\ & + 1.230 \text{freedomToMakeChoices}(0) + 0.517 \text{generosity}(0) - 0.742 \text{perceptionsOfCorruption}(0)] \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

GDP per capita in 2017 PPP dollars is calculated from nominal GDP per capita in local currency units, by multiplying it by a fixed ratio, determined by the ratio of the two variables in the start year of the simulation:

$$\text{GDP}PCPPP = \text{GD}PPC \cdot \text{ratioGDP} \quad (3)$$

$$ratioGDP = \frac{GDPPCPPP(0)}{GDPPC(0)} \quad (4)$$

Here is a backtest of the method used to model life satisfaction, which compares the results to the actual values for the 2005-2021 period in Spain:

Figure 5: Life satisfaction backtest, 2005-2021

It is worth noting that the life satisfaction calculator fails to capture the large drop in life satisfaction from 2007 to 2008. I suspect this drop was driven by the Global Financial Crisis. Helliwell et al. (2024) include a specification of their panel data regression analysis that includes year fixed effects (Table 8 in the Statistical Appendix), and the coefficient for the year 2008 is statistically significant and particularly large. However, the fixed effects specification is not helpful for generating future scenarios, since the coefficients for future years are unknown, so I have used the panel data analysis without year fixed effects.

3.1.2 Nutrition

We use average calorie consumption per person per day as our indicator for nutrition.

In a joint publication from the World Bank and the UN Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) entitled 'Analysing Food Security Using Household Survey Data', 'prodecure two' is '[u]sed when food quantities do not exist or they cannot be converted to grams [of energy potential], but food expenditures are available' (Molledo et al, 2014, p.22). To predict calories consumed per capita per day in the ToBe model, a simplified version of this method is used, as demand estimates for food are available in the model to act as consumption survey data. Given the absense of endogenous features that might predict available food energy, we can use economic variables, namely household and government final demand, instead.

Variables of household and government food demand (in Classification of Individual Consumption by Purpose, or COICOP, terms) and an estimation of a 'calorie unit value' (€ per calorie, or calories per €) are required. We calculate this calorie unit value, essentially a factor for kcal per unit of final demand, using a) UN FAO calories consumption data, and b) household plus government final demand in the agriculture sector as proxy for COICOP category 1 to estimate the sum of household and government demand for food

(while neglecting those parts of food production that are reported in other sectors than the agriculture sector, i.e. the food industry). Multiplying a historical value for calories per unit of food demand by household and government final demand in the agricultural sector, we estimate total calories consumed in a country. Dividing by the population in that year yields calories per capita, which allows us to compare average calorie intake with nutritional thresholds.

We first calculate the conversion factor $kcalPerFinalDemand$, which converts final demand to kilocalories of food consumed. To do so, we convert an estimate for kilocalories per unit of household final demand $kcalPerHouseholdFinalDemand_{(0)}$ to kilocalories per unit of household plus government final demand in the agriculture sector:

$$kcalPerFinalDemand = kcalPerHouseholdFinalDemand_{agriculture(0)} \cdot \frac{householdFinalDemand_{agriculture(0)}}{householdFinalDemand_{agriculture(0)} + governmentFinalDemand_{agriculture(0)}} \quad (5)$$

Calorie consumption per person per year $kcalPerCapita$ is then calculated by multiplying this conversion factor with deflated household plus government final demand in the agriculture sector, and dividing it by population:

$$kcalPerCapita = \frac{householdFinalDemandDeflated_{agriculture} + governmentFinalDemandDeflated_{agriculture}}{population} \cdot kcalPerFinalDemand \quad (6)$$

From this, we derive the average daily calorie consumption per person by dividing by the number of days per year:

$$kcalPerCapitaPerDay = \frac{kcalPerCapita}{365.25} \quad (7)$$

The standardised nutrition variable is then obtained by measuring the difference between $kcalPerCapitaPerDay$ and the minimum value $nutritionThresholdBase$ and comparing it to the difference between the upper and lower thresholds. These threshold values have been sourced from relevant literature and data sources. The lower threshold is set at 1960 kilocalories, the value set by the UN FAO for minimum dietary energy requirements (MDER) for Spain (though this is a 2008 value, other values set in other years in the FAO dataset for Spain are almost identical). The good life threshold value is set at 2700, the value used for this indicator in O'Neill et al. (2018).

$$nutritionStandardised = \frac{kcalPerCapitaPerDay - nutritionThresholdBase}{nutritionThreshold - nutritionThresholdBase} \quad (8)$$

3.1.3 Life Expectancy

Life expectancy is calculated using the 'life table methodology', typically employed by official statistics agencies to estimate life expectancy at birth, and life expectancy for people at specific ages in a given year (World Health Organisation, 2020). This approach is also known as 'period' life expectancy. The function in the wellbeing module for calculating life expectancy effectively creates an annual life table for the COMPASS Model for each year of simulation, whilst pulling life expectancy at year 0 in the table (i.e. at birth) as our life expectancy indicator.

All that is required to produce the table are our endogenously determined mortality rates ($mortalityRate_{ag,ge}$). Mortality rates are calculated using coefficients derived from a random effects, fixed slopes panel regression approach and a range of endogenous and exogenous drivers. The eight demographic cohorts in the model are calculated using bespoke coefficients derived from the panel regression. The drivers predicting mortality rates in our model are: occurrence of self-harm, fine particulate matter (PM2.5), transport injuries, health care access (logarithm of health output per capita in nominal terms), health care workers, the share of private health expenditure, and the occurrence of heart disease, dementia, and stroke. Not all drivers are used in the calculation of each cohort mortality rate (see Demographics module for further details).

Crucially, however, age cohorts within the COMPASS Model are calculated for four cohorts, one of which includes year 0 (in cohort 0-17), which makes the life table approach impossible. To get around this, we produce a coefficient to transform the ToBe age group mortality rates into specific mortality rate estimates for each of the 101 year groups in the life table. We divide the average mortality rate for male and female in 2019 for each of the four model age cohorts by the corresponding individual year mortality rates, sourced from Instituto Nacional de Estadística (INE) data. The resulting factors for each of our 101 age groups, read in from the ToBe data file, are multiplied by our dynamic $mortalityRate_{ag,ge}$ in the model to get changing year specific mortality rates.

$$mortalityRate_{ly} = mortalityRate_{ag,ge} \cdot lifeYearsCE_{ly} \quad (9)$$

First, the survivors per life year are calculated. For ease of calculation, we start with a hypothetical population cohort of 100,000 people. To calculate survivors moving to each subsequent age group, the population cohort in each year is multiplied by $1 - mortalityRate_{ag,ge}$.

$$survivors_{ly+1} = survivors_{ly} \cdot (1 - mortalityRate_{ly}) \quad (10)$$

Then, the deaths per life year are calculated, which reduces the survivors at each year stage. This is calculated implicitly in the `lifeExpectancy` function, so no specific variable exists, but it is included here for clarity.

$$deaths_{ly} = survivors_{ly} \cdot mortalityRate_{ly} \quad (11)$$

We then estimate the $personYearsLived_{ly}$ for each life year cohort, moving into the next cohort. We assume (as is common) that deaths from the survivors group are evenly distributed throughout the year, so that a half of a life year is lost upon each death:

$$personYearsLived_{ly} = survivors_{ly} - \frac{deaths_{ly}}{2} \quad (12)$$

For the final age group, a different equation is applied as there is no subsequent age group to move in to and it is an open-ended category (e.g., 100+):

$$personYearsLived_{ly=100+} = \frac{survivors_{ly}}{mortalityRate_{ly}} \quad (13)$$

Then, the $personYearsRemaining_{ly}$ is calculated recursively, beginning from the highest age in the life table and summing downward.

$$personYearsRemaining_{ly} = \sum_{i=ly+1}^{101} personYearsLived_i \quad (14)$$

The final step in raw life expectancy estimation is to take the life expectancy for year 0 from the life table (element number 1 in the ly index), after total person-years remaining has been summed recursively.

$$lifeExpectancy = \frac{personYearsRemaining_{ly=1}}{survivors_1} \quad (15)$$

Healthy life expectancy is calculated from life expectancy by subtracting a fixed number of years, determined by the difference between the two variables in the start year of the simulation:

$$healthyLifeExpectancy = lifeExpectancy - diffLifeExpectancy \quad (16)$$

where

$$diffLifeExpectancy = lifeExpectancy(0) - healthyLifeExpectancy(0) \quad (17)$$

The life expectancy variable is then standardized according to the procedure from O'Neill et al. (2018):

$$healthyLifeExpectancyStandardised = \frac{healthyLifeExpectancy - HLEBThresholdBase}{HLEBThreshold - HLEBThresholdBase} \quad (18)$$

where *HLEBThresholdBase* is currently set to 0, and *HLEBThreshold* to 65.

3.1.4 Connectivity

Connectivity is a new indicator proposed in the Doughnut 3.0 framework (Fanning and Raworth, in review). It is calculated as the average of access to public transport and access to internet:

$$connectivity = \frac{1}{2}(accessToPublicTransport + accessToInternet) \quad (19)$$

Access to public transport is calculated as a function of the increase in per-capita government final demand in the transport sector.

$$\begin{aligned} accessToPublicTransport \\ = accessToPublicTransport(0) + 0.000058 \cdot \\ \frac{governmentFinalDemandDeflated_{mobility} - governmentFinalDemandDeflated_{mobility}(0)}{population} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Access to public transport is constrained to a floor of 0 and a ceiling of 1, using the `constrain()` function.

Access to internet is calculated exogenously through linear extrapolation of historical trends, using the `generic_indicator_calculator()` function. Standardisation is not yet implemented but will be added soon.

3.1.5 Access to Sanitation

Access to sanitation is defined as the average access to safely managed sanitation services. We model this indicator using a linear regression model with a single predictor: government expenditure on water treatment and purification.

The dependent variable in our regression is the proportion of the population with access to clean water, sourced from World Bank Data. The independent variable is the natural logarithm of total government final demand on water treatment. The data for the independent variable is drawn from EXIOBASE government expenditure data, aggregated from three sectors:

- Collection, purification, and distribution of water
- Waste water treatment, other
- Waste water treatment, food

When added together, we then take the natural logarithm of this expenditure value. The goodness-of-fit in this model proves to be robust, with an R^2 value of 0.71. The coefficient of the predictor was estimated to be 0.0019, with a p-value < 0.001 . This model can be improved, however, as it is based on just 21 total observations.

Using the coefficient from this regression, we model access to sanitation primarily using the endogenous variable *governmentFinalDemandDeflated_{se}*. This variable is multiplied by *waterFractionGovernmentSpending*, which is the portion of total government final demand from EXIOBASE database represented by the three sectors above. The result is an approximation of *governmentFinalDemandDeflated_{se}* which represents expenditure on water treatment and purification. The natural logarithm of this value is then taken to reflect the independent variable used in our linear regression.

On this basis, the equation for calculating *sanitation* is expressed below.

$$\begin{aligned} sanitation &= sanitationIntercept + sanitationOffset + sanitationSlope \\ &\cdot \log(waterFractionGovernmentSpending \cdot \sum_{se} governmentFinalDemandDeflated_{se}) \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Finally, we include a *sanitationOffset* to account for the difference between data used in the regression model and the model data used to calculate this indicator. This ensures that the modelled value matches the actual value for the start year of the simulation.

Like other indicators, a good life threshold is included here to determine whether our modelled indicator reaches the level of social need. We have set this threshold at 100% national access to clean water, as a fundamental necessity of life we argue no lower threshold is acceptable in a high-income economy. The offset is calculated as below:

$$sanitationStandardised = \frac{sanitation - sanitationThresholdBase}{sanitationThreshold - sanitationThresholdBase} \quad (22)$$

3.1.6 Income fairness

Definition of income fairness We define income fairness as the inverse of income inequality, based on *giniDisposableIncomeAdjusted*, the adjusted Gini coefficient of disposable income per capita, calculated across social strata (here: employmentStatus and socialGroups):

$$incomeFairness = 1 - giniDisposableIncomeAdjusted \quad (23)$$

We frame this indicator as income fairness (rather than income equality) because the goal should be a fair income distribution, not necessarily an equal income distribution, as most people consider the 'ideal' level of inequality to be greater than zero (e.g. Kiatpongsan and Norton, 2014).

Calculating the Gini coefficient of disposable income We use the *gini_pairs* function (in *functions.jl*) to calculate *giniDisposableIncome*, the Gini coefficient of disposable income per capita by employment status and social group:

$$giniDisposableIncome = giniCoefficient(disposableIncomePC_{es,sg}) \quad (24)$$

Adjusting the Gini coefficient to match t=0 (2020) observations We then multiply this Gini coefficient by *giniDisposableIncomeAdjustmentFactor* to arrive at the adjusted Gini Coefficient of disposable income:

$$giniDisposableIncomeAdjusted = giniDisposableIncome \cdot giniDisposableIncomeAdjustmentFactor \quad (25)$$

The adjustment factor is calculated as the ratio of the 2020 value of our model-computed Gini coefficient of disposable income and the observed 2020 Gini coefficient of disposable income, thus adjusting the model-based Gini coefficient to match the observed one in 2020.

$$giniDisposableIncomeAdjustmentFactor = \frac{giniDisposableIncome_{observed}(0)}{giniDisposableIncome_{model}(0)} \quad (26)$$

The rationale for this adjustment factor is that our model-computed *giniDisposableIncome* are systematically underestimates, because our income variable is grouped (with low resolution, i.e. effectively few social agents) and because our model does not currently include all income terms.

Calculating standardised income fairness Standardised income fairness is calculated from income fairness following the standardisation in O'Neill et al. (2018):

$$incomeFairnessStandardised = \frac{incomeFairness - socialBottomIncomeFairness}{socialThresholdIncomeFairness - socialBottomIncomeFairness} \quad (27)$$

where *socialBottomIncomeFairness* is the internationally-historically worst performance in income fairness, and *socialThresholdIncomeAdequacy* is the social threshold (minimum acceptable standard) for income fairness.

Social threshold for income fairness The social threshold for income fairness is set as a scenario parameter. We set the default value based on survey data on 'ideal' income inequality ratios (Kiatpongsan and Norton, 2014), translated to a Gini coefficient roughly following Millward-Hopkins and Oswald (2021), and adjusted to obtain a 'minimum acceptable standard' rather than the 'ideal' situation.

Kiatpongsan and Norton's report survey results on what people consider “ideal” disposable income ratios (F) between high earners (CEOs or cabinet ministers) and low-skill earners. For the case of Spain, we read these as $F \sim 3$ for CEOs and $F \sim 2.5$ for cabinet ministers. Based on Millward-Hopkins and Oswald's (2021) categories but using our F value readings of Kiatpongsan and Norton's (2014) figures, we consider Spain to be an egalitarian country, using a fair income ratio of 2.5 for Spain, which following Millward-Hopkins and Oswald (2021) translates into a gini value of 0.12.

However, given that Kiatpongsan and Norton (2014) report 'ideal' inequality levels, we use a slightly higher gini value as a social threshold (the minimum acceptable standard). Specifically, we use a gini value of 0.18, which corresponds to $F = 4$ in Kiatpongsan and Norton (2014), that is, the unequal end of what egalitarian countries (such as Spain) consider fair and the equal end of what moderate countries consider fair, according to Millward-Hopkins and Oswald (2021). A Gini coefficient value of 0.18 for disposable income translates into an income Fairness ($1 - \text{Gini}$) value of 0.82.

Theoretically, it would be desirable to account for the differentiated cost of living, as the fairness of the income distribution depends on the distribution of the cost of living: an unequal income distribution could be perfectly fair (equitable) if it perfectly matches the (also unequal) distribution of the cost of living. This is an avenue for future improvements.

Social bottom for income fairness We set the social bottom for income fairness (*socialBottomIncomeFairness*) to 0.29, determined as 1 minus the worst international historical performance in the Gini coefficient of disposable income, with a value of 0.71 for Namibia in 1993 (according to World Bank data reported on Our World In Data).

3.1.7 Income adequacy

Definition of income adequacy Income adequacy is conceptualised as the inverse of a poverty headcount ratio.

$$incomeAdequacy = 1 - povertyHeadcountRatio \quad (28)$$

We frame this indicator as income adequacy (rather than income poverty) because it is defined as the inverse of poverty and should therefore not be called poverty. 'Adequacy' might be a bit of a euphemism for any income above the (crudely defined) poverty line, and we seek to improve this indicator in the future to reflect the actual cost of living.

Calculation of poverty headcount ratio based on customised poverty line The poverty headcount ratio is calculated as the share of the adult population on incomes below the poverty line (to avoid counting all youth as poor, given that the current model implementation doesn't consider youth in the income calculation (or in the *employmentStatus* index used in our model) at all). Once we implement household types and dependencies, the headcount ratio should then be calculated directly as the share of all people living on incomes below the poverty line.

$$povertyHeadcountRatio = 1 - \frac{\sum(population_{es,sg} \forall (es, sg) \text{ with } (disposableIncomePC_{es,sg} < povertyLine))}{populationAdult} \quad (29)$$

The initial value and change logic of the poverty line are determined via scenario parameters, enabling us to choose between keeping the poverty line constant ('none') or letting it track changes in GDPPC ("trackGDPPC") or inflation in terms of the consumer price index CPI indexed to 2020 ("trackCPI") -- the latter being the default.

$$povertyLine = \begin{cases} povertyLineBase & \text{if changePovertyLine = "none"} \\ povertyLineBase \cdot \frac{GDPPC}{GDPPC(0)} & \text{if changePovertyLine = "trackGDPPC"} \\ povertyLineBase \cdot (indexCPI - 1) & \text{if changePovertyLine = "trackCPI"} \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

Calculation of the at-risk-of-poverty headcount ratio for comparison For comparison, we also calculate the well-established at-risk-of-poverty headcount ratio (AROPHR), i.e. the share of the population on incomes below a certain fraction of median per-capita income (following EU convention, we use 60%).

Given that the calculation of the poverty headcount ratio based on coarsely grouped income data in relation to a poverty line is fairly sensitive to the exact values of the grouped income and poverty line, we complement the direct estimation of AROPHR (via headcount ratio calculation) with an econometric estimation of AROPHR based on regression upon the Gini coefficient of disposable income (using WorldBank data from 1980-2021; $R^2 = 0.52$).

$$atRiskOfPovertyHeadcountRatio = a + b \cdot giniDisposableIncomeAdjusted \quad (31)$$

where $a = -0.122$ is the *interceptGiniOnPovertyHeadcountRatio* and $b = 0.967$ is the *coefficientGiniOnPovertyHeadcountRatio*.

Given that the Gini coefficient is less sensitive to specific values and that the at-risk-of-poverty headcount ratio is plainly a function of the relative income distribution, the latter approach might be more robust in the current model implementation.

Figure 6: Higher values of the Gini coefficient of disposable income (x) are associated with higher values of the at-risk-of-poverty headcount ratio (y). Black dots show data for Spain from the years 1980-2021, with the red line showing the best fit as obtained from OLS regression ($R^2 = 0.517$).

Standardised income adequacy Standardised income adequacy is calculated from the income adequacy headcount ratio, following the standardisation in O'Neill et al. (2018):

$$incomeAdequacyStandardised = \frac{incomeAdequacyHeadcountRatio - socialBottomIncomeAdequacy}{socialThresholdIncomeAdequacy - socialBottomIncomeAdequacy} \quad (32)$$

where *socialBottomIncomeAdequacy* is the internationally-historically worst performance in income adequacy, and *socialThresholdIncomeAdequacy* is the social threshold (minimum acceptable standard) for income adequacy.

The social threshold for income adequacy is set as a scenario parameter. We set its default value to 0.95, which aligns with O'Neill et al. (2018) and for the Gini-based at-risk-of-poverty headcount ratio also corresponds almost perfectly to the social threshold for income inequality ($-0.122 + 0.967 \cdot 0.18 = 0.052$).

For the AROPHR-based income adequacy terms, we set the social bottom to 0.617, based on the worst international historical performance in AROPHR of 0.383 in Zambia in 1991 (based on 1963-2021 WorldBank data, accessed via Our World in Data (OWID)).

For the poverty headcount ratio calculated based on a customised (parameter-determined) poverty line, the "social bottom" cannot be readily taken from data and is thus set to 1 (meaning a poverty rate of 100%).

3.1.8 Gender equality

Definition and calculation of different gender equality metrics We define and calculate alternative metrics of gender equality, namely gender equality of income amongst (1) employees, (2) employees of equal skill, (3) potential workers.

Gender equality of income among employees (1) is calculated as the ratio of average per-capita disposable incomes of female to male employees.

$$genderEqualityIncomeEmployees = \frac{\sum_{sg \in femaleSocialGroups} (disposableIncome_{es="employed",sg})}{\sum_{sg \in femaleSocialGroups} (population_{es="employed",sg})} / \frac{\sum_{sg \in maleSocialGroups} (disposableIncome_{es="employed",sg})}{\sum_{sg \in maleSocialGroups} (population_{es="employed",sg})} \quad (33)$$

Gender equality of income among employees of equal skill (2) is calculated as the ratio of disposable incomes of female to male employees within each skill level, averaged (with population weighting) across different skill levels.

$$genderEqualityIncomeEmployeesEqualSkill = \frac{1}{\sum_{sg \in femaleSocialGroups} (population_{es="employed",sg})} \cdot \sum_{sl=skillLevels} \left(\frac{disposableIncomePC_{es="employed",sg=firstFemaleSG+sl-1}}{disposableIncomePC_{es="employed",sg=firstMaleSG+sl-1}} \cdot population_{es="employed",sg=firstFemaleSG+sl-1} \right) \quad (34)$$

Gender equality of income among potential workers (3) is calculated as the ratio of average per-capita incomes of female to male 'potential workers' (i.e. the working-age population excluding capitalists).

$$genderEqualityIncomePotentialWorkers = \frac{\sum_{sg \in femaleSocialGroups} (disposableIncome_{es="potentialWorkers",sg})}{\sum_{sg \in femaleSocialGroups} (population_{es="potentialWorkers",sg})} / \frac{\sum_{sg \in maleSocialGroups} (disposableIncome_{es="potentialWorkers",sg})}{\sum_{sg \in maleSocialGroups} (population_{es="potentialWorkers",sg})} \quad (35)$$

Note that while Metric 2 focuses on salary disparities (in current implementation: hourly wage disparities) when controlling for skill level, Metrics 1 and 3 combine this with disparities in the relative skill distribution among employees of each gender (1) and disparities in employment levels in the population of 'potential workers' of each gender.

Eventually, gender equality metrics should be extended to and calculated across other employment status (pensioners, capitalists) and other social outcomes (e.g. education or health), once these are modelled endogenously (and well).

Standardised gender equality Standardised gender equality is calculated from gender equality, following the standardisation in O'Neill et al. (2018):

$$genderEqualityIncomeEmployeesStandardised = \frac{genderEqualityIncomeEmployees - socialBottomGenderEqualityIncomeEmployees}{socialThresholdGenderEquality - socialBottomGenderEqualityIncomeEmployees} \quad (36)$$

where *socialBottomGenderEqualityIncomeEmployees* is the worst international historical performance in gender equality of income amongst employees, and *socialThresholdGenderEquality* is the social threshold (minimum acceptable standard) for gender equality.

The social threshold for gender equality is set as a scenario parameter. We set its default value to 1, meaning that no gender wage gap is seen as acceptable, as this expresses a direct identity-based disparity (which is different from accepting e.g. 5% poverty in the population when these 5% are randomly distributed across identity traits, i.e. without knowing who those 5% are). One could argue for a slightly lower threshold

value to allow for some statistically insignificant but not systemic disparity, especially given that this is the unadjusted wage ratio (i.e. not accounting for differences in occupation or working hours). However, the differences in occupation and working hours (often due to care responsibilities) are very much part of the picture and problem and should therefore not excuse wage disparities.

We set the social bottom for gender equality of income amongst employees to 0.472, based on the worst international historical performance of 0.528 in South Korea in 1985 (based on 1970-2016 OECD data, accessed via OWID).

3.1.9 Job availability

Definition of job availability We define job availability as the inverse of the unemployment rate (expressed as a share of the labour force).

$$jobAvailability = 1 - unemploymentRate \quad (37)$$

We frame this indicator as job availability (rather than employment) because employment is typically defined as the employed share of the working-age population, and it is unclear what would constitute a desirable level of employment in those terms. By contrast, unemployment of people wanting employment (i.e. the labour force) is clearly undesirable, and thus an indicator based on (the inverse of) the unemployment rate lends itself much better for defining a social threshold. This indicator, however, should not be called 'employment rate', given that that term has an established and different definition.

Standardised job availability Standardised job availability is calculated from job availability, following the standardisation in O'Neill et al. (2018):

$$jobAvailabilityStandardised = \frac{jobAvailability - socialBottomJobAvailability}{socialThresholdJobAvailability - socialBottomJobAvailability} \quad (38)$$

where *socialBottomJobAvailability* is the worst international historical performance in job availability, and *socialThresholdJobAvailability* is the social threshold (minimum acceptable standard) for jobAvailability.

The social threshold for job availability is set as a scenario parameter. We set its default value to 0.97 (thus raising ambition beyond the 94% threshold used by O'Neill et al., 2018). The rationale for this is that unlike with some other social indicators, here the reference group (the labour force) is defined by *wanting* the outcome in question (employment). Theoretically, the goal should hence be 100% job availability. In reality, 0% unemployment is difficult to ensure due to dynamic needs and frictional unemployment. However, there is little reason why as much as 6% unemployment should be an acceptable minimum. Indeed, data show that many countries perform significantly better than 6% unemployment. We therefore choose a middle-ground value of 3% unemployment as a minimum acceptable standard.

We set the social bottom for job availability to 0.612, based on the worst international historical performance of 0.388 in North Macedonia in 1996 (based on 1991-2023 WorldBank data, accessed via OWID).

3.1.10 Social support

The social support indicator used in this module is based on the value of a survey question from the Gallup World Poll (WP27), "If you were in trouble, do you have relatives or friends you can count on to help you whenever you need them, or not?". The national average values from respondents - a proportion between 0-1 from binary yes/no response - is used as a predictor of life satisfaction within the COMPASS Model.

The value of the social support indicator is estimated using four variables - two endogenous and two exogenous - and coefficients produced via an (almost) global panel regression model.

The two exogenous variables are values of survey responses from other questions in the Gallup World Poll. Their inclusion in this regression model is based on statistical analysis in the Gallup World Poll methodology file, which includes p-value estimates for each survey question, and a range of other Gallup World Poll questions or other exogenous variables (such as life expectancy).

The endogenous variables are included based on literature review, where research has shown trust, social networks, and other measures of social capital are negatively impacted by the social consequences of market economies (unemployment, inequality, etc) (Xu and Marandola, 2023; Azzollini, 2023).

The regression model includes fixed entity effects, and involves 821 observations. Though the overall panel is large - 115 countries over 15 years - irregular data for data for the Gini coefficient (sourced from United Nations data) means total data points eventually used in the regression model are smaller as a missing value for predictor in a year means all predictors are dropped in that year. All four predictors are highly statistically significant - $p < 0.001$ - and the model has strong overall goodness-of-fit, with an overall R^2 of 0.69. It is significantly weaker as a predictive model within countries, however, with a 'within' R^2 of 0.27. Coefficients for each predictor are listed below:

- Unemployment: -0.199
- Respect: 0.2998
- Gini coefficient: -0.0029
- Positive Experience Index: 0.0034

The approach for calculating social support, therefore, is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 socialSupport &= bRespectSocialSupport \cdot gallupRespect + bPEISocialSupport \\
 &\cdot gallupPositiveExperienceIndex + bUnemploymentSocialSupport \cdot unemploymentRate \\
 &+ bGiniSocialSupport \cdot (1 - incomeFairness) + socialSupportOffset
 \end{aligned} \tag{39}$$

The *socialSupportOffset* is calculated by subtracting the model estimate of *socialSupport* in the first period, based on the last year of historic data, from the historic data of *socialSupport* from the Gallup World Poll.

$$\begin{aligned}
 socialSupportOffset &= socialSupport(0) \\
 &- (bPEISocialSupport \cdot gallupPositiveExperienceIndex(0) \\
 &\quad + bRespectSocialSupport \cdot gallupRespect(0) \\
 &\quad + bUnemploymentSocialSupport \cdot unemploymentRate(0) \\
 &\quad + bGiniSocialSupport \cdot GiniIndex(0))
 \end{aligned} \tag{40}$$

Standardised social support Standardised social support is calculated from social support, following the standardisation in O'Neill et al. (2018):

$$socialSupportStandardised = \frac{socialSupport - socialSupportThresholdBase}{socialSupportThreshold - socialSupportThresholdBase} \tag{41}$$

The bottom threshold is based on the lowest real world value in 2020 from the Gallup World Poll, at a value of 0.51 (Benin, 2020). The good life threshold, with a value of 0.9, is derived from O'Neill et al (2018).

3.1.11 Education (net secondary enrollment rate)

The education indicator used here is net secondary school enrollment rate. At present, it is modelled on the basis of a simple bivariate regression using the logarithm (base 10) of the value of public education expenditure per capita.

The regression model is based on panel data covering over 3,700 data observations, with an average of 131 countries per time period, and 29 time periods per country. The model has a modest goodness-of-fit, with an overall R^2 of 0.55, and a 'within' R^2 of 0.45, and log education expenditure per capita variable is highly statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). The coefficient for $\log EducationPC$ as a predictor is 21.68.

Data for share of GDP devoted to public education expenditure are sourced from the World Bank, as is data for GDP per capita. Missing data points have been linearly interpolated, except for countries with excessive amounts of missing data where plausible interpolation is not possible.

Public education expenditure is calculated by dividing $governmentFinalDemandDeflated_{education}$ by $population$:

$$educationPC = \frac{governmentFinalDemandDeflated_{education}}{population} \quad (42)$$

We then take the logarithm (base 10) of $educationPC$ to calculate $\log EducationPC$:

$$\log EducationPC = \log_{10}(educationPC) \quad (43)$$

Finally, $secondaryEducationNet$ is calculated by multiplying the dependent variable by the parameter which represents the coefficient calculated by the panel regression model, $\log EducationPC$. The value of this equation is also constrained between 0 and 1, primarily to prevent the value of $secondaryEducationNet$ from rising above 1 (i.e 100% net enrollment, which is functionally impossible).

$$secondaryEducationNet = \text{constrain}((\log EducationPC \cdot \beta_{\log EducationPC}) + secondaryEducationOffset, 0, 1) \quad (44)$$

The $secondaryEducationOffset$ is calculated by subtracting the model estimate of $secondaryEducationNet$ in the first period, based on the last year of historic data, from the historic data of $secondaryEducationNet$.

$$secondaryEducationOffset = secondaryEducationNet(0) - (\beta_{\log EducationPC} \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{governmentFinalDemandDeflated_{education}(0)}{population(0)} \right)) \quad (45)$$

As with other indicators, the value of $secondaryEducationNet$ is standardised to compare against Doughnut threshold value for this indicator. This is calculated as follows:

$$educationStandardised = \frac{secondaryEducationNet - educationThresholdBase}{educationThreshold - educationThresholdBase} \quad (46)$$

The bottom threshold value is based on real net enrollment data, and the value of 0.26 is chosen as the lowest value in the final year of data for this indicator (Tanzania, 2018). The upper threshold is 0.95, based on the value employed by O'Neill et al (2018).

3.1.12 Democracy (democratic quality)

Constructing the democracy indicator The democracy indicator used in this model is based on the 'voice and accountability' (VA) indicator of the World Bank's World Governance Indicator (WGI) framework.

The WGI dataset reports the Voice and Accountability (VA) indicator primarily in the form of global standard anomalies. That is, for each country i and year t , the reported VA value (the standard anomaly) is calculated as the difference between the raw VA value $VA_{i,t}^{\text{raw}}$ and the global mean mean_i of the raw VA values for all countries i for that year, $\text{mean}_i(VA^{\text{raw}})$, divided by the corresponding global standard deviation, $\text{sd}_i(VA^{\text{raw}})$.

$$VA_{i,t} = \frac{VA_{i,t}^{\text{raw}} - \text{mean}_i(VA_{i,t}^{\text{raw}})}{\text{sd}_i(VA_{i,t}^{\text{raw}})}$$

This standardisation however removes trends or fluctuations in the global mean and variance and is thus less suitable for time series analysis (Kaufmann and Kraay, 2024).

We therefore base our democracy indicator on the 'raw' (non-standardised) values of the VA indicator, which we reconstruct from the reported standard anomalies of VA as well as the global mean and global standard deviation of the raw VA values of each year (which are also reported):

$$VA_{i,t}^{\text{raw}} = (VA_{i,t} \cdot \text{sd}_i(VA_{i,t}^{\text{raw}})) + \text{mean}_i(VA_{i,t}^{\text{raw}}) \quad (47)$$

Finally, we obtain our democratic quality indicator by rescaling the raw VA values from their original scale (-2.5 to 2.5) to a scale from 0 to 1:

$$\text{democraticQuality}_i(t) = (VA_{raw,i}(t) + 2.5)/5 \quad (48)$$

Modeling the democracy indicator We model the democracy indicator in year t as a linear function of an autoregressive term (lag-5 of the democracy indicator) and several lagged (lag-5) socio-economic drivers (with transformations applied as appropriate):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{democraticQuality}(t) = & 0.1127 + 0.96714 \cdot \text{democraticQuality}(t - 5) \\ & - 0.00717 \cdot \ln(GDP\text{PCPPP}(t - 5)) \\ & + 0.0177 \cdot \ln(\text{incomeFairness}(t - 5)) \\ & - 0.0078 \cdot \ln(1 - \text{secondaryEducationNet}(t - 5)) \\ & - 0.0029 \cdot \ln(\text{population}(t - 5)) \\ & + 0.033 \cdot \text{urbanisation}(t - 5) \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

The graph below shows a 2016 international cross-section of democracy values predicted with this equation vs. the observed 2016 values, reflecting the very good fit (which is expected when using an autoregressive term).

The second graph shows a backtest of the modelled (predicted) vs. observed data for Spain for the years 2006 to 2023, again showing a reasonably good fit. What might look like an anticorrelation for the local minimum and local maximum of observed democracy is in fact an artefact of the lag-5 autoregressive term, as there were local minima / maxima, respectively, 5 years before.

Figure 3

Figure 4

Calculation of the socio-economic drivers of democracy The predictor variables are calculated endogenously in other parts of the model, with the exception of urbanisation, which is calculated by extrapolating its hyperbolic historical trend. This is done by performing a hyperbolic transformation (in the data spreadsheet), using 1 as a saturation value, and setting the change rate of the hyperbolic transform $urbanisationHyp$ to its historical linear trend $slopeUrbanisationHyp$:

$$\begin{aligned} urbanisationHyp &= \log(1 - urbanisation) \\ \frac{d}{dt}(urbanisationHyp) &= slopeUrbanisationHyp \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

Moreover, GDPPC is converted to GDPPCPPP by multiplying it with the conversion rate $internationalDollarPPPofLCU2021$. Note that $secondaryEducationNet$ here refers to net secondary school enrolment rates.

Calculation of the lagged variables The lag-5 terms are implemented using the standard delay implementation in the COMPASS Model, where the derivative of the lagged variable is defined by the difference between the original and the lagged variable, scaled by the inverse of the chosen delay time (here: 5 years):

$$\frac{d}{dt}(laggedVariable) = \frac{1}{delayTime} \cdot (originalVariable - laggedVariable) \quad (51)$$

Underpinning regression analysis The intercept and the coefficients in the above equation for democracy are obtained from OLS regression of the transformed predictor variables upon the democracy indicator, using panel data from 1996-2023 (2006-2023 after applying lags) across 128 countries, with 992 observations and an adjusted R^2 value of 0.96.

The regression was initially performed upon a larger set of predictors (with a lag-10 democracy term and an oilCountry dummy variable (lag-5)) but the latter turned out to be statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$) and were thus removed through stepwise model simplification.

The basic approach and the set of predictors included in the regression are based on Barro (1999). Our approach deviates from Barro (1999) in four main regards. First, whereas Barro used the Freedom House electoral rights and civil liberties indices, we use the WGI VA indicator as the basis for our democracy indicator (see above), which we believe better distinguishes different degrees of democratic quality within broadly democratic countries. Second, unlike Barro, we did not include year-fixed effects, as our regression analysis serves forecasting purposes, and in that case year-fixed effects have some caveats. Excluding year-fixed effects did not significantly change the regression results. Third, whereas Barro primarily uses seemingly unrelated regressions, we use OLS regression, which according to Barro makes very little difference in practice. Fourth, we applied transformations to all predictors where the distributions and scatter plots against democracy suggested non-normal distributions or non-linear relationships.

Calculating standardised democracy Standardised democracy is calculated from democracy, following the standardisation in O'Neill et al. (2018):

$$\begin{aligned} &democraticQualityStandardised \\ &= \frac{democraticQuality - democraticQualitySocialBottom}{democraticQualitySocialThreshold - democraticQualitySocialBottom} \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

where *democracySocialBottom* is the internationally-historically worst performance in democracy (observed in North Korea in 2006, with a value of 0.0542), and *democracySocialThreshold* is the social threshold (minimum acceptable standard) for democracy.

We set the social threshold for democracy to 0.8 (corresponding to a score of 1.5 of the voice and accountability indicator), based on the distribution of the indicator and a sense-check: all countries that have met this threshold in recent years (Denmark, Finland, the Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Sweden, Switzerland, Luxembourg) are generally considered fairly democratic. This threshold is higher than the threshold used in O'Neill et al. 2018 (0.8 on the original scale of the average of the WGI voice and accountability indicator and the WGI political stability indicator), a threshold that may appear too low when considering that it was reached by the USA at a time when well-regarded empirical research concluded that "(in) the United States, our findings indicate, the majority does not rule" (Gilens and Page, 2014; p. 576).

3.1.13 Access to energy

The access to energy indicator measures the proportion of the Spanish population that has access to electricity (essentially a proxy for access to energy more broadly). However, historical data used to calibrate our model for social indicators places access to energy at a value '1' (100%) for Spain from 2000 to 2020. In other words, access to electricity has been universal for at least two decades. Therefore, we extrapolate it at a constant value of 1 into the future.

This indicator is then standardised:

$$energyAccessStandardised = \frac{energyAccess - energyAccessThresholdBase}{energyAccessThreshold - energyAccessThresholdBase} \quad (53)$$

where *energyAccessThresholdBase* is the internationally-historically worst performance for access to energy in the period 2000-2020 (i.e. 0.008), and *energyAccessThreshold* is the social threshold (minimum acceptable standard) for access to energy (i.e. 0.95), in line with O'Neill et al. (2018).

By broadening an understanding of access to energy to include other forms of energy, and other components of 'access' (such as cost and fuel poverty, infrastructural inequalities, stability of supply, etc), new approaches may be taken with this indicator in future.

Variables - Wellbeing Module

Variable	Description	Unit
<i>accessToEnergy</i>	Access to electricity	Proportion
<i>accessToEnergyStandardised</i>	Standardised access to electricity to a value between 0 and 1	Dimensionless
<i>accessToInternet</i>	Proportion of population using the Internet	Proportion
<i>accessToPublicTransport</i>	Proportion of population with access to public transport	Proportion
<i>accessToSanitation</i>	Access to safely managed water source	Proportion
<i>atRiskOfPovertyHeadcountRatio</i>	Population share on incomes below at-risk-of-poverty threshold	Proportion
<i>atRiskOfPovertyHeadcountRatioFromGini</i>	Gini-based econometric estimate of population share below at-risk-of-poverty threshold	Proportion
<i>atRiskOfPovertyLine</i>	AT-risk-of-poverty threshold (here: 60% of median disposable per-capita income)	LCU/year
<i>connectivity</i>	Connectivity	Proportion
<i>democracyLag5</i>	Lag-5 of democracy	Dimensionless
<i>democraticQuality</i>	Democratic quality	Dimensionless
<i>democraticQuality</i>	Democratic quality (score from 0 to 1)	Dimensionless
<i>democraticQualityStandardised</i>	Standardised democratic quality (score from 0 to 1)	Dimensionless
<i>disposableIncome_{es,sg}</i>	Disposable income by employment status and social group	LCU/year
<i>disposableIncomePC_{es,sg}</i>	Disposable income per capita by employment status and social group	LCU/person/year
<i>educationLag5</i>	Lag-5 of education (net secondary school enrolment rate)	Proportion
<i>educationPC</i>	Education sector government final demand per person	LCU/person
<i>educationStandardised</i>	Standardised net education enrollment rate	Dimensionless
<i>gallupPositiveExperienceIndex</i>	Value of national level survey responses (Spain) from Gallup World Poll	Index 0-100
<i>gallupRespect</i>	Value of national level survey responses (Spain) from Gallup World Poll	Proportion
<i>GDPPC</i>	Nominal GDP per capita at market price	LCU/person/year
<i>GDPPCPPP</i>	GDP per capita, PPP	2017 International \$/person/year
<i>GDPPCPPPLag5</i>	Lag-5 of GDP per capita in PPP terms (constant 2021 dollars)	\$/person/year

Variable	Description	Unit
<i>genderEqualityIncomeEmployees</i>	Ratio of average per-capita disposable income of female to male employees	Proportion
<i>genderEqualityIncomeEmployeesEqualSkill</i>	Weighted average ratio of disposable income of female to male employees of equal skill, averaged across skill levels	Proportion
<i>genderEqualityIncomeEmployeesStandardised</i>	Standardised gender equality of income amongst employees	Dimensionless
<i>genderEqualityIncomePotentialWorkers</i>	Ratio of average per-capita disposable income of female to male potential workers	Proportion
<i>giniDisposableIncome</i>	Gini coefficient of disposable income per capita	Dimensionless
<i>giniDisposableIncomeAdjusted</i>	Gini coefficient of disposable income per capita, adjusted to match 2020 observations	Dimensionless
<i>governmentFinalDemandDeflated_{se}</i>	The government final demand per sector in nominal terms	LCU/year
<i>healthyLifeExpectancy</i>	Healthy life expectancy	Years
<i>healthyLifeExpectancyStandardised</i>	Standardised healthy life expectancy with regards to the threshold and minimum value	Dimensionless
<i>householdFinalDemandDeflated_{se}</i>	Agricultural sector household final demand used as estimate of total household expenditure on food.	LCU
<i>incomeAdequacy</i>	Population share on adequate incomes (above poverty line)	Proportion
<i>incomeAdequacyAROPHR</i>	Population share above the at-risk-of-poverty threshold (60% of median income)	Proportion
<i>incomeAdequacyAROPHRFromGini</i>	Gini-based econometric estimate of population share above the at-risk-of-poverty threshold	Proportion
<i>incomeAdequacyAROPHRFromGiniStandardised</i>	Standardised Gini-based estimate of population share above the at-risk-of-poverty threshold	Dimensionless
<i>incomeAdequacyAROPHRStandardised</i>	Standardised population share above at-risk-of-poverty threshold	Dimensionless
<i>incomeAdequacyStandardised</i>	Standardised population share on adequate incomes	Dimensionless
<i>incomeFairness</i>	Fairness of income distribution (1 - gini(disposable income))	Dimensionless
<i>incomeFairnessLag5</i>	Lag-5 of income fairness (1-gini)	Dimensionless
<i>incomeFairnessStandardised</i>	Standardised fairness of income distribution (distance to social threshold divided by range from worst performance to threshold)	Dimensionless

Variable	Description	Unit
<i>jobAvailability</i>	Share of labour force who is employed (1-unemployment rate)	Proportion
<i>jobAvailabilityStandardised</i>	Standardised share of labour force who is employed	Dimensionless
<i>kcalPerCapita</i>	Total estimated calories per capita	LCU/Year
<i>kcalPerCapitaPerDay</i>	Total estimated calories per capita per day	Proportion
<i>lifeExpectancy</i>	Life expectancy	Years
<i>lifeSatisfaction</i>	Life satisfaction	Likert Scale [0-10]
<i>logEducationPC</i>	Logarithm (base 10) of education sector government final demand per person	Dimensionless
<i>mortalityRate_{ag,ge}</i>	Endogenous mortality rates from population module based on INE historical data	Mortality per person
<i>mortalityRate_{ly}</i>	Specific mortality rates for 101 individual year groups, indexed using [ly], for life table	Mortality per person
<i>nutritionStandardised</i>	Standardised nutrition with regards to the threshold and minimum value	Dimensionless
<i>personYearsLived_{ly}</i>	Total estimated years of life lived at each year group	Years
<i>personYearsRemaining_{ly}</i>	Descending cumulative measure of total years of life remaining in each year group	Years
<i>population</i>	Total population	Persons
<i>population_{ag,ge}</i>	From population module, total age and gender cohorts summed for total population.	People
<i>population_{es,sg}</i>	Population size of social strata by employment status and social group	Persons
<i>populationLag5</i>	Lag-5 of population	Persons
<i>povertyHeadcountRatio</i>	Population share on incomes below poverty line	Proportion
<i>povertyLine</i>	Poverty line	LCU/year
<i>secondaryEducationNet</i>	Secondary education net enrollment rate	Dimensionless
<i>socialSupport</i>	Question regarding social trust from Gallup World Poll	Proportion
<i>socialSupportStandardised</i>	Standardised level of social support	Dimensionless
<i>survivors_{ly}</i>	Population surviving at each year group in life table, after subtracting deaths	People

Variable	Description	Unit
<i>unemploymentRate</i>	Share of the labour force that is not employed	Proportion
<i>urbanisationHyp</i>	Urbanisation rate (hyperbolic transform)	Dimensionless
<i>urbanisationHypLag5</i>	Lag-5 of urbanisation rate (hyperbolic transform)	Dimensionless

Parameters - Wellbeing Module

Parameter	Description	Unit
<i>bGiniSocialSupport</i>	Coefficient in social support regression model	Change in socialSupport per unit of gini coefficient
<i>bLogEducationPC</i>	Coefficient from net secondary education panel regression model	Change in netSecondaryEducation per unit of logEducationPC
<i>bPEISocialSupport</i>	Coefficient for Gallup World Poll variable in social support regression model	Change in socialSupport per unit of positive experience index GWP question
<i>bUnemploymentSocialSupport</i>	Coefficient in social support regression model	Change in socialSupport per unit of unemployment rate
<i>bRespectSocialSupport</i>	Coefficient for Gallup World Poll variable in social support regression	Change in socialSupport per unit of respect GWP question
<i>coefficientDemocracyLag5</i>	Coefficient of democracy lag-5 on democracy (from regression)	Dimensionless
<i>coefficientEducationLag5Hyp</i>	Coefficient of log(education_sat - education, lag5) on democracy (from regression)	Dimensionless
<i>coefficientGDPCCPPPLag5Log</i>	Coefficient of log(GDP per-capita, lag5) on democracy (from regression)	Dimensionless
<i>coefficientIncomeFairnessLag5Log</i>	Coefficient of log(incomeFairness, lag5) on democracy (from regression)	Dimensionless
<i>coefficientPopulationLag5Log</i>	Coefficient of log(population, lag5) on democracy (from regression)	Dimensionless
<i>coefficientUrbanisationLag5</i>	Coefficient of (urbanisation, lag5) on democracy (from regression)	1 / Proportion
<i>democracySocialBottom</i>	Social bottom (worst international historical performance) in democracy	Dimensionless

Parameter	Description	Unit
<i>democracySocialThreshold</i>	Social threshold (minimum acceptable performance) in democracy	Dimensionless
<i>diffLifeExpectancies</i>	Difference between life expectancy and healthy life expectancy in the initial year	Year
<i>energyThreshold</i>	The social threshold for access to energy	Fraction
<i>energyThresholdBase</i>	The minimum value for access to energy over all countries between 2000 and 2020	Fraction
<i>freedomToMakeChoices</i>	Freedom to make life choices	Proportion
<i>generosity</i>	Generosity	Dimensionless
<i>interceptDemocracy</i>	Intercept for democracy equation (from regression)	Dimensionless
<i>internationalDollarPPPofLCU2021</i>	LCU to PPP conversion factor (constant international 2021 dollars per LCU)	\$ PPP / LCU
<i>kcalPerFinalDemand</i>	Parameter, constant value read in from dataframe: calories per € of agriculture household final demand	Kcal/LCU
<i>offset</i>	Difference between the actual and calculated value of life satisfaction in the initial year	Likert Scale [0-10]
<i>perceptionsOfCorruption</i>	Perceptions of corruption	Proportion
<i>ratioGDP</i>	Ratio of GDP PPP in 2017 international \$ to GDP at market price in LCU	Dimensionless
<i>sanitationIntercept</i>	Intercept for sanitation equation (from regression)	Dimensionless
<i>sanitationOffset</i>	Difference between the actual and calculated value of sanitation in the initial year	Dimensionless
<i>sanitationSlope</i>	Slope for sanitation equation (from regression)	Dimensionless
<i>secondaryEducationOffset</i>	Difference between the actual and calculated value of net secondary enrollment rate in the initial year	Dimensionless
<i>slopeUrbanisationHyp</i>	2000-2020 slope of $\ln(1 - \text{urbanisation})$	1/year
<i>socialSupportOffset</i>	Difference between the actual and calculated value of social support in the initial year	Dimensionless

Parameter	Description	Unit
<i>waterFractionGovernmentSpending</i>	Fraction of the three sanitation-related sectors in Exiobase (namely, Collection, purification, and distribution of water, Waste water treatment, other, and Waste water treatment, food) as a proportion of total government final demand	Proportion

4 Documentation of the Sustainability Module

4.1 Introduction and overview

The Sustainability module has three main functions. First, it calculates the resource use and pollution for various types of resources and pollutants. Second, it assesses the sustainability of a country by comparing these quantities of pollution and resource use to sustainability thresholds. Last, the module includes several feedback mechanisms that represent how environmental change affects socioeconomic systems.

4.2 Biophysical resource use

The first function of the Sustainability module is to calculate the resource use and pollution related to economic activity in each of the sectors. The module calculates the domestic resource use and pollution on a sector-by-sector basis using the output and the resource intensities for each sector. In the current implementation, we use a production-based approach, meaning that we consider the resource use and pollution that is attributable to domestic economic activity. Later the model will be extended with a consumption-based approach to assess the total resource use and pollution that is attributable to the consumption of goods and services in Spain. This section first outlines the high-level equations and methods that were used to calculate the resource use and pollution, and then provides a more detailed description of the methods that were used to calculate the resource and pollution intensities.

4.2.1 Resources

The three resources under consideration are energy use, material use, and blue water consumption. For each of these, we use data from EXIOBASE to calculate the total resource use and the corresponding intensities. For energy use, we consider the total use of final energy from all energy carriers, expressed in Terajoules. For materials, we use all categories of "Domestic Extraction Used" in EXIOBASE, which includes extraction of crops and other biomass, metal ores, non-metallic minerals, and fossil fuels. The extraction from all these sources is aggregated into one category, expressed in tonnes of materials. Blue water consumption expresses the total amount of freshwater that is withdrawn from rivers, lakes, and aquifers by humans and that is not returned to the respective source. For this variable, we use all categories in EXIOBASE that correspond to blue water consumption. This variable is expressed in cubic km of water.

The equations for calculating the resource use in each sector and the total resource use are outlined below. First, the resource use is calculated on a sector-by-sector basis using the output for each sector and the resource intensities for that sector. The domestic resource use is calculated by the following equations:

$$domesticEnergyUse_{se} = outputReal_{se} \cdot domesticEnergyIntensity_{se} \quad (54)$$

$$domesticMaterialUse_{se} = outputReal_{se} \cdot domesticMaterialIntensity_{se} \quad (55)$$

$$domesticWaterConsumption_{se} = outputReal_{se} \cdot domesticWaterConsumptionIntensity_{se} \quad (56)$$

The resource intensities for the initial year are calculated using output and domestic resource use per sector. The resource intensity growth rate is calculated from the 2000-2020 exponential trend by fitting a linear regression against time of the first difference of the variable's natural logarithms, extracting the intercept, and converting it into the growth rate by exponentiating it and subtracting one. The resource intensities then evolve over time according to this growth rate:

$$\frac{d}{dt}(\text{domesticEnergyIntensity}_{se}) = \text{energyIntensityGrowth}_{se} \cdot \text{domesticEnergyIntensity}_{se} \quad (57)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(\text{domesticMaterialIntensity}_{se}) = \text{materialIntensityGrowth}_{se} \cdot \text{domesticMaterialIntensity}_{se} \quad (58)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(\text{domesticWaterConsumptionIntensity}_{se}) = \text{domesticWaterConsumptionIntensityGrowth}_{se} \cdot \text{domesticWaterConsumptionIntensity}_{se} \quad (59)$$

Then, total resource use is calculated by summing resource use over all sectors:

$$\text{domesticEnergyUse} = \sum_{se} \text{domesticEnergyUse}_{se} \quad (60)$$

$$\text{domesticMaterialUse} = \sum_{se} \text{domesticMaterialUse}_{se} \quad (61)$$

$$\text{domesticWaterConsumption} = \sum_{se} \text{domesticWaterConsumption}_{se} \quad (62)$$

4.2.2 Pollution

The Sustainability module considers the following types of pollution: CO₂ emissions, nitrogen fixation, phosphorus fixation, PM_{2.5} (i.e. fine particulate matter) emissions, air pollution, and nitrogen fertilizer. For CO₂ emissions, we consider CO₂ emissions data available in EXIOBASE, which consist of CO₂ emissions from fossil fuel combustion, cement, and lime production, peat decay, and from waste. CO₂ emissions are expressed in tonnes of CO₂.

For nitrogen pollution, we consider nitrogen that is fixed by humans through agricultural activity and atmospheric deposition of nitrogen that is due to nitrogen emissions into the atmosphere. This fixation of nitrogen is expressed in kg of nitrogen. We use FAOSTAT data for nitrogen fixation, and assign them to EXIOBASE sectors according to their share in the respective types of nitrogen pollution.

For phosphorus pollution, we consider the fixation of phosphorus from mineral fertilizers, as this expresses the introduction of new phosphorus into the environment. The fixation of phosphorus is expressed in kg of phosphorus. Similarly to nitrogen, we use data from FAOSTAT for application of mineral phosphorus fertilizers, and assign them to EXIOBASE sectors according to their share of phosphorus pollution. For more details on this assignment, see the next section on the calculation of resource and pollution intensities.

For PM_{2.5}, we consider emissions data available in EXIOBASE, which consist of PM_{2.5} emissions from fossil fuel combustion processes, and from various other industrial processes. PM_{2.5} emissions are expressed in tonnes of PM_{2.5}.

Furthermore, air pollution and nitrogen fertilizer are calculated to later include them into the Index for Sustainable Economic Welfare (ISEW) by Bleys & Soupart (2024). Air pollution is modelled for different pollutants (NH₃, NMVOC, NO_x, PM_{2.5}, and SO_x), which are identifiable and accessible via the index *ap*. While the data for all of the air pollutants come from EXIOBASE, data for the nitrogen fertilizer are taken from the FAO. The value for NH₃ is corrected to account for systematic deviation with the data source of Bleys & Soupart (2024).

The general structure of the equations is identical to those for resources, namely pollution is calculated on a sector-by-sector basis using sectoral output and pollution intensities. We currently use domestic intensities so have a production-based approach.

Pollution flows per sector are calculated as follows:

$$domesticCO2_{se} = outputReal_{se} \cdot domesticCO2Intensity_{se} \quad (63)$$

$$domesticNitrogenPollution_{se} = outputReal_{se} \cdot domesticNitrogenPollutionIntensity_{se} \quad (64)$$

$$domesticPhosphorusPollution_{se} = outputReal_{se} \cdot domesticPhosphorusPollutionIntensity_{se} \quad (65)$$

$$domesticPM25_{se} = outputReal_{se} \cdot domesticPM25Intensity_{se} \quad (66)$$

$$domesticAirpollution_{ap,se} = outputReal_{se} \cdot domesticAirPollutionIntensity_{ap,se} \quad (67)$$

$$domesticNitrogenFertilizer_{se} = outputReal_{se} \cdot domesticNitrogenFertilizerIntensity_{se} \quad (68)$$

Pollution intensities are determined by a growth rate and therefore also their initial values. For nitrogen, phosphorus, PM_{2.5}, nitrogen fertilizer, and air pollution we assume one growth rate per indicator that is equal over all sectors. The initial values are calculated by dividing the domestic pollution in the start year by the output in the start year. The growth rates are calibrated to the 2000-2020 exponential trend in pollution intensities:

$$\frac{d}{dt}(domesticCO2Intensity_{se}) = CO2IntensityGrowth_{se} \cdot domesticCO2Intensity_{se} \quad (69)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(domesticPhosphorusFixationIntensity_{se}) = phosphorusIntensityGrowth \cdot domesticPhosphorusFixationIntensity_{se} \quad (70)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(domesticNitrogenFixationIntensity_{se}) = nitrogenIntensityGrowth \cdot domesticNitrogenFixationIntensity_{se} \quad (71)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(domesticPM25Intensity_{se}) = PM25IntensityGrowth \cdot domesticPM25Intensity_{se} \quad (72)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(domesticAirPollutionIntensity_{ap,se}) = intensityGrowthAirPollution \cdot domesticAirPollutionIntensity_{ap,se} \quad (73)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(domesticNitrogenFertilizerIntensity_{se}) = intensityGrowthNitrogenFertilizer \cdot domesticNitrogenFertilizerIntensity_{se} \quad (74)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(domesticAirPollutionIntensity_{ap,se}) = intensityGrowthAirPollution \cdot domesticAirPollutionIntensity_{ap,se} \quad (75)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(\text{domesticNitrogenFertilizerIntensity}_{se}) = \text{intensityGrowthNitrogenFertilizer} \cdot \text{domesticNitrogenFertilizerIntensity}_{se} \quad (76)$$

Total pollution from domestic economic activity is calculated by summing over all sectors. For CO₂ emissions, we also add a correction factor (*domesticCO2Offset*) to align EXIOBASE emissions with those from the Global Carbon Project:

$$\text{domesticCO2} = \sum_{se} \text{domesticCO2}_{se} + \text{domesticCO2Offset} \quad (77)$$

$$\text{domesticNitrogenPollution} = \sum_{se} \text{domesticNitrogenPollution}_{se} \quad (78)$$

$$\text{domesticPhosphorusPollution} = \sum_{se} \text{domesticPhosphorusPollution}_{se} \quad (79)$$

$$\text{domesticPM25} = \sum_{se} \text{domesticPM25}_{se} \quad (80)$$

$$\text{domesticAirPollution}_{ap} = \sum_{se} \text{domesticAirPollution}_{ap,se} \quad (81)$$

$$\text{domesticNitrogenFertilizer} = \sum_{se} \text{domesticNitrogenFertilizer}_{se} \quad (82)$$

4.2.3 Calculation of resource and pollution intensities

We use different methods for calculating resource and pollution intensities, depending on the variable in question. As discussed above, for CO₂ emissions, energy use, material use, blue water consumption, PM_{2.5} emissions, and air pollution, we use EXIOBASE data. The EXIOBASE categories used for each of these variables are listed in the appendix.

For nitrogen and phosphorus fixation, we use a more tailored method, which is discussed in the following subsections. The reason for this custom approach is that EXIOBASE does not contain data on nitrogen and phosphorus fixation as specified by the planetary boundaries framework. Therefore, we use data from FAOSTAT on the application of mineral fertilizers and manure, and assign these to sectors based on their contribution to total nitrogen and phosphorus pollution in EXIOBASE.

Nitrogen fixation intensities Human societies significantly impact the global nitrogen cycle, mainly through the alteration of nitrogen inputs into ecosystems beyond natural levels. As the alteration of nitrogen inputs has severe impacts on ecosystems and biodiversity, it is included in the planetary boundaries framework (Richardson et al., 2023). The global control variable for nitrogen in the framework is the introduction by humans of new reactive nitrogen into the Earth system, or anthropogenic fixation of N. The current boundary value and is set to 62 Tg N per year (Richardson et al., 2023).

The main sources of anthropogenic nitrogen fixation are the agriculture sector (through the use of synthetic fertilizers, manure, biological fixation in agriculture), and combustion processes that generate reactive nitrogen compounds (industrial power plants and internal combustion engines) (Fowler et al., 2013).

To calculate nitrogen fixation, we start from the Cropland nutrient balances of FAOSTAT, which detail anthropogenic fixation of nitrogen per country. More specifically, we use the categories "Mineral fertilizers", "Manure applied to soils", "Atmospheric deposition", "Biological fixation", and "Seed". We use different methods to assign atmospheric fixation ("Atmospheric deposition") and human fixation (all other categories). The reasoning is that atmospheric fixation of nitrogen in the soil of a specific country may have been emitted in other countries. Therefore, responsibility for atmospheric fixation is assigned to countries based on their contribution to total atmospheric nitrogen pollution. On the contrary, human fixation is always applied to the soil in the country where it is reported. As such, we assign responsibility for human fixation to the country where it is applied, while we assign total atmospheric fixation to countries according to their emissions of reactive nitrogen compounds.

In the current version, we only calculate territorial pollution of nitrogen for each country and sector.

For **human fixation**, total nitrogen input is considered to be applied in the country where it is reported. Let N_c^h be total human fixation in country c , due to agricultural activity, according to FAOSTAT.

We then calculate agricultural nitrogen pollution per sector drawing on EXIOBASE. We use four nitrogen-related pollution types from EXIOBASE (Table 1 in the Appendix) and denote this set by L , indexed by l . Let $NE_{l,c,s}^h$ be agricultural pollution of nitrogen compounds in EXIOBASE, of pollution type l in country c and sector s , expressed in mass terms. These pollution types are then converted into their nitrogen content using the stoichiometric ratios of the molecules. With χ_l denoting the nitrogen content of pollution type l , we can calculate the total nitrogen pollution according to EXIOBASE $NE_{c,s}^h$ of sector s in country c as follows:

$$NE_{c,s}^h = \sum_{l \in L} \chi_l NE_{l,c,s}^h \quad (83)$$

The values for χ_l are given in Table 4 in the Appendix. The relative contribution of each sector to total agricultural nitrogen pollution is then calculated as follows:

$$\alpha_{c,s}^h = \frac{NE_{c,s}^h}{\sum_{s \in S} NE_{c,s}^h} \quad (84)$$

where S is the set of all sectors in EXIOBASE. Using these relative contributions, we allocate the reported FAOSTAT nitrogen fixation to sectors:

$$N_{c,s}^h = \alpha_{c,s}^h N_c^h \quad (85)$$

$N_{c,s}^h$ is human fixation of nitrogen in sector s in country c .

For **atmospheric fixation**, we use the atmospheric deposition category of the cropland nutrient balances. Let N_c^a be atmospheric fixation in each country according to the FAOSTAT data, and N^a global atmospheric fixation (i.e. the sum over all countries).

We then calculate the contribution of each country and sector to global atmospheric nitrogen pollution using EXIOBASE. For this calculation, we use all nitrogen-containing air pollution types in EXIOBASE (Table 2 in the Appendix), which we again denote by the set L , indexed by l . Let $NE_{l,c,s}^a$ be atmospheric pollution of nitrogen compounds according to EXIOBASE, of pollution type l in country c and sector s , expressed in mass terms. We calculate total nitrogen pollution $NE_{c,s}^a$ of sector s in country c according to EXIOBASE as follows:

$$NE_{c,s}^a = \sum_{l \in L} \chi_l NE_{l,c,s}^a \quad (86)$$

where χ_l is the nitrogen content of pollution type l .

The relative contribution of each sector to global atmospheric nitrogen pollution is then calculated as follows:

$$\alpha_{c,s}^a = \frac{NE_{c,s}^a}{\sum_{s \in S, c \in C} NE_{c,s}^a} \quad (87)$$

where S is the set of all sectors, and C the set of all countries (or regions) in EXIOBASE.

Using these relative contributions, we allocate responsibility for global atmospheric nitrogen fixation from FAOSTAT data to countries and sectors as follows:

$$N_{c,s}^a = \alpha_{c,s}^a N^a \quad (88)$$

Now, territorial nitrogen fixation in country c and sector s is given by:

$$E_{c,s}^N = N_{c,s}^h + N_{c,s}^a \quad (89)$$

The $E_{c,s}^N$ values for Spain are used as the initial values for the *nitrogenPollutionIntensity_{se}* variables, which are then updated over time using the growth rate *nitrogenIntensityGrowth*.

Phosphorus fixation Similar to nitrogen, phosphorus (P) is an essential building block of life, and humans have severely altered the global phosphorus cycle through mining and fertilizer application. The regional control variable for phosphorus is defined as the amount of mineral phosphorus that is applied to erodible soils, with a boundary value of 6.2 Tg of P per year (Richardson et al., 2023). Note that contrary to the nitrogen boundary, we use the regional boundary, which only focuses on application of mineral fertilizer to soils.

We again take phosphorus fixation data from the Cropland nutrient balances of FAOSTAT. As explained above, we only consider the category of "Mineral fertilizers" for the phosphorus footprint.

The calculations for phosphorus fixation are identical to the human fixation component of the nitrogen footprint, but only the mineral fertilizers category is considered. Let P_c^h be total fixation of mineral phosphorus in country c , due to agricultural activity, according to FAOSTAT. The phosphorus fixation per country is then allocated to its sectors based on total agricultural phosphorus pollution that is available in the EXIOBASE database.

First, we calculate agricultural phosphorus pollution per sector drawing on EXIOBASE. We use two phosphorus-related pollution types from EXIOBASE (Table 3 in the Appendix) and denote this set by L , indexed by l . Let $PE_{l,c,s}$ be the agricultural pollution of phosphorus of pollution type l in country c and sector s in EXIOBASE, expressed in mass terms. These are already expressed in phosphorus content, so no conversion is needed. Total phosphorus pollution $PE_{c,s}$ of sector s in country c according to EXIOBASE is calculated as follows:

$$PE_{c,s} = \sum_{l \in L} PE_{l,c,s} \quad (90)$$

The relative contribution of each sector to total agricultural phosphorus pollution in a country is then calculated as follows:

$$\alpha_{c,s} = \frac{PE_{c,s}}{\sum_{s \in S} PE_{c,s}} \quad (91)$$

where S is the set of all sectors in EXIOBASE. Using these relative contributions, we allocate the reported FAOSTAT phosphorus fixation to the specific sectors:

$$P_{c,s} = \alpha_{c,s}P_c \quad (92)$$

where $P_{c,s}$ is human fixation of mineral phosphorus in sector s in country c .

The $P_{c,s}$ values for Spain are used as the initial values for the *phosphorusPollutionIntensity_{se}* variables, which are then updated over time using the growth rate *phosphorusIntensityGrowth*.

4.3 Sustainability assessment

A second function of the Sustainability module is to assess the sustainability of a country. More specifically, three types of assessments are made. First, the module compares different types of per-capita pollution and resource use to national-level planetary boundary variables (in line with O'Neill et al., 2018; Fanning et al., 2020), downscaled from the global values by equal-per-capita shares. Second, the module also compares resource use to a national fair share threshold of globally sustainable levels of resource use, which is not part of the planetary boundaries framework. The rationale for the fair share framework is that each person on Earth should have equal access to the biophysical resources that are available on the planet. Third, the module evaluates water stress, which is a measure of the amount of water that humans consume compared to the amount of water that is available for humans.

4.3.1 Planetary boundaries

The three planetary boundaries that are currently implemented are climate change (CO₂ emissions), nitrogen and phosphorus fixation, and blue water consumption. Although nitrogen and phosphorus fixation belong to the same planetary boundary of biogeochemical flows, they are calculated in two separate indicators. Following O'Neill et al. (2018), national fair shares of planetary boundaries are expressed in per-capita terms, and are compared against per-capita resource use or pollution flows. The domestic (territorial) per-capita resource use or pollution variables linked to the three implemented boundaries are calculated as follows:

$$domesticCO2PC = \frac{domesticCO2}{population} \quad (93)$$

$$domesticNitrogenPollutionPC = \frac{domesticNitrogenPollution}{population} \quad (94)$$

$$domesticPhosphorusPollutionPC = \frac{domesticPhosphorusPollution}{population} \quad (95)$$

$$domesticWaterConsumptionPC = \frac{domesticWaterConsumption}{population} \quad (96)$$

Note that to be in line with O'Neill et al. (2018), consumption-based resource and pollution footprints should be used instead of the territorial pollution/resource use. These footprints will be implemented once the input-output structure is implemented also in the foreign ("rest of the world") economy.

However, a territorial approach is also useful, and already in territorial terms Spain is currently overshooting planetary boundaries.

With the exception of CO₂, the per capita planetary boundaries are calculated by dividing the global planetary boundary by the global population.

$$\text{nitrogenPCPlanetaryBoundary} = \frac{\text{nitrogenPlanetaryBoundary}}{\text{populationGlobal}} \quad (97)$$

$$\text{phosphorusPCPlanetaryBoundary} = \frac{\text{phosphorusPlanetaryBoundary}}{\text{populationGlobal}} \quad (98)$$

$$\text{waterConsumptionPCPlanetaryBoundary} = \frac{\text{waterConsumptionPlanetaryBoundary}}{\text{populationGlobal}} \quad (99)$$

For CO₂ emissions, we use the global remaining carbon budget of 2020 that gives a 50% chance of staying within 1.5 degrees Celsius of global warming (Forster et al., 2024). The remaining carbon budget of Spain is obtained by downscaling the global budget in proportion to Spain's share in the global population in 2020:

$$\text{domesticCarbonBudget} = \frac{\text{population}(0)}{\text{populationGlobal}(0)} \cdot \text{globalCarbonBudget} \quad (100)$$

Using the domestic carbon budget and the domestic CO₂ emissions in the start year, a required decay rate for CO₂ emissions is calculated as follows:

$$\text{requiredCarbonDecayRate} = \frac{\text{domesticCO2}(0)}{\text{domesticCarbonBudget}} \quad (101)$$

Now, the per capita planetary boundary for CO₂ emissions is modelled as follows:

$$\text{CO2PCPlanetaryBoundary} = \text{domesticCO2}(0) \cdot \exp(-\text{requiredCarbonDecayRate} \cdot t) \quad (102)$$

where t is the time in years since the start year. This trajectory is consistent with the remaining carbon budget and the domestic CO₂ emissions in the start year, and is a simplified version of the approach by Raupach et al. (2014).

The global remaining carbon budget is set to 400 Gt, while the boundary for blue water consumption is set to 4000 km³. For nitrogen and phosphorus fixation, they are set to 62 · 10⁹ kg and 6.2 · 10⁹ kg respectively, based on the the planetary boundaries (Richardson et al., 2023).

4.3.2 Fair shares thresholds

Total material use is not part of the planetary boundaries framework, but is still considered a relevant indicator of sustainability, as it is often seen as a proxy for several planetary boundaries (e.g. for biodiversity loss). Domestic material use per capita is calculated as follows:

$$\text{domesticMaterialUsePC} = \frac{\text{domesticMaterialUse}}{\text{population}} \quad (103)$$

This is then compared to a fair-shares threshold, which starts at 7.2 tonnes/person, in line with O'Neill et al. (2018), but evolves over time according to the global population growth.

$$\text{materialPCPlanetaryBoundary} = \text{initialMaterialPCPlanetaryBoundary} \cdot \frac{\text{populationGlobal}(0)}{\text{populationGlobal}(t)} \quad (104)$$

where $\text{initialMaterialPCPlanetaryBoundary}$ is the initial per capita planetary boundary for material use.

4.3.3 Standardisation of the resource use and pollution variables

The per capita resource use and pollution variables are then standardised with their respective planetary boundaries or fair-shares thresholds to assess whether Spain is within the planetary boundaries or fair-shares thresholds (standardised value less than or equal to 1) or not (value greater than 1).

For most variables, the standardisation is done by dividing the per capita resource use or pollution by the respective planetary boundary or fair-share threshold.

$$\text{domesticMaterialUseStandardised} = \frac{\text{domesticMaterialUsePC}}{\text{materialPCPlanetaryBoundary}} \quad (105)$$

$$\text{domesticNitrogenPollutionStandardised} = \frac{\text{domesticNitrogenPollutionPC}}{\text{nitrogenPCPlanetaryBoundary}} \quad (106)$$

$$\text{domesticPhosphorusPollutionStandardised} = \frac{\text{domesticPhosphorusPollutionPC}}{\text{phosphorusPCPlanetaryBoundary}} \quad (107)$$

$$\text{domesticWaterConsumptionStandardised} = \frac{\text{domesticWaterConsumptionPC}}{\text{waterConsumptionPCPlanetaryBoundary}} \quad (108)$$

For CO₂ emissions, this approach is not valid once the CO₂ boundary approaches zero, as it would artificially inflate the standardised value and eventually become undefined. To overcome this, we adopt a formulation that works in terms of the growth rates. For a variable X , let gX be the growth rate of X . For a variable $C = \frac{A}{B}$ that is a fraction of the variables A and B , the growth rate gC of C equals $gA - gB$.

With this, we can express the evolution of the standardised CO₂ emissions as follows:

$$\frac{d}{dt}(\text{domesticCO2Standardised}) = \text{domesticCO2Standardised} \cdot (g_{\text{domesticCO2}} - g_{\text{CO2PCPlanetaryBoundary}}) \quad (109)$$

Note that once domesticCO2 and/or $\text{CO2PCPlanetaryBoundary}$ are smaller than 0.1 (i.e. effectively zero), we set their respective growth rates to zero for numerical stability. The initial value of $\text{domesticCO2Standardised}$ is set to 1, as the boundary value starts from the same value as the domestic CO₂ emissions in the start year.

4.3.4 Water stress

The last part of the sustainability assessment is water. We operationalize the concept with the water stress indicator (SDG 6.4.2) from the Sustainable Development Goals (United Nations, 2015) to measure water scarcity. The measure compares water use with water availability (Vanham et al., 2018):

$$\text{waterStress} = \frac{\text{waterUse}}{\text{waterAvailability}} \quad (110)$$

The variable waterUse can be total blue water consumption or withdrawal, and waterAvailability is the total renewable blue water resources available to humans after subtracting the water required to sustain essential ecosystem services (i.e. the environmental flow requirements). It is recommended to assess water stress both with water consumption and withdrawal, as they capture different aspects of human pressures on the water cycle (Vanham et al., 2018). For now, we focus on blue water consumption, as the data are

available in EXIOBASE. The data for total renewable water resources and environmental flow requirements for Spain are taken from AQUASTAT (FAO, 2025).

As such, the water stress indicator is calculated as follows:

$$waterStress = \frac{domesticWaterConsumption}{totalRenewableWaterResources - environmentalFlowRequirements} \quad (111)$$

In the current implementation, the only variable that drives changes in the water stress indicator is domestic water consumption. In the future, we would like to implement the availability of water (i.e. *totalRenewableWaterResources*) as dependent on the climate change scenario that is chosen for the model run.

4.4 Environmental change and impacts on society

The last part of the Sustainability module expresses feedback mechanisms of environmental change on society. There are currently three implemented feedback mechanisms:

- Economic damages due to climate change
- Mortality due to climate change related heat stress
- Mortality due to PM_{2.5} emissions

To project climatological variables into the future, the model uses the five emissions scenarios from the IPCC's sixth assessment report (IPCC, 2021). Each scenario consists of a combination of a shared socioeconomic pathway (SSP) and a representative concentration pathways (RCP). The SSPs are a set of scenarios that describe different possible futures for global society, while the RCPs describe different possible futures for greenhouse gas emissions. The model uses the SSP-RCP combinations to project future climate variables, such as temperature and precipitation. The five scenarios are:

- SSP1-1.9: Sustainability (taking the green road)
- SSP1-2.6: Sustainability (taking the green road)
- SSP2-4.5: Middle of the road (taking the middle road)
- SSP3-7.0: Regional rivalry (taking the rocky road)
- SSP5-8.5: Inequality (taking the uneven road)

The table below shows the expected temperature change over time compared to the baseline period of 1850 - 1900 for each SSP-RCP combination (IPCC, 2021).

Scenario	Best estimate 2021–2040	2041–2060	2081–2100
SSP1-1.9	1.5 °C	1.6 °C	1.4 °C
SSP1-2.6	1.5 °C	1.7 °C	1.8 °C
SSP2-4.5	1.5 °C	2.0 °C	2.7 °C
SSP3-7.0	1.5 °C	2.1 °C	3.6 °C
SSP5-8.5	1.6 °C	2.4 °C	4.4 °C

Table 5: Expected temperature change over time compared to the 1850–1900 baseline for each SSP-RCP combination (IPCC, 2021).

4.4.1 Climate damages

The second feedback mechanism represents economic damages due to climate change. We use a damage function from Neal et al. (2025), who adapted (among others) the damage function proposed by Kotz et al. (2024) to account for global weather effects.

The general principle behind the damage function is that changes in temperature and precipitation affect the growth rate of GDP per capita. The driving mechanism for damages is the year-on-year differences in temperature and precipitation, which reflects how climate change-induced weather variability has negative effects on the economy. The damage function also includes several lags of these weather variables, to represent that weather shocks can have persistent effects on economic growth that go beyond the year when the shocks happen.

In the original studies, the damage function is expressed in terms of the growth of the natural logarithm of GDP per capita, using the following equation:

$$\ln\left(\frac{GDPPC(t+1)}{GDPPC(t)}\right) = g + climateDamagesLn \quad (112)$$

Where $GDPPC$ is the GDP per capita, g is the growth in $GDPPC$ attributable to other factors, and $climateDamagesLn$ is the reduction in the growth of $\ln(GDPPC)$ that is attributable to climate change.

The formulation of the damage function is:

$$\begin{aligned} climateDamagesLn = & \sum_{l \in LT} (coefficientLocalTemperature_l \cdot diffLocalTemperature_l \\ & + coefficientGlobalTemperature_l \cdot diffGlobalTemperature_l + \\ & coefficientLocalTemperatureInteraction_l \cdot diffLocalTemperature_l \\ & \cdot longTermAverageTemperature) + \\ & \sum_{l \in LP} (coefficientLocalPrecipitation_l \cdot diffLocalPrecipitation_l + \\ & coefficientGlobalPrecipitation_l \cdot diffGlobalPrecipitation_l + \\ & coefficientLocalPrecipitationInteraction_l \cdot diffLocalPrecipitation_l \\ & \cdot longTermAveragePrecipitation) \end{aligned} \quad (113)$$

LT is the set of lags for the temperature variables, and LP is the set of lags for the precipitation variables. Conforming to the original study, LT consists of 0 to 8 time lags, while LP consists of 0 to 4 lags.

The variables $diffLocalTemperature_{lt}$ and $diffGlobalTemperature_{lt}$ represent the lagged year-on-year difference in average local (i.e. Spanish) and global surface temperatures, respectively. Note that on the global scale, only surface temperature on land is taken into account, in line with Neal et al. (2025). These values are higher than the average global surface temperature when taking into account the Earth's ocean surface. However, for the damage function only the year-on-year difference is important, which is not affected by a higher base value for global surface temperature. The variable $longTermAverageTemperature$ is the long-term average temperature in Spain, which is calculated as the average temperature between 1979 and 2020.

Similarly, $diffLocalPrecipitation_{lp}$ and $diffGlobalPrecipitation_{lp}$ represent the year-on-year difference in average local (i.e. Spanish) and global precipitation, and $longTermAveragePrecipitation$ the long-term average precipitation in Spain between 1979 and 2020.

Coefficients for the different terms are taken from the bootstrapped coefficients in Neal et al. (2025). The precipitation and temperature variables depend on the SSP-RCP combination chosen in the scenario

parameter. Data for the precipitation and temperature variables for the five scenarios are taken from the World Bank Climate Change Knowledge Portal (2025). For the local weather variables, we use the median projections for each scenario per country for the mean of all climate models. For the global weather variables, we aggregate the country-level data to the global level by taking a weighted average, where the weights are the surface areas of the countries.

The resulting $climateDamagesLn$ gives the reduction in the growth of $\ln(GDP_{PC})$ due to climate change. As we are interested in the growth in GDP_{PC} and not its logarithm, $climateDamagesLn$ needs to be converted to climate damages per capita by taking the exponential of the logged value. We also subtract 1 from the result to arrive at the percentage growth rate of GDP_{PC} attributable to climate change:

$$climateDamages = e^{climateDamagesLn} - 1 \quad (114)$$

Now, $climateDamages$ can be included in the growth rate of GDP. Using the quotient rule for differentiation on the growth of GDP per capita, we get:

$$\frac{d}{dt}\left(\frac{GDP}{population}\right) = \frac{\frac{d}{dt}(GDP) \cdot population - GDP \cdot \frac{d}{dt}(population)}{population^2} \quad (115)$$

After reordering the terms, this leads to:

$$\frac{\frac{d}{dt}(GDP)}{GDP} = \frac{\frac{d}{dt}(population)}{population} + \frac{\frac{d}{dt}(GDP_{PC})}{GDP_{PC}} \quad (116)$$

or to simplify the notation, we can write this as:

$$gGDP = gPopulation + gGDP_{PC} \quad (117)$$

Where gX is the percentage growth rate of variable X , and $gGDP$ is the growth rate of GDP without taking into account climate damages. Now the growth rate of GDP with climate damages can be expressed as follows:

$$gGDP^{CD} = gPopulation + gGDP_{PC} + climateDamages \quad (118)$$

Therefore, the difference in the growth rate of GDP due to climate damages is $gGDP^{CD} - gGDP$, which is exactly $climateDamages$.

The figure below shows the cumulative effect of climate damages on GDP for Spain until the end of the century for different climate scenarios. These effects are in line with the results of the original studies.

As our model calculates GDP endogenously as the sum of its endogenously calculated components (and calculates GDP per capita endogenously from GDP), we cannot simply apply this correction term to the GDP per capita growth rate. One way to implement climate damages, in theory, is to use them to reduce capital or to increase the capital-to-output ratio (reduce capital productivity). Taking the latter as an example, this increase could be implemented as follows:

$$capitalToOutput(t+1) = \frac{capitalToOutput(t)}{1 + climateDamages} \quad (119)$$

The difference in the capital-to-output ratio between time $t+1$ and t then equals:

$$\frac{capitalToOutput(t)}{1 + climateDamages} - capitalToOutput(t) \quad (120)$$

Using this, we can write the differential equation for the change to the capital-to-output ratio as:

Figure 7: Cumulative reductions in Spain’s GDP per capita due to climate damages, relative to a baseline without climate damages. Note that the current model calculates these would-be climate damages for illustrative purposes but does not implement a mechanism that realises the implied relative reductions in GDP.

$$\frac{d}{dt}(\text{capitalToOutput}) = \frac{-\text{climateDamages} \cdot \text{capitalToOutput}}{1 + \text{climateDamages}} \quad (121)$$

The effect of climate damages would then be to increase the capital stock that is required to produce the same level of output. If supply constraints were implemented, this would then curtail output itself. However, in the current model, supply constraints are not incorporated, and instead the effect would be to lead to higher investments (also not constrained) to generate the required capital to meet demand - which is not realistic and not the intended effect, as it does not necessarily reduce GDP at all. Therefore, in the current implementation, we calculate climate damages as a counterfactual but do not feed them back into the Economy module.

4.4.2 Heat death mortality multiplier

We represent excess heat deaths due to climate change through a heat death multiplier that is applied to mortality rates to account for additional deaths due to climate change, and scales with global temperature change (derived from the SSP-RCP climate scenario).

The heat death multiplier is then calculated as a linear function of the temperature change:

$$\text{heatDeathMultiplier} = \frac{\max(\min(\text{heatDeathsSlope} \cdot \text{temperatureChange} + \text{heatDeathsIntercept}, 100), 0)}{100} \quad (122)$$

The heat death multiplier is constrained by the above equation to be a value between 0 and 1. The slope and intercept are estimated based on data from Kendrovski et al. (2017). The values used are 1.4763 for the slope, and -1.2307 for the intercept.

4.4.3 Mortality due to PM_{2.5} emissions

Exposure to PM_{2.5} is one of the drivers of mortality rates in the Demographics module, and can be linked to the PM_{2.5} emissions from the Sustainability module. We used a regression model to estimate the relationship between the average annual PM_{2.5} exposure (in micrograms per cubic meter) and PM_{2.5} emissions (in tonnes of emissions), using the following form:

$$\Delta \ln(\text{exposurePM25}) = \text{interceptEmissionsPM25} + \text{coefficientEmissionsPM25} \cdot \Delta \text{domesticPM25} \quad (123)$$

where $\Delta X = X(t) - X(t - 1)$. We estimated the coefficients using the historical data for Spain between 2000 and 2020, using an OLS regression on first differences. The R^2 of this regression is 13.67%, and the p-value for the coefficient is 0.1086. The intercept has a value of -0.02033, and the coefficient has a value of 2.91e-9. This regression should be improved by using a more comprehensive dataset, including more countries and possibly a longer time series to increase the robustness of the estimates.

With these values, the growth rate of PM_{2.5} exposure is then calculated in the model as follows:

$$\text{exposurePM25GrowthRate} = \exp(\text{interceptEmissionsPM25} + \text{coefficientEmissionsPM25} \cdot \frac{d}{dt}(\text{domesticPM25})) - 1 \quad (124)$$

With this growth rate, we can formulate the PM_{2.5} exposure as a differential equation:

$$\frac{d}{dt}(\text{exposurePM25}) = \text{exposurePM25GrowthRate} \cdot \text{exposurePM25} \quad (125)$$

Variables - Sustainability Module

Variable	Description	Unit
<i>climateDamages</i>	The reduction in the growth rate of GDP due to climate change	Dimensionless
<i>climateDamages</i>	The reduction in the growth rate of GDP per capita due to climate change	Dimensionless
<i>climateDamagesLn</i>	The natural logarithm of the reduction in the growth rate of GDP per capita due to climate change	Dimensionless
<i>CO2PCPlanetaryBoundary</i>	Planetary boundary for CO ₂ emissions per capita	Tonnes CO ₂ / person / year
<i>diffGlobalPrecipitation_{lt}</i>	The lagged difference between average global precipitation at time t and t-1	mm of rainfall
<i>diffGlobalTemperature_{lt}</i>	The lagged difference between average global land surface temperature at time t and t-1	Degrees Celsius
<i>diffLocalPrecipitation_{lt}</i>	The lagged difference between average local precipitation (in Spain) at time t and t-1	mm of rainfall
<i>diffLocalTemperature_{lt}</i>	The lagged difference between average local land surface temperature (in Spain) at time t and t-1	Degrees Celsius
<i>domesticAirPollution_{ap,se}</i>	Domestic air pollution per sector and type of pollutant	Tonnes/year
<i>domesticAirPollution_{ap}</i>	Total domestic air pollution from different pollutants	Tonnes/year
<i>domesticAirPollutionIntensity_{ap,se}</i>	Air pollution intensity of output per sector for each pollutant	Tonnes/LCU
<i>domesticAirPollutionIntensity_{ap}</i>	Air pollution intensity of total domestic output for different pollutants	Tonnes/LCU
<i>domesticCO2</i>	Total domestic CO ₂ emissions	Tonnes CO ₂ /year
<i>domesticCO2_{se}</i>	Domestic CO ₂ emissions per sector	Tonnes CO ₂ /year
<i>domesticCO2Intensity</i>	CO ₂ intensity of the total output	Tonnes CO ₂ /LCU
<i>domesticCO2Intensity_{se}</i>	CO ₂ intensity of the output per sector	Tonnes CO ₂ /LCU
<i>domesticCO2PC</i>	CO ₂ emissions per capita (territorial approach)	Tonnes CO ₂ /person/year
<i>domesticCO2Standardised</i>	The standardised version of domestic CO ₂ per capita, compared to the fair share of the carbon budget	Dimensionless
<i>domesticEnergyIntensity</i>	Energy intensity of the total output	TJ/LCU

Variable	Description	Unit
<i>domesticEnergyIntensity_{se}</i>	Energy intensity of the output per sector	TJ/LCU
<i>domesticEnergyUse</i>	Total domestic energy use	TJ energy/year
<i>domesticEnergyUse_{se}</i>	Domestic energy use per sector	TJ/year
<i>domesticEnergyUsePC</i>	Energy use per capita (territorial approach)	TJ/person/year
<i>domesticMaterialIntensity</i>	Material intensity of the total output	Tonnes materials/LCU
<i>domesticMaterialIntensity_{se}</i>	Material intensity of the output per sector	Tonnes materials/LCU
<i>domesticMaterialUse</i>	Total domestic material use	t materials/year
<i>domesticMaterialUse_{se}</i>	Domestic material extraction per sector	tonnes/year
<i>domesticMaterialUsePC</i>	Material use per capita (territorial approach)	t materials/person/year
<i>domesticMaterialUseStandardised</i>	The standardised material use per capita, compared to the fair shares boundary	Dimensionless
<i>domesticNitrogenFertilizer</i>	Total domestic Nitrogen Fertilizer	tonnes/year
<i>domesticNitrogenFertilizer_{se}</i>	Domestic Nitrogen Fertilizer used per sector	tonnes/year
<i>domesticNitrogenFertilizerIntensity</i>	Nitrogen fertilizer intensity of total domestic output	tonnes/LCU
<i>domesticNitrogenFertilizerIntensity_{se}</i>	Nitrogen fertilizer intensity of output per sector	tonnes/LCU
<i>domesticNitrogenPollution</i>	Total domestic nitrogen pollution	kg N /year
<i>domesticNitrogenPollution_{se}</i>	Domestic nitrogen pollution per sector	kg/year
<i>domesticNitrogenPollutionIntensity</i>	Nitrogen pollution intensity per unit of domestic output	kg N/LCU
<i>domesticNitrogenPollutionIntensity_{se}</i>	Nitrogen pollution intensity of the output per sector	kg N/LCU
<i>domesticNitrogenPollutionPC</i>	Nitrogen fixation per capita (territorial approach)	kg N/person/year
<i>domesticNitrogenPollutionStandardised</i>	The standardised nitrogen pollution per capita, compared to the per capita planetary boundary	Dimensionless
<i>domesticPhosphorusPollution</i>	Total domestic phosphorus pollution	kg P/year
<i>domesticPhosphorusPollution_{se}</i>	Phosphorus pollution per domestic sector	kg/year
<i>domesticPhosphorusPollutionIntensity</i>	Phosphorus pollution intensity per unit domestic output	kg P/LCU
<i>domesticPhosphorusPollutionIntensity_{se}</i>	Phosphorus pollution intensity of the output per sector	kg P/LCU
<i>domesticPhosphorusPollutionPC</i>	Phosphorus pollution per capita (territorial approach)	kg P / person/year
<i>domesticPhosphorusPollutionStandardised</i>	The standardised phosphorus pollution per capita, compared to the per capita planetary boundary	Dimensionless

Variable	Description	Unit
<i>domesticPM25</i>	Total domestic PM _{2.5} emissions	t PM _{2.5} /year
<i>domesticPM25_{se}</i>	Domestic PM _{2.5} particulate emissions per sector	t PM _{2.5} /year
<i>domesticPM25Intensity</i>	PM _{2.5} intensity of the total domestic output	t PM _{2.5} /LCU
<i>domesticPM25Intensity_{se}</i>	PM _{2.5} intensity of the output per sector	t PM _{2.5} /LCU
<i>domesticWaterConsumption</i>	Total domestic blue water consumption	km ³ water/year
<i>domesticWaterConsumption_{se}</i>	Territorial blue water consumption per sector	km ³ /year
<i>domesticWaterConsumptionIntensity</i>	Blue water consumption intensity of the total domestic output	km ³ water/LCU
<i>domesticWaterConsumptionIntensity_{se}</i>	Blue water consumption intensity of the output per sector	km ³ water/LCU
<i>domesticWaterConsumptionPC</i>	Domestic blue water consumption per capita	km ³ water/person/year
<i>domesticWaterConsumptionStandardised</i>	The standardised blue water consumption per capita, compared to the per capita planetary boundary	Dimensionless
<i>exposurePM25</i>	The average annual exposure to PM _{2.5}	micrograms / m ³
<i>exposurePM25GrowthRate</i>	The annual growth rate of the PM _{2.5} exposure	Fraction
<i>heatDeathMultiplier</i>	Multiplier for heat deaths based on temperature change	Dimensionless
<i>materialPCPlanetaryBoundary</i>	Per capita planetary boundary for material use	tonnes/person/year
<i>nitrogenPCPlanetaryBoundary</i>	Per capita planetary boundary for nitrogen footprint	kg/person/year
<i>outputReal_{se}</i>	Output for each sector	LCU / year
<i>phosphorusPCPlanetaryBoundary</i>	Per capita planetary boundary for phosphorus footprint	kg/person/year
<i>population</i>	Total population	People
<i>populationGlobal</i>	Total global population	People
<i>price_{se}</i>	The unit price of goods in the normal sectors	LCU/unit of good
<i>temperatureChange</i>	Surface temperature change	Degrees Celsius
<i>waterConsumptionPCPlanetaryBoundary</i>	Per capita planetary boundary for blue water consumption	km ³ /person/year
<i>waterStress</i>	The fraction of available renewable water that is used by humans (water stress indicator: SDG 6.4.2)	Proportion

Parameters - Sustainability Module

Parameter	Description	Unit
<i>CO2IntensityGrowth_{se}</i>	Rate of change of CO ₂ intensities for each sector	Dimensionless
<i>coefficientExposurePM25</i>	The coefficient for the PM _{2.5} exposure related to PM _{2.5} emissions	Annual exposure/Tonne
<i>coefficientGlobalPrecipitation_{lp}</i>	The coefficient for the lagged difference of global precipitation.	Dimensionless
<i>coefficientGlobalTemperature_{lt}</i>	The coefficient for the lagged difference of global temperature.	Dimensionless
<i>coefficientLocalPrecipitation_{lp}</i>	The coefficient for the lagged difference of local precipitation	Dimensionless
<i>coefficientLocalPrecipitationInteraction_{lp}</i>	The coefficient for the interaction between lagged difference of local precipitation and long term local average precipitation.	Dimensionless
<i>coefficientLocalTemperature_{lt}</i>	The coefficient for the lagged difference of local temperature.	Dimensionless
<i>coefficientLocalTemperatureInteraction_{lt}</i>	The coefficient for the interaction between lagged difference of local temperature and long term local average temperature.	Dimensionless
<i>domesticCO2Offset</i>	Offset for CO ₂ emissions to align Exiobase emissions with the global carbon project	t CO ₂
<i>energyIntensityGrowth_{se}</i>	Rate of change of energy intensities for each sector	Dimensionless
<i>environmentalFlowRequirements</i>	The yearly water flow required to sustain essential ecosystem services	km ³ /year
<i>heatDeathsIntercept</i>	Intercept of expected health deaths function	Proportion
<i>heatDeathsSlope</i>	Slope of expected health deaths function	Proportion
<i>initialDomesticCO2</i>	The domestic CO ₂ emissions in the last year of data	Tonnes/Year
<i>initialMaterialPCPlanetaryBoundary</i>	Initial per capita planetary boundary for material use	Tonnes/Person
<i>initialPopulationGlobal</i>	The initial global population	People
<i>intensityGrowthAirPollution_{ap}</i>	The growth in the intensity of each air pollutant	Dimensionless
<i>intensityGrowthNitrogenFertilizer</i>	The growth in the intensity of nitrogen fertilizer use	Dimensionless
<i>interceptExposurePM25</i>	The intercept in the PM _{2.5} exposure regression	Growth/year
<i>longTermAveragePrecipitation</i>	The average yearly precipitation in Spain between 1979-2020	mm/year
<i>longTermAverageTemperature</i>	The average yearly temperature in Spain between 1979-2020	Degrees Celsius
<i>materialIntensityGrowth_{se}</i>	Rate of change of material intensities for each sector	Dimensionless
<i>nitrogenIntensityGrowth</i>	Rate of change of nitrogen pollution intensity in the aggregate economy	Dimensionless
<i>nitrogenPlanetaryBoundary</i>	The global planetary boundary for nitrogen pollution	kg/year

Parameter	Description	Unit
<i>phosphorusIntensityGrowth</i>	Rate of change of phosphorus pollution intensity in the aggregate economy	Dimensionless
<i>phosphorusPlanetaryBoundary</i>	The global planetary boundary for phosphorus pollution	kg/year
<i>PM25IntensityGrowth</i>	Rate of change of PM _{2.5} intensity for the aggregate economy	Dimensionless
<i>sharedSocioeconomicPathway</i>	The shared socioeconomic pathway that is chosen as scenario	Dimensionless
<i>totalRenewableWaterResources</i>	The total amount of renewable surface water available per year	km ³ /Year
<i>waterConsumptionIntensityGrowth</i>	Rate of change of the blue water consumption intensity for the aggregate economy	Dimensionless
<i>waterConsumptionPlanetaryBoundary</i>	The global planetary boundary for blue water consumption	km ³ /year

5 Documentation of the Economy Module

5.1 Introduction and background

The economy module is a dynamic stock—flow consistent (SFC) input—output (IO) model of an open national economy, with trade flows to a “rest of the world” foreign economy (Passarella, 2023; Jackson and Jackson, 2025). This is based on the post-Keynesian approach and integrates both the dimension determining output and relative prices through a Sraffian system of price equations in an open economy setup.

Input—output (IO) models provide insights into the interdependencies among industries and, similarly to standard computable general equilibrium (CGE) models, can be readily extended to incorporate ecosystem-related variables. However, their main limitation lies in their static nature: they are not dynamic models, as they typically compare two distinct economic states without capturing the transitional processes between them. In particular, the macroeconomic dynamic is absent and final demand is completely exogenous. They are usually adopted to study the impact of an exogenous shock on final demand and its effect on sectoral production and employment through the intersectoral multipliers.

On the other hand, stock—flow consistent (SFC) models (Godley and Lavoie, 2007) represent a specific class of system dynamics approaches developed primarily by post-Keynesian macroeconomists since the early 2000s. Over the past decade, SFC models have become increasingly prominent in ecological macroeconomics due to their ability to coherently integrate economic and ecological flows with their corresponding stocks (e.g. Dafermos et al., 2017; Jackson and Victor, 2020; Dafermos and Nikolaidi, 2022; Carnevali et al., 2024). This characteristic makes them highly adaptable and powerful tools for simulating, analysing, and comparing alternative environmental policy scenarios.

The SFC approach provides a sound macroeconomic and monetary framework within which the behavioural equations of the agents consistently operate with associated monetary flows, and the stringency between the different balance sheets is described. The SFC framework allows for a rigorous representation of the monetary dimension of the production process, treating the real and financial sides of the economy in an integrated way (Nikiforos and Zezza, 2017). All transactions are explicitly realized in monetary terms, and agents must equip themselves with currency before carrying out their “trades” in each period. The determination of real quantities goes hand in hand with the dynamics of money circulation. As a result, the process of money creation, circulation, and destruction is explicitly represented throughout sequential macroeconomic accounting.

The key features of the SFC approach can be summarized as follows: (a) the consideration of both flow and stock variables and the related macro-accounting consistency constraints; (b) unlike real assets, financial assets held by an agent or sector have an accounting counterpart on the liability side of the balance sheets of other agents or sectors (Fontana et al., 2020); (c) the explicit formalization of a sequential process where all agents/sectors have to realize their transactions in monetary terms; (d) the use of dynamic macroeconomic models, where endogenous variables move forward non-ergodically in historical time; (e) each financial stock is associated with its own flow, meaning that the former is continuously fuelled by (and, in turn, fuels) the latter. In parallel, each flow comes from and goes somewhere—there are no black holes. This is coherent with the “quadruple accounting” principle, according to which any economic transaction requires at least four recorded entries for the accounting matrices to balance out (Copeland, 1949; Godley and Lavoie, 2006).

A key limitation of SFC models is their aggregation: they typically do not account for sectoral interdependencies, as they focus on the economy as a whole. Moreover, they usually study nominal variables, while the dimension regarding relative prices and value determination is usually disregarded.

In this context, the integration of SFC and IO structures has been explored in recent studies to better capture both sectoral interdependencies and macro-financial consistency (e.g. Berg et al. 2015; Bimpizas-Pinis et al. 2023). Among other things, these hybrid models are particularly promising for ecological macroeconomic applications, as they make it possible to overcome the aforementioned criticalities and allow for the analysis of distributional, environmental, and structural dynamics in a consistent framework.

5.2 Model setup

In the economy module, the macroeconomic system consists of households, the production sector, the government, the central bank, a commercial bank, and the foreign sector (rest of the world).

Public spending and exports represent the autonomous component of demand and constitute the exogenous injection of purchasing power into the economy, triggering the interaction between the multiplier and accelerator mechanisms, which determine the long-run pattern of GDP.¹

Investments financed by loans represent a second source of (endogenous) injection of purchasing power (Cesaratto et al., 2003; Freitas and Serrano, 2015). Money is endogenously created (Lavoie, 1985; Moore, 1988), both through the issuance of new loans and the issuance of new public debt (see e.g. McLeay et al., 2014; Werner, 2014). Money creation begins with firms' demand for loans which, once approved by banks, are credited as deposits. To meet the resulting reserve requirements, banks adjust their positions by accessing interbank or central bank credit facilities, or by selling assets. Consequently, the monetary authority accommodates banks' reserve needs, making the money supply endogenously determined, while retaining control over policy interest rates—especially when public deficits are directly or indirectly financed by the central bank.

Differently from traditional IO models, where investments are an exogenous component of the final demand vector, in this model investments are still part of the vector of final demand, but their determination is endogenous. They respond to the principle of capacity adjustment; namely, firms adjust capacity to satisfy expected demand at the target degree of capacity utilization. Firms can finance investments using retained profits or loans. Dividends and wages are distributed at the end of the period. Household consumption depends on the disposable income distributed at the end of the delayed (previous) period. Households hold their wealth in the form of deposits and public bonds. Government spending is composed of direct public spending (in sectoral goods and services) and three components: unemployment subsidies, pension benefits, and social benefits.

The banking sector provides loans to firms and collects deposits from households. It holds the difference between deposits and loans as reserves at the central bank. The latter acts as lender of last resort, acquiring the residual part of public bonds not demanded by the private sector.

¹Autonomous expenditures are those components of aggregate demand which are independent of current income, such as public spending, exports, credit to consumption and autonomous investments (Lavoie, 2014; Serrano and Freitas, 2015). On the contrary, although they may exhibit an endogenous behavior, they are at the origin of the circular flow of income. On the other hand, consumption and induced investments are fully dependent on current income and aggregate demand (Pariboni, 2016; Cesaratto and Di Bucchianico, 2020). Each autonomous spending component realized in a given period generates a corresponding amount of production and income. This income is distributed at the end of the period and forms the basis for consumption in the following period, generating a corresponding amount of production and income, and so on. The repeated unfolding of this sequence over time represents the multiplier effect triggered by autonomous spending in each period. Each income–expenditure cycle reflects the ongoing interaction — the “ping-pong” — between the production sector and households, through income payments, induced consumption, and firms' revenues. The accelerator effect refers to the dual role of investments. On one hand, investment is a component of aggregate demand; by generating income, it becomes a second source of induced consumption. On the other hand, according to the principle of capacity adjustment, investment also reacts to changes in aggregate demand. As such, variations in investment feed back into aggregate demand, production, and income, leading to further rounds of investment adjustment.

The production structure consists of six sectors: agriculture, education, energy, health care, mobility and otherSectors. In the current version, we assume that capital goods production is realised within the sector “otherSectors”. To this extent, this sector produces intermediate goods, capital goods, and final consumption goods.

The circular flow of materials that characterises an economy with two or more basic commodities would require the Leontief inverse matrix to solve the simultaneity in the determination of total production and prices (Leontief, 1986; Pasinetti, 1975). With the exception of the model initialisation, for the sake of realism (and compatibility with the used modeling package), we assume that sectors do not solve any simultaneous system to determine the quantity to produce, and they cannot take as given the quantity desired by the other sectors. Conversely, each sector determines current production based on expected demand.

Current demand in non-capital sectors depends on final demand (exports, government, and household demand) plus intermediate goods demand coming from other sectors. Current demand in the capital sector depends on final demand (exports, government, and household demand) plus investment goods (capital goods) and intermediate goods demand from other sectors. Prices are determined according to the normal cost of production. Firms apply a markup over unit costs of production, which include wage costs, intermediate inputs, and capital amortisation. A simultaneous system for the initial calibration of expected quantities and prices is adopted in the model initialisation phase. The remainder of this section documents the workings of the whole economy module and describes five agents: the government, firms and their production, individuals, the commercial bank, and the central bank.

5.3 Government documentation

5.3.1 Government Spending

Government spending is determined by government final demand for domestic production, government imports, unemployment subsidies, social benefits, and pension benefits.

$$\begin{aligned}
governmentExpenditure = & \sum_{se} (governmentFinalDemandNominal_{se}) \\
& + \sum_{sg} (unemploymentBenefits_{sg} + pensionBenefits_{sg}) \\
& + \sum_{es,sg} (socialBenefitsOther_{es,sg}) \\
& + \sum_{se} (governmentFinalDemandImportsNominal_{se})
\end{aligned} \tag{126}$$

Government final demand by sector (in real terms) is calculated via a differential equation, where the change rate in government final demand is given by the population growth times an elasticity (expressing how population growth translates into growth in government final demand), and is offset by a multiplicative factor *governmentFinalDemandIncrease* (set as a scenario parameter, with start and end year defined by scenario parameters *governmentFinalDemandIncreaseStartYear* and *governmentFinalDemandIncreaseEndYear*). These scenario parameters enable simulating policy change in government final demand (formulated as an offset to its growth rate).

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d}{dt}(governmentFinalDemandReal_{se}) = & governmentFinalDemandReal_{se} \\
& \cdot populationGrowth \cdot governmentSpendingElasticity \\
& \cdot (1 + governmentMultiplier_{se}) \quad \forall se
\end{aligned} \tag{127}$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{governmentMultiplier}_{se} \\
 = & \begin{cases} \text{governmentFinalDemandIncrease}_{se} & \text{if } t \in [\text{governmentFinalDemandIncreaseStartYear}, \\ \text{governmentFinalDemandIncreaseEndYear}] \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}
 \end{aligned} \tag{128}$$

The monetary value of direct public expenditures is:

$$\text{governmentFinalDemandNominal}_{se} = \text{governmentFinalDemandReal}_{se} \cdot \text{price}_{se} \quad \forall se \tag{129}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{governmentFinalDemandImportsNominal}_{se} = \text{governmentFinalDemandImportsReal}_{se} \\
 \cdot \text{priceImports}_{se} \quad \forall se
 \end{aligned} \tag{130}$$

The deflated values of direct public spending are:

$$\text{governmentFinalDemandDeflated}_{se} = \text{governmentFinalDemandReal}_{se} \cdot \text{priceBase}_{se} \quad \forall se \tag{131}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{governmentFinalDemandImportsDeflated}_{se} = \text{governmentFinalDemandImportsReal}_{se} \\
 \cdot \text{priceImportsBase}_{se} \quad \forall se
 \end{aligned} \tag{132}$$

The unemployment benefits are calculated as the product of the unemployment benefits per capita and the number of unemployed people. The unemployment benefits per capita are computed as a fraction of the market nominal wage (as a result, they follow the behaviour of real wages). This fraction is computed using the ratio between unemployment benefits per capita and the nominal wage rate in the base year. The same methodology is adopted to index pension benefits and other social benefits.

$$\text{unemploymentBenefits}_{sg} = \text{unemploymentBenefitsPC}_{sg} \cdot \text{population}_{unemployed,sg} \quad \forall sg \tag{133}$$

$$\text{unemploymentBenefitsPC}_{sg} = \text{monetaryWage} \cdot \text{unemploymentBenefitsFraction}_{sg} \quad \forall sg \tag{134}$$

The pension benefits are calculated as the product of the pension benefits per capita and the number of pensioners.

$$\text{pensionBenefits}_{sg} = \text{pensionBenefitsPC} \cdot \text{population}_{pensioners,sg} \quad \forall sg \tag{135}$$

In addition to following the trend of real wages, pension benefits depend on the ratio between the growth rate of the retired population and that of the working-age population. This mechanism mimics a Notional Defined Contribution system.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{pensionBenefitsPC}_{sg} = \text{monetaryWage} \cdot (\text{pensionBenefitsFraction}_{sg} + \text{pensionSystemParameter} \\
 \cdot (\text{populationWorkingAgeGrowth} - \text{retiredPopulationGrowth})) \quad \forall sg
 \end{aligned} \tag{136}$$

The government provides other social benefits to the population. The benefits per capita depends on the social group.

$$\text{socialBenefitsOther}_{es,sg} = \text{socialBenefitsOtherPC}_{es} \cdot \text{population}_{es,sg} \quad \forall es, sg \tag{137}$$

$$\text{socialBenefitsOtherPC}_{es} = \text{monetaryWage} \cdot \text{socialBenefitsFraction}_{es} \quad \forall es \tag{138}$$

5.3.2 Fiscal revenues

The fiscal revenue of the government is the sum of social contributions paid on wages, taxes on profits of firms, and taxes on gross income.

$$governmentIncome = socialContributions + \sum_{se} (profitTaxes_{se}) + \sum_{es,sg} (incomeTaxes_{es,sg}) \quad (139)$$

5.3.3 Government Debt

The stock of government debt evolves according to the difference between government income and government spending each year. It is initialized to the initial government debt in the start year.

$$\frac{d}{dt}(governmentDebt) = governmentExpenditure - governmentIncome \quad (140)$$

5.4 Production documentation

5.4.1 Output and production

Each sector defines desired production based on the expected demand:

$$\frac{d}{dt}(outputExpected_{se}) = expParameter \cdot (delayedDemand_{se} - outputExpected_{se}) \quad \forall se \quad (141)$$

where *expParameter* is the parameter of the adaptive expectation function. The expected demand is formed through adaptive expectations, where it adjusts gradually based on past realised demand; specifically, it is a weighted average of past observed demand values, with weights decreasing for more distant periods in the past.

The sectoral output is the difference between expected demand and inventories coming from the previous period (target inventories could be included; now they are implicitly equal to zero). The latter are computed as current production plus inventories from the previous period minus sales.

$$outputReal_{se} = outputExpected_{se} - delayedInventories_{se} \quad \forall se \quad (142)$$

The nominal and deflated values of sectoral outputs are computed as:

$$outputNominal_{se} = outputReal_{se} \cdot price_{se} \quad \forall se \quad (143)$$

$$outputDeflated_{se} = outputReal_{se} \cdot priceBase_{se} \quad \forall se \quad (144)$$

The demand received by each non-capital sector corresponds to the sum of the final demand (household, government, and exports) and the demand for intermediate goods originating from the other sectors (in real terms). The demand for the capital sector also includes the investments of other sectors.

$$demand_{se} = \sum_{se} outputReal_{sej} \cdot A_{se,j} + finalDemand_{se} \quad \forall se \quad (145)$$

$$demand_{capitalSector} = \sum_{se} outputReal_{sej} \cdot A_{se,j} + finalDemand_{se} + \sum_{se} investmentsDomestic_{se} \quad (146)$$

where the final demand is the sum of the government and households for domestic goods, and exports:

$$finalDemand_{se} = \frac{1}{price_{se}} \cdot (householdFinalDemandNominal_{se} + governmentFinalDemandNominal_{se} + exportsNominal_{se}) \quad \forall se \quad (147)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(exportsReal_{se}) = exportsReal_{se} \cdot populationWorkingAgeGrowth \quad \forall se \quad (148)$$

The exports in the initial year are the sum of the final demand, intermediate goods and capital goods (gross fixed capital formation) coming from the rest of the world.

5.4.2 Capital and investments

Firms invest according to the principle of “capacity adjustment”, namely firms adjust productive capacity in order to satisfy expected demand. The investments in each sector are the difference between the amount of capital required to satisfy the expected demand at the target (normal) degree of capacity utilisation and the amount of capital the firm would have if it did not invest (considering depreciations).

$$investments_{se} = \max(0, outputExpected_{se} \cdot capitalToOutputRatio_{se} - capital_{se}(1 - depRate_{se})) \quad \forall se \quad (149)$$

Investment demand is satisfied through both domestic and imported capital goods. The ratios are taken from the data in the initial year. The monetary value of investments is a function of such ratios and the price of foreign and domestic prices. The nominal demand for domestic capital goods is:

$$investmentsDomestic_{se} = investments_{se} \cdot domesticRatioInvestments_{se} \quad \forall se \quad (150)$$

The nominal value of investments is:

$$investmentsNominal_{se} = investments_{se} \cdot domesticRatioInvestments_{se} \cdot price_{capitalSector} + investments_{se} \cdot (1 - domesticRatioInvestments_{se}) \cdot priceImport_{capitalSector+1} \quad \forall se \quad (151)$$

Investments are financed through a mix of retained profits and loans.

$$retainedProfits_{se} = \min(investmentsNominal_{se} \cdot fracRetainedProfits, grossProfits_{se}) \quad \forall se \quad (152)$$

$$loansDemand_{se} = investmentsNominal_{se} - retainedProfits_{se} \quad \forall se \quad (153)$$

The change in capital stock for each sector is calculated as gross investments minus the product of the depreciation rate and capital. Gross investments are the sum of investments required to replace depreciated capital plus the investments expanding the current capital stock. The depreciation rates are calibrated on the data of the initial year.

$$\frac{d}{dt}(capital_{se}) = investments_{se} - capital_{se} \cdot depRate_{se} \quad \forall se \quad (154)$$

The change in the loans stock is the difference between current loan demand and the debt repayment.

$$\frac{d}{dt}(loans_{se}) = loansDemand_{se} - loans_{se} \cdot \delta \quad \forall se \quad (155)$$

The dynamic of debt repayment follows the dynamic of capital depreciation (i.e. in the case of full leverage, amortization is equal to loan repayment).

The current value of the capital stock depends on both the foreign and domestic price of capital goods (this should be valued according to historical cost, but we cannot do that in ModelingToolkit, then it is valued at the replacement cost).

$$capitalValue_{se} = capital_{se} \cdot domesticRatioInvestments_{se} \cdot price_{capitalSector} + capital_{se} \cdot (1 - domesticRatioInvestments_{se}) \cdot priceImports_{capitalSector} \quad \forall se \quad (156)$$

5.4.3 Profits and investment financing

The gross profits are computed as the difference between firm revenues and intermediate costs, the wage bill, and capital amortisation. The latter is composed of loans repayment and retained profits to replace the corresponding amount of depreciated capital.

$$grossProfits_{se} = sales_{se} \cdot price_{se} - intermediateCosts_{se} - grossWages_{se} - capitalAmortization_{se} \quad \forall se \quad (157)$$

The intermediate costs are the sum of the cost of all inputs used by each sector (domestic and imported commodities).

$$intermediateCosts_{se} = \sum_j outputReal_{se} \cdot A_{j,se} \cdot price_j + \sum_j outputReal_{se} \cdot A_{imp,j,se} \cdot priceImp_j \quad \forall se \quad (158)$$

The net profits are the the gross profits minus the tax on corporate income.

$$netProfits_{se} = grossProfits_{se} \cdot (1 - taxRateCorporateIncome) \quad \forall se \quad (159)$$

The amount of distributed profits corresponds to the net profits minus retained profits. These are distributed to the social groups that make up the capitalist class in proportion to the subgroup population shares.

$$distributedProfits_{se} = netProfits_{se} - retainedProfits_{se} \quad \forall se \quad (160)$$

5.4.4 Prices

Prices are computed based on the normal costs of production, with a firm markup over normal unitary costs. In each period, to compute unit costs, firms use the input prices from the previous period. This method allows for breaking the simultaneity characterising price determination in an IO system of production (in the IO system, production is circular and prices are interdependent). However, their interdependency and the relative prices are incorporated in the system at the initialisation phase where initial prices are computed simultaneously. This method allows avoiding the use a Leontief inverse matrix within each simulation period, while producing the same results. The price of each sector is:

$$price_{ese} = (labourIntensity_{ese} \cdot monetaryWage + \sum_j A_{j,ese}^{exp} \cdot delayedPrice_j + \sum_j A_{j,ese}^{exp,imp} \cdot delayedPriceImports_j) \cdot (1 + markup) \quad \forall ese \quad (161)$$

Foreign prices in each period converge to domestic inflation (the initial values of foreign prices are computed together with the simultaneous system aimed at determining domestic prices):

$$\frac{d}{dt}(priceImports_{ese}) = priceImports_{ese} \cdot inflation \quad \forall ese \quad (162)$$

The CPI inflation rate $inflationCPI$ (i.e. weighted rate of inflation per period) is computed using the weights derived from the sector split of household final demand:

$$inflationCPI = \sum_{se} sectorSplitHouseholdFinalDemand_{se} \cdot inflation_{se} \quad \forall se \quad (163)$$

Currently, in the model, mechanisms affecting relative prices are absent. Therefore, $inflationCPI$ converges to the difference between $nominalWageGrowth$ and $labourProductivityGrowth$:

$$inflationCPIConvergence = nominalWageGrowth - labourProductivityGrowth \quad (164)$$

Based on this quasi-inflation rate, we calculate the CPI price index $indexCPI$ (indexed to the value of the start year, i.e. starting from 1 and tracking CPI).

$$\frac{d}{dt}(indexCPI) = inflationCPIConvergence \cdot indexCPI \quad (165)$$

(At the moment, for the sake of simplicity, we are assuming that the real exchange rate is kept stable through a convergence between domestic and foreign inflation. Further developments may require considering adjustments in the nominal exchange rate in order to maintain a stable real exchange rate and a non-explosive (implosive) balance of payments).

5.4.5 Labour productivity growth

The dynamic of labour intensity in each sector is: Labour intensity (working hours per unit of output) in each sector is calculated via a differential equation that expresses changes in labour intensity as a function of labour productivity growth. Assuming a simple exponential decay function, the change in labour intensity can then be expressed as:

$$\frac{d}{dt}(labourIntensity_{ese}) = -\frac{labourIntensity_{ese} \cdot labourProductivityGrowth}{1 + labourProductivityGrowth} \quad (166)$$

5.4.6 GDP and trade

The monetary value of imports in each sector depends on the demand of foreign intermediate goods and foreign capital goods:

$$importsNominal_{se} = \sum_{se} outputReal_{se} \cdot A_{j,se}^{imp} \cdot priceImports_j + investments_{se} \cdot foreignRatio_{se} \cdot priceImports_{capitalSector} \quad \forall se \quad (167)$$

The total value of imports includes government demand and households demand for foreign goods and the domestic firm demand for foreign intermediate goods and capital goods:

$$importsNominal = \sum_{se} importsNominal_{se} + \sum_{se} governmentFinalDemandImportsNominal_{se} + \sum_{se} householdFinalDemandImports_{se} \quad (168)$$

The monetary value of exports includes the export of intermediate goods, capital goods and consumption goods (final demand from the rest of the world):

$$exportsNominal = \sum_{se} exportsNominal_{se} \quad (169)$$

$$exportsReal_{se} = \sum_{se} exportsReal_{se} \cdot price_{ese} \quad \forall se \quad (170)$$

The real (or deflated) GDP is computed as:

$$\begin{aligned} GDP = & \sum_{se} governmentFinalDemandNominal_{se} \frac{priceBase_{se}}{price_{ese}} \\ & + \sum_{se} householdFinalDemand_{se} \frac{priceBase_{se}}{price_{ese}} \\ & + \sum_{se} investmentsDomesticNominal_{se} \frac{priceBase_{capitalSector}}{price_{capitalSector}} \\ & + \sum_{se} exportsNominal_{se} \frac{priceBase_{se}}{price_{ese}} - \sum_{se} imporsIntermediateNominal_{se} \frac{priceImportsBase_{se}}{priceImports_{ese}} \end{aligned} \quad (171)$$

where $priceBase_{se}$ are the prices in the base year and $price_{ese}$ are current prices.

The nominal GDP is:

$$\begin{aligned} GDPNominal = & \sum_{se} governmentFinalDemandNominal_{se} \\ & + \sum_{se} householdFinalDemandNominal_{se} + \sum_{se} investmentsDomesticNominal_{se} \\ & + \sum_{se} exportsNominal_{se} - \sum_{se} imporsIntermediateNominal_{se} \end{aligned} \quad (172)$$

5.4.7 Labour market

Employment hours for each sector are calculated as the output per sector multiplied by labour intensity.

$$employmentHours_{se} = outputReal_{se} \cdot labourIntensity_{se} \quad \forall se \quad (173)$$

Employment hours for each sector and social group are calculated as the employment hours for the sector multiplied by the employment distribution. This distribution divides the employment hours per sector over the social groups and is calibrated on the data of the initial year.

$$employmentHours_{se,sg} = employmentHours_{se} \cdot employmentDistribution_{se,sg} \quad \forall se, sg \quad (174)$$

$$\sum_{sg} employmentDistribution_{se,sg} = 1 \quad \forall se \quad (175)$$

Employment in terms of people for each sector is calculated as the employment hours divided by the product of base weekly work hours and working weeks per year.

$$employmentPeople_{se} = \frac{employmentHours_{se}}{weeklyWorkHoursBase_{se} \cdot workingWeeksPerYear} \quad \forall se \quad (176)$$

The working weeks per year is set to 48 weeks standard. The base weekly work hours are calibrated on the data of the initial year with the following formula.

$$weeklyWorkHoursBase_{se} = \frac{employmentHours_{se}}{employmentPeople_{se,sg} \cdot workingWeeksPerYear} \quad \forall se \quad (177)$$

Employment in terms of people for each social group is calculated as the sum of employment hours for each sector and social group divided by the product of base weekly work hours and working weeks per year.

$$employmentPeople_{sg} = \frac{\sum_{se} employmentHours_{se,sg}}{weeklyWorkHoursBase_{se} \cdot workingWeeksPerYear} \quad \forall sg \quad (178)$$

The employment rate for each social group is calculated as the employment in terms of people divided by the total population that is of working age for that group.

$$employmentRate_{sg} = \frac{employmentPeople_{sg}}{populationWorkingAge_{sg}} \quad \forall sg \quad (179)$$

The overall employment rate is calculated as the total employment in terms of people over all social groups divided by the total population of working age.

$$employmentRate = \frac{\sum_{sg} employmentPeople_{sg}}{\sum_{sg} populationWorkingAge_{sg}} \quad (180)$$

The unemployment rate for each social group is calculated as the fraction of the labour force that is not employed.

$$unemploymentRate_{sg} = 1 - \frac{employmentPeople_{sg}}{labourForce_{sg}} \quad \forall sg \quad (181)$$

The overall unemployment rate is calculated as the fraction of the labour force that is not employed over the total labour force. The latter is computed using the estimated participation and the working age population.

$$unemploymentRate = 1 - \frac{\sum_{sg} employmentPeople_{sg}}{\sum_{sg} labourForce_{sg}} \quad (182)$$

The wage bill paid by each sector is calculated as the monetary wage (hourly wage) multiplied by the employment hours.

$$grossWages_{se} = monetaryWage \cdot employmentHours_{se} \quad \forall se \quad (183)$$

Gross wages received by each social group are computed as total sectoral gross wages multiplied by the distribution share of that group within the sector. The latter is initialized by considering the distribution of wages among the various social groups in each sector in the base year.

$$grossWages_{se,sg} = grossWages_{se} \cdot grossWagesDistribution_{se,sg} \quad (184)$$

The growth rate of monetary wage is a function of the unemployment rate (which is a proxy of workers' bargaining power):

$$\frac{d}{dt}(monetaryWage) = monetaryWage \cdot \varsigma \cdot (1 - U_{t-1}) \quad (185)$$

where ς is a parameter that represents the bargaining power of workers in correspondence with a given level of unemployment. (We do not incorporate inflation expectations into the growth rate of money wages, since the possibility to secure higher wages still depends on workers' bargaining power).

5.4.8 Delayed variables

Delayed variables are defined as follows:

$$d(delayedInvestments_{se}) = \frac{investments_{se} - delayedInvestments_{se}}{delayTime} \quad \forall se \quad (186)$$

$$d(\text{delayedInventories}_{se}) = \frac{\text{inventories}_{se} - \text{delayedInventories}_{se}}{\text{delayTime}} \quad \forall se \quad (187)$$

$$d(\text{delayedDemand}_{se}) = \frac{\text{demand}_{se} - \text{delayedDemand}_{se}}{\text{delayTime}} \quad \forall se \quad (188)$$

$$d(\text{delayedLoans}_{se}) = \frac{\text{loans}_{se} - \text{delayedLoans}_{se}}{\text{delayTime}} \quad \forall se \quad (189)$$

$$d(\text{delayedPrice}_{ese}) = \frac{\text{price}_{ese} - \text{delayedPrice}_{ese}}{\text{delayTime}} \quad \forall ese \quad (190)$$

5.5 Individuals documentation

5.5.1 Labour market

The working-age population for each social group is calculated as the sum of the population in working age groups.

$$\text{populationWorkingAge}_{sg} = \sum_{ag \in \text{ageGroups}_{working}} \text{population}_{ag,sg} \quad \forall sg \quad (191)$$

The labour force in terms of people for each social group is calculated as the working-age population multiplied by the labour force participation rate. This assumes that capitalists do not engage in typical labour activities.

$$\text{labourForcePeople}_{sg} = \text{labourForceParticipationRate} \cdot \text{populationWorkingAge}_{sg} \quad \forall sg \quad (192)$$

The employed population for each social group is equal to the employment in terms of people.

$$\text{population}_{employed,sg} = \text{employmentPeople}_{sg} \quad \forall sg \quad (193)$$

The unemployed population for each social group is calculated as the working-age population minus the employed population and capitalists per adult.

$$\text{population}_{unemployed,sg} = \text{labourForcePeople}_{sg} - \text{employmentPeople}_{sg} \quad \forall sg \quad (194)$$

The capitalist population for each social group is calculated as the capitalists per adult multiplied by the adult population.

$$\text{population}_{capitalist,sg} = \text{capitalistsPerAdult} \cdot \sum_{ag \in \text{ageGroups}_{adult}} \text{population}_{ag,sg} \quad \forall sg \quad (195)$$

The pensioner population for each social group is calculated as the non-capitalist portion of the population aged 64 and above.

$$\text{population}_{pensioner,sg} = (1 - \text{capitalistsPerAdult}) \cdot \text{population}_{age64plus,sg} \quad \forall sg \quad (196)$$

We consider the population that is out of the labour force as the working age population that is not part of the labour force, nor part of the capitalist class.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{population}_{outOfLabourForce,sg} &= (1 - \text{capitalistsPerAdult}) \cdot \text{populationWorkingAge}_{sg} \\ &\quad - \text{labourForcePeople}_{sg} \quad \forall sg \end{aligned} \quad (197)$$

Social contributions are calculated as the social contribution rate multiplied by the sum of gross wages for all sectors and social groups. The parameter *socialContributionsRate* is calibrated by summing the average social contribution rate for employers and employees in the initial year.

$$socialContributions = socialContributionRate \cdot \sum_{se,sg} grossWages_{se,sg} \quad (198)$$

Gross wages for each social group are calculated as the sum of gross wages for all sectors.

$$grossWages_{sg} = \sum_{se} grossWages_{se,sg} \quad \forall sg \quad (199)$$

5.5.2 Income

The gross income for employed individuals in each social group is calculated as gross wages minus social contributions.

$$grossIncome_{employed,sg} = (1 - socialContributionRate) \cdot grossWages_{sg} + socialBenefitsOther_{employed,sg} \quad \forall sg \quad (200)$$

Gross income for unemployed individuals in each social group is equal to unemployment benefits plus social benefits.

$$grossIncome_{unemployed,sg} = unemploymentBenefits_{sg} + socialBenefitsOther_{unemployed,sg} \quad \forall sg \quad (201)$$

Gross income for pensioners in each social group is equal to pension benefits and social benefits.

$$grossIncome_{pensioner,sg} = pensionBenefits_{sg} + socialBenefitsOther_{pensioner,sg} \quad \forall sg \quad (202)$$

Gross income per capita for capitalists depends on the population and the profits distributed to each social group, plus social benefits:

$$grossIncome_{capitalist,sg} = socialBenefitsOther_{capitalist,sg} + netProfit \cdot \frac{population_{capitalist,sg}}{\sum_{sg \in socialGroups} population_{capitalist,sg}} \quad (203)$$

People not in the working age labour force only receive social benefits:

$$grossIncome_{outOfLabourForce,sg} = socialBenefitsOther_{outOfLabourForce,sg} \quad \forall sg \quad (204)$$

Individuals pay income taxes on their gross income according to different tax brackets (progressive taxation):

$$incomeTaxesPC_{es,sg} = \sum_{tb} \begin{cases} (\min(taxBracketUpper_{tb}, grossIncomePC_{es,sg}) - taxBracketLower_{tb}) \cdot marginalTaxRate_{tb}, & \text{if } grossIncomePC_{es,sg} \geq taxBracketLower_{tb} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (205)$$

$$incomeTaxes_{es,sg} = incomeTaxesPC_{es,sg} \cdot population_{es,sg} \quad \forall es, sg \quad (206)$$

Fiscal brackets are indexed to inflation in order to avoid the fiscal drag:

$$\frac{d}{dt}(taxBracketLower_{tb}) = taxBracketLower_{tb} \cdot inflation \quad \forall tb \quad (207)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(taxBracketUpper_{tb}) = taxBracketUpper_{tb} \cdot inflation \quad \forall tb \quad (208)$$

The disposable income for each employment status and social group is calculated as the gross income minus taxes.

$$disposableIncome_{es,sg} = grossIncome_{es,sg} - incomeTaxes_{es,sg} \quad (209)$$

The delayed disposable income is calculated by the following formula.

$$\frac{d}{dt}(delayedDisposableIncome_{es,sg}) = - \left(\frac{1}{delayTime} \right) \cdot (delayedDisposableIncome_{es,sg} - disposableIncome_{es,sg}) \quad \forall es, sg \quad (210)$$

The total disposable income is calculated as the sum of disposable income for all employment statuses and social groups.

$$disposableIncome = \sum_{es,sg} disposableIncome_{es,sg} \quad (211)$$

Per capita disposable income for each employment status and social group is calculated as disposable income divided by the population of that group if it is non-zero.

$$disposableIncomePC_{es,sg} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } population_{es,sg} = 0 \\ \frac{disposableIncome_{es,sg}}{population_{es,sg}} & \text{if } population_{es,sg} > 0 \end{cases} \quad \forall es, sg \quad (212)$$

Overall per capita disposable income is calculated as the total disposable income divided by the adult population.

$$disposableIncomePC = \frac{disposableIncome}{populationAdult} \quad (213)$$

5.5.3 Consumption

The household final demand is calculated as the propensity to consume multiplied by the sum of the delayed disposable income for all employment statuses and social groups.

$$householdFinalDemand = propensityToConsume \cdot \sum_{es,sg} delayedDisposableIncome_{es,sg} \quad (214)$$

Households consume both domestic and imported goods.

$$householdFinalDemandDomestic = householdFinalDemand \cdot domesticRatioHouseholds \quad (215)$$

$$householdFinalDemandImported = householdFinalDemand \cdot (1 - domesticRatioHouseholds) \quad (216)$$

Household final demand for each sector is calculated as the product of the sector split of household final demand and the overall household final demand.

$$\begin{aligned} householdFinalDemand_{se} \\ = sectorSplitHouseholdFinalDemand_{se} \cdot householdFinalDemandDomestic \quad \forall se \end{aligned} \quad (217)$$

$$\begin{aligned} householdFinalDemandImports_{se} = sectorSplitHouseholdFinalDemandImports_{se} \\ \cdot householdFinalDemandImported \quad \forall se \end{aligned} \quad (218)$$

5.5.4 Household wealth

The change in household wealth is calculated as disposable income minus household consumption. The household wealth is initialised to the initial government debt (minus check deposits).

$$\frac{d}{dt}(wealthHouseholds) = disposableIncome - householdFinalDemand \quad (219)$$

Household wealth is fully stored in deposits.

$$timeDepositsHouseholds = wealthHouseholds \quad (220)$$

The disposable income distributed at the end of each period is stored as check deposits in the bank account. The initial amount of check deposits is equal to the initial disposable income (household consumption in the first period originates from that amount).

$$checkDepositsHouseholds = disposableIncome \quad (221)$$

5.6 Commercial bank and central bank

The commercial bank grants loans to firms and collect deposits. It holds the difference between deposits and loans as reserves at the central bank.

The overall loans are calculated as the sum of loans for all sectors.

$$loans = \sum_{se} loans_{se} \quad (222)$$

$$reserves = checkDepositsHouseholds + timeDepositsHouseholds - loans \quad (223)$$

Public debt is entirely held by the central bank:

$$bondCentralBank = governmentDebt \quad (224)$$

5.7 Stock-flow consistency

The net wealth of each sector is computed as follows.

$$netWealthCentralBank = bondCentralBank - reserves \quad (225)$$

$$netWealthGovernment = -governmentDebt \quad (226)$$

$$netWealthBank = loans + reserves - timeDepositsHouseholds - checkDepositsHouseholds \quad (227)$$

$$netWealthFirms = capitalValue - loans \quad (228)$$

$$netWealthHouseholds = TimeDepositsHouseholds + CheckdepositsHouseholds \quad (229)$$

The redundant equation ensures the stock—flow consistency of the model. This equation should be equal to 0 if the model is to be stock—flow consistent.

$$sfcCheck = bondCentralBank - reserves \quad (230)$$

The balance sheet matrix of the macro-economy is:

Assets	Households	Production	Banks	Government	Central Bank	Rest of World	Σ
Check deposits	$+M_h^c$		$-M_b^c$			$-M_x^c$	0
Time deposits	$+M_h$		$-M_b$				0
Reserves			$+H_b$		$-H$	$+H_x$	0
Loans		$-L$	$+L$				0
Fixed capital		$+K$					$+K$
Inventories		$+INV$					$+INV$
Public bonds	$+B_h$			$-B$		$-B_x$	0
Foreign bonds	$+FB_h$				$+FB_{CB}$	$-FB$	0
FX reserves					$+H^f$	$-H^f$	0
Net Wealth	$-V_h$	$-V_p$	0	$+V_G$	$-V_{CB}$	$-V_x$	$-K - INV$
Σ	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

The transaction matrix is:

Transactions Matrix

Transactions	Households	Prod. Current	Prod. Capital	Banks	Government	Central Bank	Rest of World	Σ
Consumption	$-C$	$+C^d$					$+C^{imp}$	0
Retained profits	$-FU$		$+FU$					0
Investments		$+I^d$	$-I$				$+I^{imp}$	0
Intermediate imports		$-IM_{int}$					$+IM_{int}$	0
Exports		$+X$					$-X$	0
Government spending		$+G^d$			$-G$		$+G^{imp}$	0
Unemployment benefits	$+U$				$-U$			0
Pensions	$+PE$				$-PE$			0
Social benefits	$+SB$				$-SB$			0
Wages	$+W$	$-W$						0
Profits	Π	$-\Pi$						0
Taxes	$-T$				$+T$			0
Interest on loans								0
Interest on time deposits								0
Interest on gov. bonds								0
Interest on foreign bonds								0
Interest on reserves								0
ΔM_h^c	$-\Delta M_h^c$			$+\Delta M_b^c$			$+\Delta M_x^c$	0
ΔM_h	$-\Delta M_h$			$+\Delta M_b$				0
ΔH_b				$+\Delta H_b$		$-\Delta H$	$+\Delta H_x$	0
ΔL			$+\Delta L$	$-\Delta L$				0
ΔB	$-\Delta B_h$				$+\Delta B$		$+\Delta B_x$	0
ΔFB_h	$-\Delta FB_h$					$-\Delta FB_h$	$+\Delta FB_h$	0
ΔH^f						$-\Delta H^f$	$+\Delta H^f$	0

Variables - Economy Module

Variable	Description	Unit
<i>bondCentralBank</i>	Public bonds held by central bank	LCU
<i>capital_{se}</i>	Capital stock per sector	Units of capital
<i>capitalIntensity</i>	Capital intensity of the economic system	/
<i>capitalToOutput_{se}</i>	Capital-to-output ratio	Units of capital/unit of output
<i>capitalValue</i>	Monetary value of the capital stock	LCU
<i>checkdepositsHouseholds</i>	Households' check deposits	LCU
<i>carbonTaxRate_{se}</i>	Carbon tax rate applied to sector <i>se</i>	LCU/tonne CO ₂
<i>carbonTax_{se}</i>	Total carbon tax paid by sector <i>se</i> , based on its emissions and carbon tax rate	LCU/Year
<i>carbonTaxRevenue</i>	Total carbon tax revenue collected from all sectors	LCU/Year
<i>delayedDemand_{se}</i>	The demand from the previous period for each sector	LCU/Year
<i>delayedDisposableIncome</i>	Delayed disposable income	LCU/Year
<i>delayedDisposableIncome_{es,sg}</i>	Delayed disposable income per social group.	LCU/Year
<i>delayedExchangeRate</i>	Exchange rate from the previous period	FCU/LCU
<i>delayedExternalDebt</i>	Delayed external debt	LCU
<i>delayedGovernmentDebt</i>	Delayed Government debt	LCU
<i>delayedInflation_{ese}</i>	The delayed value of the inflation rate	1/year
<i>delayedInventories_{se}</i>	Delayed firms' inventories	Unit of good
<i>delayedInvestments_{se}</i>	Delayed investments	Unit of good/Year
<i>delayedLoans_{se}</i>	Delayed firms' loans	LCU
<i>delayedPrice_{ese}</i>	The delayed value of prices for the expanded sectors	LCU/unit of good
<i>delayedPriceImports_{ese}</i>	The delayed unit price of imported goods (expanded)	LCU/unit of good
<i>delayedWealthHouseholds</i>	Delayed households wealth	LCU
<i>demand_{se}</i>	Demand for each sector	Unit of good/Year
<i>disposableIncome</i>	Disposable income	LCU/Year
<i>disposableIncome_{es,sg}</i>	Disposable income by employment status and social group.	LCU/Year

Variable	Description	Unit
<i>disposableIncomePC</i>	Disposable income per capita	LCU/Person/Year
<i>disposableIncomePC_{es,sg}</i>	Disposable income per capita by employment status and social group.	LCU/Person/Year
<i>domesticCO2</i>	Total domestic CO ₂ emissions	Tonnes/Year
<i>domesticCO2_{se}</i>	Territorial emissions of CO ₂ per sector	Tonnes/Year
<i>employmentHours_{se,sg}</i>	Employment in hours, per sector and social group	Hours/Year
<i>employmentHours_{se}</i>	Total employment hours per sector	Hours /Year
<i>employmentPeople_{se}</i>	Total employment in terms of people per sector	Persons
<i>employmentRate</i>	Employment rate	Fraction
<i>employmentRate_{sg}</i>	Employment rate per social group	Fraction
<i>exchangeRate</i>	Exchange rate	FCU/LCU
<i>exportsReal_{se}</i>	The delayed unit price of imported goods (expanded)	Unit of good/Year
<i>exportsValue_{se}</i>	Monetary value of exports per each sector	LCU/Year
<i>exportsValueTot</i>	Monetary of value of exports	LCU/Year
<i>externalDebt</i>	External debt	LCU
<i>finalDemand_{se}</i>	Final demand for each sector	Unit of good/Year
<i>GDP</i>	Gross Domestic product Deflated	LCU/Year
<i>GDPNominal</i>	Gross Domestic product	LCU/Year
<i>GDPPC</i>	Deflated GDP per capita	LCU/Person/Year
<i>governmentDebt</i>	Total public debt	LCU
<i>governmentExpenditure</i>	Total government spending	LCU/Year
<i>governmentFinalDemandDeflated_{se}</i>	Deflated government final demand for each sector	LCU/Year
<i>governmentFinalDemandImportsNominal_{se}</i>	Government final demand for foreign production	LCU/Year
<i>governmentFinalDemandImportsReal_{se}</i>	Government final demand for foreign production in real terms	Unit of good/Year
<i>governmentFinalDemandNominal_{se}</i>	Government final demand for each sector	LCU/Year
<i>governmentFinalDemandReal_{se}</i>	Government final demand for domestic production in real terms	Unit of good/Year
<i>governmentFinalDemandTot</i>	Total government final demand	LCU/Year
<i>governmentIncome</i>	Fiscal revenues	LCU/Year
<i>grossIncome_{es,sg}</i>	Gross income per social group per employment status	LCU/Year
<i>grossIncomePC_{es,sg}</i>	Gross income per social group per employment status, per person	LCU/Person/Year

Variable	Description	Unit
<i>grossProfits</i>	Gross profits	LCU/Year
<i>grossProfits_{se}</i>	Gross profits per sector	LCU/Year
<i>grossWages</i>	Gross wages	LCU/Year
<i>grossWages_{se,sg}</i>	Gross wages per sector and social group	LCU/Year/Year
<i>grossWages_{se}</i>	Gross wages per sector	LCU/Year
<i>grossWages_{sg}</i>	Gross wages per social group	LCU/Year
<i>householdFinalDemand</i>	Total household final demand	LCU/Year
<i>householdFinalDemand_{se}</i>	Household final demand per sector	LCU/Year
<i>householdFinalDemandDeflated_{se}</i>	Deflated household final demand per sector	LCU/Year
<i>householdFinalDemandDomestic</i>	Household nominal demand for domestic goods	LCU/Year
<i>householdFinalDemandImported</i>	Household nominal demand for imported goods	LCU/Year
<i>householdFinalDemandImports_{se}</i>	Household nominal demand for imported goods per each sector	LCU/Year
<i>importsNominal</i>	Nominal imports	LCU/Year
<i>importsNominal_{se}</i>	Nominal imports per sector	LCU/Year
<i>importsValueIntermediate_{se}</i>	Nominal value of intermediate imports	LCU/Year
<i>incomeTaxes_{es,sg}</i>	Fiscal revenue for social group and employment status	LCU/Year
<i>incomeTaxesPC_{es,sg}</i>	Fiscal revenue for social group and employment status, per person	LCU/Person/Year
<i>indexCPI</i>	CPI index	Fraction
<i>inflation_{ese}</i>	Inflation per each sector	1/year
<i>inflationCPI</i>	Inflation CPI	1/year
<i>intermediateCosts_{se}</i>	Intermediate costs	LCU/Year
<i>inventories_{se}</i>	Inventories per each sector	Unit of good
<i>investments_{se}</i>	Investments per each sector	Unit of good/Year
<i>investmentsDomestic_{se}</i>	Investments in domestic capital goods per each sector	Unit of good/Year
<i>investmentsDomesticNominal_{se}</i>	Nominal investments in domestic capital goods per each sector	LCU/Year
<i>investmentsNominal_{se}</i>	Nominal investments per each sector	LCU/Year
<i>labourForce</i>	Labour force	People
<i>labourForceParticipationRate</i>	The labour force participation rate	Fraction
<i>labourForcePeople_{sg}</i>	Labour force per each social group	People

Variable	Description	Unit
<i>labourIntensity_{ese}</i>	Labour intensity	working hours/unit of good
<i>labourProductivityGrowth</i>	Labour productivity growth rate	1/year
<i>loans</i>	Loans	LCU
<i>loans_{se}</i>	Loans per each sector	LCU
<i>marginalTaxRate_{tb}</i>	Marginal tax rate	Percentage
<i>markup</i>	Markup	Fraction
<i>monetaryWage</i>	Monetary wage	LCU
<i>NDP</i>	Net domestic product	LC/YearU
<i>netProfit</i>	Net profits	LC/YearU
<i>netProfits_{se}</i>	Net profits per each sector	LC/YearU
<i>netWealthBank</i>	Net wealth of commercial bank	LCU
<i>netWealthCentralBank</i>	Net wealth of central bank	LCU
<i>netWealthFirms</i>	Net wealth of firms	LCU
<i>netWealthGovernment</i>	Net wealth of government	LCU
<i>netWealthHouseholds</i>	Net wealth of households	LCU
<i>nominalWageGrowth</i>	Growth rate of nominal wages	1/year
<i>outputDeflated_{se}</i>	Deflated output per each sector	LCU/Year
<i>outputExpected_{se}</i>	Expected demand	Unit of good/Year
<i>outputNominal_{se}</i>	Nominal value of output per each sector	LCU/Year
<i>outputReal_{se}</i>	Output produced by each sector	Unit of good/Year
<i>pensionBenefits</i>	Pension benefits	LCU/Year
<i>pensionBenefits_{sg}</i>	Pension benefits per each social group	LCU/Year
<i>pensionBenefitsPC</i>	Pension benefits per pensioner	LCU/Person/Year
<i>population</i>	Total population	People
<i>population_{ag,sg}</i>	Population per age group and social group	Persons
<i>population_{es,sg}</i>	Population per employment status and social group	
<i>populationAdult</i>	Adult population	
<i>populationGrowth</i>	Population growth rate	1/year

Variable	Description	Unit
<i>populationWorkingAge</i>	Working age population	Persons
<i>populationWorkingAge_{sg}</i>	Working age population per each social group	Persons
<i>populationWorkingAgeGrowth</i>	Working age population growth rate	1/year
<i>price_{ese}</i>	The unit price of domestic goods (expanded vector)	LCU/unit of good
<i>priceImports_{ese}</i>	The unit price of imported goods (expanded vector)	LCU/unit of good
<i>profitTaxes_{se}</i>	Taxes on profits per each sector	LCU/Year
<i>propensityToConsumeV</i>	Propensity to consume out of income	Fraction
<i>publicDeficit</i>	Public deficit	LCU
<i>reserves</i>	Commercial bank reserves	LCU
<i>retainedProfits_{se}</i>	Retained profits per each sector	LCU/Year
<i>retiredPopulation</i>	Retired population	Persons
<i>retiredPopulationGrowth</i>	Growth rate of retired population	1/year
<i>sales_{se}</i>	Sales in each sector	LCU/Year
<i>sfcCheck</i>	Redundant equation	LCU/Year
<i>socialBenefitsOther_{es,sg}</i>	Other types of social benefits per social group and employment status	LCU/Year
<i>socialBenefitsOtherPC_{es}</i>	Other types of social benefits per employment status, per person	LCU/Person/Year
<i>socialContributions</i>	Social contributions	LCU/Year
<i>taxBracketLower_{tb}</i>	Lower tax bracket	LCU
<i>taxBracketUpper_{tb}</i>	Upper tax bracket	LCU
<i>timedepositsHouseholds</i>	Time deposits	LCU
<i>unemployedPeople</i>	The unemployment in people	Persons
<i>unemploymentBenefits</i>	Total unemployment benefits	LCU/Year
<i>unemploymentBenefits_{sg}</i>	Unemployment benefits per social group	LCU/Year
<i>unemploymentBenefitsPC</i>	The unemployment benefits per unemployed person	LCU/Person/Year
<i>unemploymentRate</i>	Unemployment rate	Fraction
<i>unemploymentRate_{sg}</i>	Unemployment rate per each sector	Fraction
<i>valueAdded_{se}</i>	The value added per sector	LCU/Year
<i>weeklyWorkHours_{se}</i>	Working hours per each week	Hours

Parameters - Economy Module

Parameter	Description	Unit
<i>adjustmentSpeed</i>	Adjustment speed of the carbon tax	Fraction
<i>baseMarginalTaxRate_{tb}</i>	The base marginal tax rate per tax bracket	Fraction
<i>baseMarkup</i>	The base markup level that firms use	Fraction
<i>baseSocialBenefitsOtherPC_{es}</i>	The base social benefits per capita per employment status	LCU/Person/year
<i>ExpParameter</i>	Parameter in the adaptive expectation function	/
<i>capitalistsPerAdult</i>	Fraction of capitalists in the adult population	Proportion
<i>carbonPriceStartYear</i>	The year when the carbon price change gets implemented	Year
<i>CO2EmissionsTarget</i>	Target level of total domestic CO ₂ emissions across all sectors	Tonne/Year
<i>delayTime</i>	Time delay	/
<i>depreciationRate_{se}</i>	Capital depreciation rate per each sector	Fraction
<i>domesticRatioHouseholds</i>	Share of household final demand for domestic goods	Fraction
<i>employmentDistribution_{se,sg}</i>	The distribution of employment in each sector split over social groups. This sums to 1 per sector	Fraction
<i>governmentFinalDemandIncrease_{se}</i>	Relative change in government final demand	Fraction
<i>governmentFinalDemandIncreaseEndYear</i>	The year when the government final demand increase ends	Year
<i>governmentFinalDemandIncreaseStartYear</i>	The year when the government final demand increase starts	Year
<i>governmentSpendingElasticity</i>	Elasticity of government final demand with respect to the population level	Dimensionless
<i>grossWagesDistribution_{se,sg}</i>	Subgroup (sector and social group) share in total gross wages	Fraction
<i>labourProductivityGrowthBase</i>	Growth rate of labour productivity (intercept)	1/Year
<i>markupIncrease</i>	Relative change in markups	Fraction
<i>markupIncreaseEndYear</i>	The year when the markup change ends	Year
<i>markupIncreaseStartYear</i>	The year when the markup change starts	Year
<i>maxCarbonTaxRate</i>	Maximum carbon tax	LCU/tonne
<i>minimumIncomeStartYear</i>	The year when the minimum income guarantee gets implemented	Year
<i>policyMarginalTaxRate_{tb}</i>	Marginal tax rate per each fiscal bracket (policy scenario)	Fraction

Parameter	Description	Unit
<i>policySocialBenefitsOtherPC_{es}</i>	Other social benefits per each employment status, per person (policy scenario)	LCU
<i>priceBase_{se}</i>	The unit price of goods in the non-capital sectors	LCU/unit of good
<i>priceImports_{se}</i>	The unit prices of imported goods	LCU/unit of good
<i>progressiveTaxationStartYear</i>	The year when the higher progressive taxation gets implemented	Year
<i>propensityToConsumeData</i>	Propensity to consume (baseline)	Fraction
<i>propensityToConsumeIncrease</i>	The year when working time reduction gets implemented	Fraction
<i>propensityToConsumeIncreaseEndYear</i>	The year when the propensity to consume increase ends	Year
<i>propensityToConsumeIncreaseStartYear</i>	The year when the propensity to consume increase starts	Year
<i>sectorSplitHouseholdFinalDemand_{se}</i>	Share of household final demand per each domestic sector	Fraction
<i>sectorSplitHouseholdFinalDemandImports_{se}</i>	Share of household final demand per each foreign sector	Fraction
<i>socialBenefitsFraction_{es}</i>	The fraction of other social benefits compared to aggregate wage rate	Fraction
<i>socialContributionRate</i>	Tax rate for social contributions	Fraction
<i>taxRateCorporateIncome</i>	Corporate income tax rate	LCU
<i>weeklyWorkHoursBase_{se}</i>	The base number of weekly work hours per sector	Hours
<i>workingTimeReductionMagnitude</i>	Relative reduction in working time	Fraction
<i>workingTimeReductionStartYear</i>	Starting year in the reduction of working time	Year
<i>workingWeeksPerYear</i>	The number of working weeks per year	

6 Documentation of the Demographics Module

6.1 Module behaviour: qualitative description

The Demographics module creates a system of equations describing population and subpopulation dynamics by age group and gender (here, mainly sex), or by age group and social group (skill and gender).

Changes in the population stock are calculated at the level of subpopulations for each age group and gender. For each age group and gender, the population stock is adjusted by:

- subtracting deaths,
- adding net migration,
- adding people “ageing” into this age group (except for the youngest age group),
- subtracting people “ageing” out of this age group (except the oldest age group).

For the youngest age group, births are added in addition to the above terms.

Deaths are calculated for each age group and gender using age-group and gender-specific mortality rates. Net migration is calculated by multiplying each subpopulation (based on age group and gender) by a uniform net migration rate (which is a simplification that will affect overall population dynamics. However, subgroup-specific data are lacking). Transfer between age groups (ageing in, ageing out) is calculated via the share of the oldest age-year in the age group. Births are calculated via (population-weighted) average fertility rates for females of the respective fertile age groups, and the sex ratio of the newborns.

Mortality rates are calculated on the basis of panel regression modelling, using coefficients derived from a random-effects, fixed-slopes regression approach and a range of endogenous and exogenous drivers. The eight demographic cohorts in the model are calculated using bespoke coefficients derived from the panel regression. Fertility rates are projected using a constant absolute annual increment which is set as a scenario parameter, with the “BusinessAsUsual” value being based on UN WPP projections. Net migration rates and their constant absolute annual increment are set as scenario parameters, with the “BusinessAsUsual” `netMigrationRate` set to the 2000-2021 average rate, and the “BusinessAsUsual” absolute annual increment is roughly based on data from Spain's National Statistics Institute (INE). The share of the oldest age-year in the age group is extrapolated at the 2020-2021 average annual absolute increment derived from UN WPP data. Note that because this approach is likely to introduce an inconsistency, as this share is technically altered by population dynamics, but adequately modelling this would require modelling each age-year.

Note that there are significant uncertainties in the future evolution of fertility rates and net migration rates, which affect overall population dynamics.

Total population is calculated bottom-up by aggregating subpopulations by age group and gender.

Subpopulations by age group and gender are translated into subpopulations by age group and social group (skill level + gender) using the historical skill level distribution (from EXIOBASE).

The module also calculates the global population, based on the projections of a given shared socioeconomic pathway (SSP).

6.2 Module behaviour: equations

Population dynamics are calculated at the subpopulation level (by age group and gender), via differential equations.

6.2.1 Youngest age group

For the youngest age group, age 0 to 17 in our model, subpopulation change is modelled as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt}(\text{population}_{ag,ge}) = & \sum_{ag=\text{ageGroups}_{fertile}} (\text{population}_{ag,ge=female} \cdot \text{fertilityRateFemales}_{ag}) \\ & \cdot \text{sexRatioOfNewborns}_{ge} \\ & + \text{population}_{ag,ge} \\ & \cdot (-\text{populationShareOldestAgeYear}_{ag,ge} + \text{netMigrationRate} - \text{mortalityRate}_{ag,ge}) \end{aligned} \quad (231)$$

This equation considers the following factors:

- influx of new individuals from births
- outflux of individuals ageing out of this age group (into the next one)
- net influx of individuals from net migration
- deaths within this age group

6.2.2 Middle two age groups

For the middle two age group (age 18 to 44, and 45 to 63, respectively) subpopulation change is modelled as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt}(\text{population}_{ag,ge}) = & \text{population}_{ag-1,ge} \cdot \text{populationShareOldestAgeYear}_{ag-1,ge} \\ & + \text{population}_{ag,ge} \\ & \cdot (-\text{populationShareOldestAgeYear}_{ag,ge} + \text{netMigrationRate} - \text{mortalityRate}_{ag,ge}) \end{aligned} \quad (232)$$

This equation considers the following factors:

- influx of individuals ageing into the group from the previous younger age group.
- outflux of individuals ageing out of this age group (into the next one).
- net influx of individuals from net migration
- deaths within this age group

6.2.3 Oldest age group

For the oldest age group, age 64 and above, subpopulation change is modelled as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt}(\text{population}_{ag,ge}) = & \text{population}_{ag-1,ge} \cdot \text{populationShareOldestAgeYear}_{ag-1,ge} \\ & + \text{population}_{ag,ge} \cdot (\text{netMigrationRate} - \text{mortalityRate}_{ag,ge}) \end{aligned} \quad (233)$$

This equation considers the following factors:

- influx of Individuals ageing into the group from the previous younger age group.
- net influx of individuals from net migration
- deaths within this age group

6.3 Main factors affecting population dynamics

6.3.1 Mortality rates (and accounting for climate change impacts on mortality)

Mortality rates are calculated on the basis of panel regression modelling, using coefficients derived from a random-effects, fixed-slopes panel regression approach and a range of endogenous and exogenous drivers. The eight demographic cohorts in the model are calculated using bespoke coefficients derived from the panel regression.

The regression models are built where the dependent variable is equal to the cohort-specific log mortality rate. Base mortality rate data for these dependent variables are sourced from UN Population Database. The predictors are chosen based on a general literature regarding the socioeconomic determinants of mortality in developed countries, and supplemented by additional literature and Global Burden of Disease data regarding the drivers of mortality between older and younger age groups, and between women and men (e.g., Vollset et al, 2024; Gavurova et al, 2020).

The factors affecting mortality rates in our model are: occurrence of self-harm, fine particulate matter (PM2.5), transport injuries, health care access (logarithm of health output per capita in nominal terms), health care workers, the share of private health expenditure, and the occurrence of heart disease, dementia, and stroke. Of these, healthcare-related variable (such as log health expenditure, share of private healthcare, and healthcare workers) are endogenous, and specific injury or disease related variables (heart disease, transport injuries, and so on) are exogenous.

The results of this regression are summarised below, with coefficients for the eight dependent mortality rate variables (coded as M1-M4, in ascending order of age for our model cohorts, and F1-F4).

Predictor	M1	M2	M3	M4	F1	F2	F3	F4
<i>logHealthPC</i>	-0.2352	-0.164	-	-0.1929	-0.1753	-	-0.1413	-0.1157
<i>privateHealth</i>	-	-	-	0.2558	-	-	-	-
<i>logExposurePM25</i>	-	0.5953	0.6529	0.1188	-	-	0.2988	-
<i>healthWorkers</i>	-	-	-0.0018	-0.0012	-	-0.0011	-	-0.0013
<i>transportInjuryMortality</i>	0.0002	-	-	-	0.0002	0.0002	-	-
<i>selfHarmMortality</i>	0.0006	0.0012	-	-	0.0006	0.0006	0.0005	-
<i>dementiaMortality</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0002
<i>strokeF4Mortality</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.00001273
<i>heartDiseaseMortality</i>	-	-	0.00003223	0.00002915	-	-	-	-

These coefficients are produced from a panel regression model for each cohort-specific mortality rate. The average number of data observations for each of these models is approximately 440, with an average of 20 observations per country, and almost 15 observations per time period. Each model has its own measure of predictive power and statistical significance, but all variables in all models have p-values lower than 0.05, an average overall R² figure of 0.49, and an average “within” R² value of 0.79.

Some of these predictors are calculated within the model using a range of endogenous variables. For example, health expenditure per capita is calculated using the healthcare portion of total output (to represent both government and household final demand devoted to health expenditure), divided by population. This is then multiplied by an offset factor to correct for the difference between the model data, and the data on which the regression model was based.

$$healthPC = \frac{outputDeflated_s e_{healthCare}}{population} \cdot logHealthOffset \quad (234)$$

The logarithm (base 10) of this $healthPC$ variable is then taken to estimate $logHealthPC$:

$$logHealthPC = log_{10}(healthPC) \quad (235)$$

A further predictor in our mortality rate calculation is the total share of private healthcare (represented as the healthcare portion of household final demand). As with $healthPC$, a data offset is included.

$$privateHealth = \frac{householdFinalDemand_s e_{healthCare}}{outputNominal_s e_{healthCare}} \cdot privateHealthOffset \quad (236)$$

Finally, for endogenous variable calculation, total health workers per 10,000 people is calculated as follows:

$$healthWorkers = \left(\frac{employmentPeople_s e_{healthCare}}{population} \cdot 10000 \right) \cdot healthWorkersOffset \quad (237)$$

For exogenous drivers of mortality, future values are calculated using an exponential decay function, where the exponent is a rate of change calculated based on past Global Burden of Disease data (using `scipy curve_fit` function in Python). This is under the assumption that the exogenous drivers of mortality used in the model, in developed countries like Spain, will follow past trends and decrease over the course of the model simulation, whilst (logically) never falling below zero (incidences of traffic collisions, or prevalence of heart disease, for example) An example of one of these equations is included below, in the case of $heartDiseaseMortality$, and this functional form is replicated identically for all exogenous predictors sourced from Global Burden of Disease:

$$\frac{d(heartDiseaseMortality)}{dt} = -heartDiseaseRate \cdot \frac{heartDiseaseMortality}{heartDiseaseRisk} \quad (238)$$

The model equation is written in a way that allows for simultaneous calculation of the eight mortality rates, even where some predictors do not apply to a specific mortality rate model. In these cases, coefficients for that variable are included as 0 so it is effectively passed over. The equation is listed in full below:

$$\begin{aligned} logMortalityRate_{ag,ge} = & bSelfHarm_{ag,ge} \cdot selfHarmMortality \\ & + bTransportInjury_{ag,ge} \cdot transportInjuryMortality + \\ & bLogHealth_{ag,ge} \cdot logHealthPC + bPrivateHealth_{ag,ge} \cdot privateHealth + \\ & bHealthWorkers_{ag,ge} \cdot healthWorkers + bLogPM25_{ag,ge} \cdot logExposurePM25 + \\ & bHeartDisease_{ag,ge} \cdot heartDiseaseMortality \\ & + bDementia_{ag,ge} \cdot dementiaMortality + \\ & bStrokeF4_{ag,ge} \cdot strokeF4Mortality + mortalityOffset_{ag,ge} \end{aligned} \quad (239)$$

An offset, $mortalityOffset_{ag,ge}$, is included to reconcile mortality rate data on which the coefficients were calculated with the mortality rate data used in the model.

As the mortality rates are calculated above as $logMortalityRate_{ag,ge}$, they must be transformed back to base mortality rates by taking the exponent. Finally the impact of climate change on mortality in terms of excess heat deaths is accounted for in terms of a $heatDeathMultiplier$ that scales with global temperature change (described in more detail in the Sustainability module):

$$mortalityRate_{ag,ge} = 10^{logMortalityRate_{ag,ge}} (1 + heatDeathMultiplier) \quad (240)$$

6.3.2 Impact of Working Hours on Mortality rate

The Demographics module also integrates empirical evidence linking long working hours to increased risk of coronary heart disease (CHD) and stroke. The model uses interpolated risk functions, applies them at the sector level, and aggregates the results to influence cause-specific mortality rates dynamically over time (which feed into the calculation of overall mortality rates). These affect overall and distributional populations dynamics, as well as life expectancy estimates and consequently life satisfaction. As such, these mechanisms reflect that reducing stress and increasing leisure time can ultimately contribute to improved long-term public health and happiness.

To translate weekly working hours into health risk levels, we use empirical estimates of risk levels for specific working hours (Descatha et al., 2020; Kivimäki et al., 2015; Bannai & Tamakoshi, 2014; Virtanen et al., 2012), and interpolate these to get a continuous spectrum of risk levels for each sector's average weekly working hours. The following empirical values for weekly working hours and corresponding relative risk for coronary heart disease are used:

$$\begin{aligned} heartDiseaseHours &= [30.0, 40.0, 50.0, 55.0, 60.0] \quad \text{and} \quad heartDiseaseRiskPerHour \\ &= [1.0, 1.05, 1.12, 1.20, 1.20] \end{aligned} \quad (241)$$

$$\begin{aligned} strokeHours &= [30.0, 40.0, 50.0, 52.5, 60.0] \quad \text{and} \quad strokeRiskPerHour \\ &= [1.0, 1.1, 1.3, 1.4, 1.4] \end{aligned} \quad (242)$$

A sector-specific relative risk is interpolated from these values, using a Julia function for LinearInterpolation:

$$\begin{aligned} heartDiseaseRisk_{se} &= \text{LinearInterpolation}(heartDiseaseHours, heartDiseaseRiskPerHour, \text{extrapolate} \\ &= \text{true})(weeklyWorkHours_{se}) \end{aligned} \quad (243)$$

$$\begin{aligned} strokeRisk_{se} &= \text{LinearInterpolation}(strokeHours, strokeRiskPerHour, \text{extrapolate} \\ &= \text{true})(weeklyWorkHours_{se}) \end{aligned} \quad (244)$$

To reflect system-wide impacts, sector-level risks are aggregated using workforce weights:

$$heartDiseaseRisk = \frac{\sum_{se} employmentPeople_{se} \cdot heartDiseaseRisk_{se}}{\sum_{se} employmentPeople_{se}} \quad (245)$$

$$strokeRisk = \frac{\sum_{se} employmentPeople_{se} \cdot strokeRisk_{se}}{\sum_{se} employmentPeople_{se}} \quad (246)$$

Disease-specific mortality evolves dynamically based on the deviation of current risk from a baseline decay rate:

$$\frac{d}{dt}(heartDiseaseMortality) = -heartDiseaseRate \cdot \frac{heartDiseaseMortality}{heartDiseaseRisk} \quad (247)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(strokeF4Mortality) = -strokeF4Rate \cdot \frac{strokeF4Mortality}{strokeRisk} \quad (248)$$

$heartDiseaseMortality$ and $strokeF4Mortality$ represent the mortality rates for coronary heart disease and stroke. This captures cumulative long-term effects of working conditions on public health.

6.3.3 Sex ratios of newborns

The sex ratio of newborns is extrapolated based on constant annual absolute increments from historical data:

$$\frac{d}{dt}(sexRatioOfNewborns_{ge}) = slopeSexRatioOfNewborns_{ge} \quad (249)$$

6.3.4 Fertility rates

Fertility rates are projected based on constant annual absolute increments set as scenario parameters (with “BusinessAsUsual’ figures based on UN WPP projections):

$$\frac{d}{dt}(fertilityRateFemales_{ag}) = changeInFertilityRateFemales_{ag} \quad (250)$$

6.3.5 Population shares of the oldest age-year in each age group

The population shares of the oldest age-year in a given age group are extrapolated based on constant annual absolute increments based on historical data, by age group and gender:

$$\frac{d}{dt}(populationShareOldestAgeYear_{ag,ge}) = slopePopulationShareOldestAgeYear_{ag,ge} \quad (251)$$

Note that simply extrapolating past trends here is likely to be somewhat inconsistent with the shares that would be obtained from population dynamics (if we were to resolve each age-year).

6.3.6 Net migration rate

Net migration rates are projected based on constant annual absolute increments set as scenario parameters (with “BusinessAsUsual’ figures based on projections from Spain's National Statistics Institute (INE)).

$$\frac{d}{dt}(netMigrationRate) = changeInNetMigrationRate \quad (252)$$

6.4 Translation to population distribution by age group and social group (not just by gender)

The absolute population distribution by age group and gender is translated into an absolute population distribution by age group and social group (which in turn differentiates gender and three skills levels) by multiplying the former with the historical relative population distribution by skill level distribution and gender.

$$population_{ag,sg} = \begin{cases} population_{ag,ge=male} \cdot initSkillLevelDistribution_{ag,sg} & \text{if } sg \text{ is male,} \\ population_{ag,ge=female} \cdot initSkillLevelDistribution_{ag,sg} & \text{if } sg \text{ is female} \end{cases} \quad \forall ag, sg \quad (253)$$

6.5 Aggregation of total population

Total population is calculated bottom-up by summing up the subpopulations per age group and gender:

$$population = \sum_{ag} \sum_{ge} population_{ag,ge} \quad (254)$$

6.6 Net migration

Net migration (immigration minus emigration) is calculated by multiplying the total population with the net migration rate.

$$netMigration = population \cdot netMigrationRate \quad (255)$$

6.7 Global population

The population module also includes the evolution of the global population. This is not modelled endogenously, but is based on the projections of a given shared socioeconomic pathway (SSP). Given a choice for the parameter *sharedSocioEconomicPathway*, the global population is calculated accordingly:

$$populationGlobal(t) = populationGlobal_{sharedSocioEconomicPathway}(t) \quad (256)$$

Indices - Demographics Module

Index	Description	Unit
<i>ag</i>	ageGroups	Distinguishes age brackets relevant for fertility rates, mortality rates, and labour force participation
<i>ge</i>	genders	Different genders (technically sexes), relevant for fertility rates, mortality rates, labour force participation, and gender inequalities
<i>sg</i>	socialGroups	Different social groups based on skill levels and gender, relevant for labour supply and income inequalities
<i>sp</i>	sharedSocioeconomicPathways	Different shared socioeconomic pathways (SSPs) used for global population projections

Variables - Demographics Module

Variable	Description	Unit
<i>dementiaMortality</i>	Prevalance of dementia, age standardised	Prevalent cases per 100,000 people
<i>employmentPeople_{se}</i>	Sectoral employment variable	People
<i>fertilityRateFemales_{ag}</i>	Age-year population-weighted average births per year per female of given age group	Births per year per female
<i>healthPC</i>	Total health output per capita	LCU
<i>healthWorkers</i>	Total healthcare workers per 10,000 of population	Worker per 10,000
<i>heartDiseaseMortality</i>	Prevalance of heart disease, age standardised	Prevalent cases 100,000 people
<i>heartDiseaseRisk</i>	Risk of heart disease	Prevalence of disease per 100,000
<i>heartDiseaseRiskInterp</i>	Interpolated link between long working hours to increased risk of heart disease	Relative Risk
<i>heatDeathMultiplier</i>	Mortality rate multiplier for heat deaths	Dimensionless
<i>householdFinalDemand</i>	Household final demand by sector	LCU/year
<i>logExposurePM25</i>	Exposure to particulate matter 2.5 in log terms	Average annual exposure (micrograms per cubic metre)
<i>logHealthPC</i>	Total log health output per capita	Dimensionless
<i>logMortalityRate_{ag,ge}</i>	Age and sex specific logarithm of the mortality rate per person	log mortality rate per person
<i>mortalityRate_{ag,ge}</i>	Total population	Deaths per person
<i>mortalityRate_{ag,ge}</i>	Mortality rate per age group and gender	Deaths per person per year
<i>netMigration</i>	Net inflow of people (immigration - emigration) per year	Net immigrants per resident per year

Variable	Description	Unit
<i>netMigrationRate</i>	Net inflow of people (immigration - emigration) per current resident per year	Net immigrants per resident per year
<i>outputNominal_{se}</i>	Nominal output by sector	LCU/year
<i>population</i>	Total population	People
<i>population_{ag,ge}</i>	Population per age group and gender	People
<i>population_{ag,sg}</i>	Population per age group and social group	People
<i>populationGlobal</i>	The total global population	People
<i>populationShareOldestAgeYear_{ag,ge}</i>	Population share of oldest age-year in age group, per age group and gender	Proportion
<i>privateHealth</i>	Total share of health output as household final demand (proxy for private health expenditure)	LCU
<i>selfHarmMortality</i>	Prevalance of self harm, age standardised	Prevalent cases per 100,000 people
<i>sexRatioOfNewborns_{ge}</i>	Share of newborns being born with male/female sex	Proportion
<i>strokeF4Mortality</i>	Incidences of stroke, oldest female age cohort	Incidences per 100,000 people
<i>strokeRisk</i>	Risk of stroke	Prevalence of disease per 100,000
<i>strokeRiskInterp</i>	Interpolated link between long working hours to increased risk of stroke	Relative Risk
<i>transportInjuryMortality</i>	Incidences of transport injury, age standardised	Incidences per 100,000 people
<i>weeklyWorkHours_{se}</i>	The average weekly work hours per person in a specific sector	Hours/Person

Parameters - Demographics Module

Parameter	Description	Unit
$bDementia_{ag,ge}$	Regression coefficient	Change in $logMortalityRate_{ag,ge}$ per change in prevalent cases of dementia per 100,000 people
$bHealthWorkers_{ag,ge}$	Regression coefficient	Change in $logMortalityRate_{ag,ge}$ per healthcare workers per 10,000 of population
$bHeartDisease_{ag,ge}$	Regression coefficient	Change in $logMortalityRate_{ag,ge}$ per change in prevalent cases of heart disease per 100,000 people
$bLogHealth_{ag,ge}$	Regression coefficient	Change in $logMortalityRate_{ag,ge}$ per unit of $logHealthPC$
$bLogPM25_{ag,ge}$	Regression coefficient	Change in $logMortalityRate_{ag,ge}$ per unit $logPM25$
$bPrivateHealth_{ag,ge}$	Regression coefficient	Change in $logMortalityRate_{ag,ge}$ per change in ratio of private health expenditure

Parameter	Description	Unit
$bSelfHarm_{ag,ge}$	Regression coefficient	Change in $logMortalityRate_{ag,ge}$ per unit of self harm prevalence per 100,000
$bStrokeF4_{ag,ge}$	Regression coefficient	Change in $logMortalityRate_{ag,ge}$ per change in stroke incidences among older women per 100,000
$bTransportInjury_{ag,ge}$	Regression coefficient	Change in $logMortalityRate_{ag,ge}$ per unit of transport injury incidences per 100,000
$changeInFertilityRateFemales_{ag}$	Absolute annual increment in age-year population-weighted average births per year per female of given age group	Births per year-squared per female
$changeInNetMigrationRate$	Absolute annual increment in the net migration rate	Net immigrants per resident per year-squared
$dementiaRate$	Exponential decay curve based on historic rates of change	Rate of decay
$heartDiseaseHours$	Working hour related to heart disease	Hour
$heartDiseaseRate$	Exponential decay curve based on historic rates of change	Rate of decay
$heartDiseaseRiskPerHour$	Risk of heart disease related to extra working time	Relative risk
$initSkillLevelDistribution_{ag,sg}$	Historical distribution of population by skill level and gender	Proportion
$populationGlobal_{sp}$	The global population projection for a given SSP	People
$selfHarmRate$	Exponential decay curve based on historic rates of change	Rate of decay
$sharedSocioeconomicPathway$	The shared socioeconomic pathway that is chosen as scenario	Dimensionless
$slopeSexRatioOfNewborns_{ge}$	Absolute annual increment in the male/female share of newborns	1 / year
$strokeF4Rate$	Exponential decay curve based on historic rates of change	Rate of decay
$strokeHours$	Working hour related to stroke	Hour
$strokeRiskPerHour$	Risk of stroke related to extra working time	Relative risk

Parameter	Description	Unit
<i>transportInjuryRate</i>	Exponential decay curve based on historic rates of change	Rate of decay

7 Documentation of Policies

Changing scenario parameters to simulate policies can result in changes in many model variables, including environmental and social indicators. This section therefore focuses on describing the direct effects of each scenario parameter or policy lever but does not necessarily detail knock-on effects.

7.1 Income Redistribution (Transfers)

Changes in transfers can be modelled by changing other social benefits per capita for each employment status $socialBenefitsOtherPC_{es}$, by changing the corresponding scenario parameters. Changes in other social benefits per capita affect the distribution of disposable income (and thus $incomeFairness$ and $incomeAdequacy$) as well as total disposable income (through changing the average effective tax rate), which in turn changes output and employment, with further knock-on effects on income, and so on.

In the “BusinessAsUsual” scenario, $socialBenefitsOtherPC_{es}$ is uniform across employment statuses, based on the total other social benefits divided by the adult population.

The “LivingIncome” scenario changes $socialBenefitsOtherPC_{es}$ to introduce differentiated public transfers for different employment statuses to ensure that, at a minimum, they reach a minimum wage standard of living (€11,500 per capita per year), intended to represent a simple version of a living income or minimum income guarantee.

Most employment statuses, such as *employed*, *unemployed* and *pensioners*, have other sources of income in the model, either in the form of wages or other benefits payments. The level of $socialBenefitsOtherPC_{es}$ is calculated for each employment status as the positive difference (if any) between the chosen minimum income level and the sum of any other income streams for the given employment status.

For *unemployed* and *outOfLabourForce* groups, this involves a substantial increase in state transfers to reach this basic threshold. Where other groups already meet this threshold, a basic “means tested” payment is applied, where much smaller additional transfers are provided on the assumption that $socialBenefitsOtherPC_{es}$ represents the sum total of additional welfare payments not captured in bespoke variables in the model (such as child benefits, disability support, other incentivising allowances, etc.). In other words, instead of setting these payments to zero, they are restricted. Because all profits created in the model go to capitalists, and the objective of the policy is more equitable redistribution, the value of additional $socialBenefitsOtherPC_{es}$ is set to 0 in the “LivingIncome” scenario.

Employment Status	Value of $socialBenefitsOtherPC_{es}$
Employed	€1000
Unemployed	€6056
Capitalist	€0
Pensioner	€2000
OutOfLabourForce	€11500

The level of social benefits at the start of the simulation is set to the base value, and the new policy value is applied from the year the policy kicks in:

$$socialBenefitsOtherPC_{es} = \begin{cases} baseSocialBenefitsOtherPC_{es} & \text{if } t < minimumIncomeStartYear \\ policySocialBenefitsOtherPC_{es} & \text{if } t \geq minimumIncomeStartYear \end{cases} \quad (257)$$

7.2 Income Redistribution (Taxation)

Changes in taxation can be modelled by changing the marginal income tax rates and the income boundaries of the corresponding tax brackets, both of which are implemented as scenario parameters. Changes in marginal tax rates or tax brackets affect effective tax rates for a given income level. Through this policy lever, the tax system can be made more or less progressive, relative to the baseline tax system which reflects Spain's current progressive tax system (as detailed below). Changes in taxation affect both the distribution of disposable income (and thus *incomeFairness* and *incomeAdequacy*) as well as total disposable income (through changing the average effective tax rate), which in turn changes output and employment, with further knock-on effects on income.

Income Bracket	Marginal tax rate for income bracket
€0 - 12,450	19%
€12,450 - 20,200	24%
€20,200 - 35,200	30%
€35,200 - 60,000	37%
€60,000 - 300,000	45%
€300,000 +	47%

As this tax system calculates tax payments as a function of individual-level gross (pre-tax) income, we first calculate the average gross income per person for each social group and employment status $grossIncomePC_{es,sg}$.

$$grossIncomePC_{es,sg} = \frac{grossIncome_{es,sg}}{population_{es,sg}} \quad (258)$$

Individual-level tax payments for each employment status and social group $incomeTaxesPC_{es,sg}$ are then calculated by multiplying the portion of income that falls into a given tax bracket with the corresponding marginal tax rate for that tax bracket $marginalTaxRate_{tb}$, and then summing these marginal tax payments over all tax brackets tb .

$$\begin{aligned}
 incomeTaxesPC_{es,sg} &= \sum_{tb} (grossIncomePC_{es,sg} \\
 &\geq taxBracketLower_{tb}) \\
 &\cdot (\min(grossIncomePC_{es,sg}, taxBracketUpper_{tb}) - taxBracketLower_{tb}) \\
 &\cdot marginalTaxRate_{tb}.
 \end{aligned} \quad (259)$$

Here, marginal tax rates for each tax bracket are defined as policy parameters:

$$marginalTaxRate_{tb} = \begin{cases} baseMarginalTaxRate_{tb} & \text{if } t < progressiveTaxationStartYear \\ policyMarginalTaxRate_{tb} & \text{if } t \geq progressiveTaxationStartYear \end{cases} \quad (260)$$

Total tax payments per social group and employment status are then obtained by multiplying the per-capita tax payments with the population size of the given social group and employment status:

$$incomeTaxes_{es,sg} = incomeTaxesPC_{es,sg} \cdot population_{es,sg} \quad (261)$$

7.3 Carbon Tax and Dividend

A Carbon Tax and Dividend policy can be modelled by introducing a dynamic carbon pricing mechanism that taxes sectoral CO₂ emissions and redistributes equal per-capita shares of the revenue to all adults. This policy aims to incentivize emission reductions while counteracting the regressive distributive effects of a stand-alone carbon tax.

The Carbon Tax and Dividend policy affects three main areas:

- Carbon tax rate dynamics
- Government revenue from carbon taxation
- Per capita redistribution through dividends

The initial value for the *carbonTaxRate* is based on the Net Effective Carbon Rates as reported by the OECD, which averaged €62.54 per tonne of CO₂e in Spain in 2023. The policy design is determined by three scenario parameters: *CO2EmissionsTarget*, *maxCarbonTaxRate_{se}* and *adjustmentSpeed*.

Carbon Tax Rate Adjustment The scenario parameters for the carbon tax can directly set a carbon tax rate or can activate a mechanism that adjusts tax rates endogenously based on whether CO₂ emissions remain below a target value.

In the latter case, carbon tax rates increase in sectors if aggregate CO₂ emissions exceed an exogenously defined target value. The increase occurs gradually, controlled by an adjustment speed parameter and capped at a maximum rate. This mechanism incrementally adjusts the carbon tax rate for each sector based on overall emissions performance and sector-specific contributions. If total domestic CO₂ emissions exceed the emissions target, the tax rate for each sector increases proportionally to that sector's share of total emissions. The speed of this adjustment is controlled by an exogenously defined parameter and ensures that more polluting sectors face steeper tax increases, while sectors with lower emissions see smaller adjustments. Theoretically, this approach creates an incentive for sectors to reduce their emissions to avoid higher carbon costs (although this latter mechanism is not yet implemented).

$$\frac{d}{dt}(\text{carbonTaxRate}_{se}) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{\text{domesticCO2}_{se}}{\text{domesticCO2}} \right) \cdot \text{adjustmentSpeed} \cdot (\text{maxCarbonTaxRate} - \text{carbonTaxRate}_{se}), & \text{if } \text{domesticCO2} > \text{CO2EmissionsTarget} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (262)$$

Carbon Tax Revenue Collection Carbon tax payments of each sector are calculated based on sectoral CO₂ emissions and the current carbon tax rate :

$$\text{carbonTax}_{se} = \text{carbonTaxRate}_{se} \cdot \text{domesticCO2}_{se} \quad (263)$$

Total revenue from the carbon tax is the sum of all sectoral carbon tax payments:

$$\text{carbonTaxRevenue} = \sum_{se} \text{carbonTax}_{se} \quad (264)$$

Integration into Sectoral Costs Carbon tax payments are treated as an additional cost to firms, which here is assumed to simply reduce their gross profits (i.e. firms do not pass these costs on to consumers via prices).

$$\begin{aligned}
grossProfits_{se} &= sales_{se} \cdot price_{ese} - intermediateCosts_{se} \\
&\quad - grossWages_{se} - \delta \cdot delayedLoans_{se} - carbonTax_{se}
\end{aligned} \tag{265}$$

In reality, a carbon tax would likely impact both pricing, investment decisions, profits, and the income distribution. These mechanisms are however not yet implemented in the model.

Integration into Public Accounts Carbon tax revenue adds to total government income:

$$\begin{aligned}
governmentIncome &= socialContributions + \sum_{se} profitTaxes_{se} \\
&\quad + \sum_{es,sg} incomeTaxes_{es,sg} + carbonTaxRevenue
\end{aligned} \tag{266}$$

As such, carbon tax revenue affects the public deficit and government debt, and could influence fiscal and monetary policy.

7.3.1 Worktime Reduction

A Worktime Reduction policy can be modelled by imposing a reduction in average weekly working hours. Our model incorporates impacts of changes in working hours on employment (Economy module) as well as on mortality rates (demographics module).

The Worktime Reduction policy is implemented as a persistent reduction in weekly working hours per sector, with the percentage reduction and the onset of the reduction set as the scenario parameters.

$$\begin{aligned}
&weeklyWorkHours_{se} \\
&= \begin{cases} weeklyWorkHoursBase_{se} \cdot (1 - workingTimeReductionMagnitude), & \text{if } t \geq workingTimeReductionStartYear \\ weeklyWorkHoursBase_{se}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}
\end{aligned} \tag{267}$$

Changes in weekly working hours impact employment, which in our model is calculated from total demand for labour hours and the weekly working hours (as described in the Economy module).

Impact of Working Hours on Mortality rate Our model incorporates the effect of long working hours on risks of coronary heart disease (CHD) and stroke, using empirical data of relative risk factors for specific working hour reference values (Descatha et al., 2020; Kivimäki et al., 2015; Bannai & Tamakoshi, 2014; Virtanen et al., 2012).

$$\begin{aligned}
heartDiseaseHours &= [30.0, 40.0, 50.0, 55.0, 60.0] \\
heartDiseaseRiskPerHour & \\
&= [1.0, 1.05, 1.12, 1.20, 1.20]
\end{aligned} \tag{268}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
strokeHours &= [30.0, 40.0, 50.0, 52.5, 60.0] \\
strokeRiskPerHour & \\
&= [1.0, 1.1, 1.3, 1.4, 1.4]
\end{aligned} \tag{269}$$

Sector-specific relative risk is interpolated from these values to estimate a continuous risk function for each sector'se:

$$\begin{aligned}
heartDiseaseRisk_{se} &= \text{LinearInterpolation}(heartDiseaseRiskPerHour, heartDiseaseHours, extrapolate \\
&= true)(weeklyWorkHours_{se})
\end{aligned}
\tag{270}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
strokeRisk_{se} &= \text{LinearInterpolation}(strokeRiskPerHour, strokeHours, extrapolate \\
&= true)(weeklyWorkHours_{se}), \quad \text{for } se \\
&\in sectors.range
\end{aligned}
\tag{271}$$

Average risk factors are then calculated as a weighted average of the risk factors for each sector, weighted by the share of each sector in total employment.

$$heartDiseaseRisk = \frac{\sum_{se} employmentPeople_{se} \cdot heartDiseaseRisk_{se}}{\sum_{se} employmentPeople_{se}}
\tag{272}$$

$$strokeRisk = \frac{\sum_{se} employmentPeople_{se} \cdot strokeRisk_{se}}{\sum_{se} employmentPeople_{se}}
\tag{273}$$

The impact of these risk on cause-specific mortality rates is incorporated by dividing the baseline decay rates of these mortality rates (estimated from data) by these average risk factors:

$$\frac{d}{dt}(heartDiseaseMortality) = -heartDiseaseRate \cdot \frac{heartDiseaseMortality}{heartDiseaseRisk}
\tag{274}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}(strokeF4Mortality) = -strokeF4Rate \cdot \frac{strokeF4Mortality}{strokeRisk}
\tag{275}$$

$heartDiseaseMortality$ and $strokeF4Mortality$ represent the mortality rates for coronary heart disease and stroke, respectively.

Risk factors greater than 1 thus lead to a smaller decline in cause-specific mortality rates, i.e. in relative terms, they increase cause-specific mortality rates.

Indices - Policies

Index	Description	Unit
<i>es</i>	Employment status	Represents different employment statuses
<i>sg</i>	Social group	Represents different social and skill groups
<i>tb</i>	Tax brackets	Represents different income taxation brackets

Variables - Policies

Variable	Description	Unit
<i>carbonTax_{se}</i>	Carbon tax payments by sector	LCU/year
<i>carbonTaxRate_{se}</i>	Carbon tax rate applied to sector <i>se</i>	LCU/tonne CO ₂
<i>carbonTaxRevenue</i>	Total carbon tax revenue	LCU/year
<i>domesticCO2</i>	Total domestic CO ₂ emissions across all sectors	Tonnes CO ₂ /year
<i>domesticCO2_{se}</i>	Sector-specific domestic CO ₂ emissions	Tonnes CO ₂ /year
<i>grossIncome_{es,sg}</i>	Gross income by employment status and social group	LCU/year
<i>grossIncomePC_{es,sg}</i>	Gross income per capita by employment status and social group	LCU/person/year
<i>heartDiseaseMortality</i>	Prevalence of heart disease, age standardised	Prevalence of disease per 100,000
<i>heartDiseaseRisk</i>	Risk of heart disease	Prevalence of disease per 100,000
<i>incomeTaxes_{es,sg}</i>	Total income taxes for all social groups and employment statuses	LCU/year
<i>incomeTaxesPC_{es,sg}</i>	Income tax payments per capita by social group and employment status	LCU/person/year
<i>output_{se}</i>	Total output of sector <i>se</i>	Output units/year
<i>population</i>	Total population used for per capita calculations	Persons
<i>population_{es,sg}</i>	Total population for employment statuses and social groups	Persons
<i>socialBenefitsOther_{es,sg}</i>	Other social benefits paid by the government to employment status <i>es</i> and social group <i>sg</i>	LCU/year
<i>strokeF4Mortality</i>	Incidences of stroke, oldest female age cohort	Prevalence of disease per 100,000
<i>strokeRisk</i>	Risk of stroke	Prevalence of disease per 100,000
<i>weeklyWorkHours_{se}</i>	Working hours per week by sector	Hour

Parameters - Policies

Parameter	Description	Unit
<i>adjustmentSpeed</i>	Proportion by which the carbon tax rate approaches the maximum if emissions exceed the target	Dimensionless
<i>baseMarginalTaxRate_{tb}</i>	The base marginal tax rates that are used in Spain for portions of income per capita in the model	Fraction
<i>baseSocialBenefitsOtherPC_{es}</i>	The initial social benefits per capita payments for different employment statuses	LCU/person
<i>CO2EmissionsTarget</i>	Target level of total domestic CO ₂ emissions across all sectors	Tonnes CO ₂ /year
<i>employmentDistribution_{se,sg}</i>	Share of employment hours assigned to social group and sector	Dimensionless
<i>heartDiseaseHours</i>	Reference values of weekly working hours for lookup table of heart disease risk rates	Hours
<i>heartDiseaseRate</i>	Exponential decay curve based on historic rates of change	Rate of decay
<i>heartDiseaseRiskPerHour</i>	Risk of heart disease related to extra working time	Dimensionless
<i>initialCarbonTaxRate_{se}</i>	Initial carbon tax rate applied to sector <i>se</i> at the beginning of the simulation	LCU/tonne CO ₂
<i>labourProductivityGrowth</i>	Growth rate of productivity over time	proportion per year
<i>maxCarbonTaxRate_{se}</i>	Maximum allowable carbon tax rate for sector <i>se</i> used in the adjustment mechanism	LCU/tonne CO ₂
<i>minimumIncomeStartYear</i>	The start year for the minimum income policy	Years
<i>policyMarginalTaxRate_{tb}</i>	The new marginal tax rate given by a progressive income policy	Fraction
<i>policySocialBenefitsOtherPC_{es}</i>	The social benefits per capita payments according to the minimum income policy for different employment statuses	LCU/person
<i>progressiveTaxationStartYear</i>	The start year of the progressive taxation policy	Years
<i>strokeF4Rate</i>	exponential decay curve based on historic rates of change	Rate of decay
<i>strokeHours</i>	Reference values of weekly working hours for lookup table of stroke risk rates	Hours
<i>strokeRiskPerHour</i>	Risk of stroke related to extra working time	Dimensionless

Parameter	Description	Unit
<i>taxRateLower_{tb}</i>	The lower bound of a given tax bracket for marginal income tax system implementation	LCU/year
<i>taxRateUpper_{tb}</i>	The upper bound of a given tax bracket for marginal income tax system implementation	LCU/year
<i>weeklyWorkHoursBase_{se}</i>	Baseline weekly working hours per sector	Hours
<i>workingTimeReductionMagnitude</i>	Proportion by which working time is reduced	Proportion
<i>workingTimeReductionStartYear</i>	Year in which the working time reduction begins	year
<i>workingWeeksPerYear</i>	Number of working weeks in a year	Weeks

8 Limitations and future improvements

Given the broad scope of the model, the complexity of the environment–society–economy system it aims to represent, and the relatively short development time of the model, there are of course numerous limitations to the present model. It’s important to note that the model is still in development and that the current implementation and calibration of the model are preliminary. Therefore, we refrain from showing or discussing simulation results until the model is fully calibrated and validated. We thus focus our discussion here on the main limitations of the current model formulation (essentially, the model equations) for each module or sphere.

On the environmental side, one key limitation is that resource use and pollution are currently calculated based on territorial accounting, thus not accounting for resource use and pollution embodied in imports and exports, which are often significant and which do not equally respond to the same policy levers. Moreover, resource use and pollution are calculated as the product of output and exogenous resource or pollution intensities, but do not differentiate specific processes, drivers or provisioning system characteristics that may affect their dynamics. For CO₂ emissions, for example, explicitly modelling energy systems, agriculture, mobility systems, and household direct emissions would offer a more differentiated representation of relevant dynamics and key factors like total energy use and the carbon intensity of the energy mix. Furthermore, a few planetary boundary indicators are not yet included in the model, for example Human Appropriation of Net Primary Production (HANPP). Similarly, currently only a subset of known environmental feedbacks (impacts of environmental change on society) are represented, with feedbacks related to soil quality and food production currently missing. Finally, our calculations of historical trends in resource or pollution intensity reduction (decoupling) are likely to be overestimates, as they are based on nominal output data and thus do not account for inflation.

On the social side, some wellbeing indicators are currently modelled in a rather simple way, with limited representation of relevant processes and drivers. Access to energy is currently represented only by linear extrapolation of its (flat) historical trend, and captures only access to electricity but not other important aspects like fuel poverty or access to residential energy services such as heating and cooling. Sanitation, nutrition, education, and connectivity are represented as simple functions of sectorial government or total expenditure only. Moreover, several wellbeing indicators that largely or fully reflect individual-level outcomes are currently only calculated at the aggregate level (life satisfaction, nutrition, education, social support, connectivity, access to energy) or calculated for each social group and employment status but reported only at the aggregate level (life expectancy, income adequacy, job availability), thus offering limited granularity. More broadly, the selection of wellbeing indicators currently represented in our model, based primarily on national-level representations of the Doughnut indicators (O’Neill et al., 2018; Fanning et al., 2022), is not necessarily a complete or perfect depiction of human wellbeing and human needs. For example, aspects like peace or housing (Raworth, 2017) or the affordability of essential goods and services (Vogel et al., 2024) are currently not represented. Finally, feedbacks from wellbeing outcomes back onto the economy (e.g. impacts of inequality on consumption) or demographics (e.g. impacts of nutrition on mortality rates or impacts of education on fertility rates) are currently not implemented. More generally, a more detailed representation of specific provisioning systems and the interdependence between production, consumption and provisioning system characteristics could offer a richer understanding of the integrated dynamics.

The accuracy of the simulations of the environmental and social indicators depends a lot on the accuracy of the simulations of the driving economic variables. Limitations of the economy module thus also propagate into the other modules, in an integrated model.

Given the complexity of the economy, the list of limitations of the economy module is long. First, the representation of economic dynamics is limited due to limited granularity, for example regarding sectorial disaggregation, differentiation of social strata (especially income and wealth strata), and differentiation of household types and related patterns of working time, consumption, benefits, and cost of living. In particular, children have zero income, and their consumption is considered only indirectly, as part of total household final demand. Per-capita income is uniform within each employment status and social group (including within the capitalist class), implying an underrepresentation of income and wealth inequality dynamics especially at the top. Also across existing social strata, the model does not currently account for how the propensity to consume varies with income (as well as with wealth, age and employment status), which may miss important distributional and aggregate dynamics. Lack of sectorial granularity also means that the energy sector is homogeneous, i.e. that there is no distinction between the fossil fuel sector and the renewable energy sector, which impedes modeling of the energy transition and the implementation of policies such as a carbon tax.

Second, the purely demand-driven representation of production does not incorporate supply constraints (e.g. shortages of labour, capital or intermediate inputs) nor constraints on lending (e.g. in the form of a leverage ratio), which also impedes the implementation of resource limits, climate damages, and other environmental feedbacks. Third, the representation of the financial system is minimal and does not incorporate interest rates on loans and government debt, private bond purchases, or mechanisms creating financial instability. Fourth, the labour force participation rate is currently held constant, rather than being a function of the employment rate (which stabilizes unemployment). Fifth, in the current model, all monetised production is performed by profit-making firms, thus not accounting for state provisioning or private not-for-profit provisioning. Similarly, sixth, all pensions are assumed to be state pensions. Moreover, eighth, non-monetised provisioning (e.g. subsistence production, gift economy, or unpaid care work) is currently not represented in the model at all. Finally, the model does not yet endogenously simulate technological change or other changes in relative inter-sector demand related to, for example, broader changes in provisioning systems. More broadly, options for representing structural changes in the current implementation are limited.

One overarching limitation of the model is that there is no endogenous representation of the socio-political dynamics of change. Moreover, international interactions are limited to trade flows, migration, and specific pollutants. International dynamics around global environmental change (e.g. links between national and international environmental policy) are not represented in the current model.

The outlined limitations provide ample room for future improvements and highlight promising avenues for future research. In addition to addressing these limitations, we also consider additional improvements that are not necessarily limitations of the model, for example the representation of time use, the implementation of additional policy levers, and the calculation of composite measures of progress such as the Index of Sustainable Economic Welfare.

9 Concluding remarks

As the famous quote goes, “all models are wrong, but some are useful” (Box and Draper, 2007, p. 414). The art of modelling a large, complicated, and complex system is about making simplifications without undermining the usefulness of the model. While the outlined limitations point to a lot of room for future improvements, we believe that the present model is nevertheless “useful”. Our model goes beyond most existing macroeconomic models in terms of its coverage of key environmental and social indicators – and partly also in terms of the sophistication of their representation. At the same time, our model also goes beyond most existing integrated assessment models in terms of the scope and granularity - and partly also the sophistication – of its representation of social indicators and national-level economic dynamics (especially from a heterodox economics perspective).

This model makes important contributions to our ability to holistically assess policy impacts and future pathways and thus to inform safe, just and resilient futures, while also paving the ground for further research and development in this area.

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11 Appendix

Table 1: EXIOBASE sectors used for the human nitrogen fixation calculations.

EXIOBASE rows
N - agriculture - water
N ₂ O - agriculture - air
NH ₃ - agriculture - air
NO _x - agriculture - air

Table 2: EXIOBASE sectors used for the atmospheric nitrogen fixation calculations.

EXIOBASE rows
N ₂ O - combustion - air
NO _x - combustion - air
NH ₃ - combustion - air
NH ₃ - non combustion - N- fertilizer production - air
NO _x - non combustion - Agglomeration plant - pellets - air
NO _x - non combustion - Agglomeration plant - sinter - air
NO _x - non combustion - Bricks production - air
NO _x - non combustion - Cement production - air
NO _x - non combustion - Chemical wood pulp, dissolving grades - air
NO _x - non combustion - Chemical wood pulp, soda and sulphate, other than dissolving grades - air
NO _x - non combustion - Chemical wood pulp, sulphite, other than dissolving grades - air
NO _x - non combustion - Glass production - air
NO _x - non combustion - Lime production - air
NO _x - non combustion - Nickel, unwrought - air
NO _x - non combustion - Oil refinery - air
NO _x - non combustion - Pig iron production, blast furnace - air
NO _x - non combustion - Production of coke oven coke - air
NO _x - non combustion - Production of gascoke - air
NO _x - non combustion - Refined copper; unwrought, not alloyed - air
NO _x - non combustion - Refined lead, unwrought - air
NO _x - non combustion - Semi-chemical wood pulp, pulp of fibers other than wood - air
NO _x - non combustion - Steel production: basic oxygen furnace - air
NO _x - non combustion - Steel production: electric arc furnace - air
NO _x - non combustion - Sulphuric acid production - air
NO _x - non combustion - Unrefined copper; copper anodes for electrolytic refining - air
NO _x - non combustion - Zinc, unwrought, not alloyed - air
NH ₃ - waste - air
NO _x - waste - air

Table 3: EXIOBASE sectors used for the phosphorus fixation calculations.

EXIOBASE rows
P - agriculture - water
P - agriculture - soil

Table 4: Nitrogen contents of different nitrogen compounds.

Compound name	Nitrogen content (g N/g compound)	Notes
N_2O	0.6365	Assuming NO_2 as reference
NH_3	0.822183	
NO_x	0.3044	
N	1	

Table 5: EXIOBASE rows used for CO_2 emissions.

EXIOBASE rows
CO_2 - combustion - air
CO_2 - non combustion - ...
CO_2 - agriculture - ...
CO_2 - waste - ...

Table 6: EXIOBASE sectors used for air pollution calculations.

EXIOBASE rows
NH_3 - combustion - ...
NH_3 - non combustion - ...
NH_3 - waste - ...
NO_x - combustion - ...
NO_x - non combustion - ...
NO_x - waste - ...
NMVOC - combustion - ...
NMVOC - non combustion - ...
PM25 - combustion - ...
PM25 - non combustion - ...
PM25 - waste - ...
SO_x - combustion - ...
SO_x - non combustion - ...
SO_x - waste - ...

Table 7: EXIOBASE rows used for energy use.

EXIOBASE rows
Energy Carrier Use: Total

Table 8: EXIOBASE rows used for material use.

EXIOBASE rows
Domestic Extraction Used - Crop residues - ...
Domestic Extraction Used - Fishery - ...
Domestic Extraction Used - Fodder crops - ...
Domestic Extraction Used - Forestry - ...
Domestic Extraction Used - Fossil Fuel: Total
Domestic Extraction Used - Grazing
Domestic Extraction Used - Metal Ores - ...
Domestic Extraction Used - Non-Metallic Minerals - ...
Domestic Extraction Used - Primary Crops - ...

Table 9: EXIOBASE rows used for blue water consumption.

EXIOBASE rows
Water Consumption Blue - Agriculture - ...
Water Consumption Blue - Livestock - ...
Water Consumption Blue - Manufacturing - ...
Water Consumption Blue - Electricity - ...

Table 10: EXIOBASE rows used for PM2.5 emissions.

EXIOBASE rows
PM2.5 - combustion - ...
PM2.5 - non combustion - ...
PM2.5 - waste - ...

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- Other v.3.8.2 is a minor bug-fix update fixing (1) extension data of the ixi tables has been one year off (2) HFC and PFC were set to zero by PRIMAP rescaling to native units rather than CO2-eq.

- (3) the D_cba_reg and D_pba_reg (total regional accounts) did not include the household emissions
- (4) Revision to industry CO₂ process emissions were made, with PRIMAP data remapped from the whole sector to only cement production. Fixing 3. includes renaming the household stressor/impact file to F_Y (was F_hh previously). The full changelog can be found in the readme file included in the upload.
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